

MATILDE

Migration Impact Assessment to Enhance
Integration and Local Development in
European Rural and Mountain Regions

Collection of European best- practices on the integration of TCNs

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Deliverable 6.9

Collection of European best-practices on the integration of TCNs

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Introduction

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1. Aim

According to the Grant Agreement (No. 870831 2019, p. 120), this report is a collection of European best-practices of policy objectives and their implementation for the integration of TCNs. Therefore, different governmental levels as well as the different areas of integration, e.g. employment, housing or social connection (Ager & Strang 2008, 170; adapted by Weidinger et al. 2017; further extended by Gruber et. al. 2020) are considered. Apart from policies, practices should also be documented that can be considered as “good” or “new” practice in their design. This tool is intended to support the work of policy makers at all levels, from local to European.

Even though it is stated as “best practices”, there is always room for improvements and “good practices, or best practices, are, sometimes, used with the same meaning.” (Mateus & Pinho 2018, p. 3). Hence, the term “good practice” is used in the following. The term “good” should indicate that this example can serve as a model for other practices as well as policy objectives and their implementation, which provides the incentive for replication, but can still be surpassed in terms of innovation, for example, with subsequent designs. However, “new” practices that are innovative, but have not yet been evaluated, however, have the potential to become good practices, should also be taken into account.

2. Definition

In this sense, a good practice is defined as “approaches, experiences or initiatives that are working well and can be replicated elsewhere, with techniques and methods that produce effects and results, considered to be effective in contributing to refugees welcoming and integration, and therefore deserving to be disseminated and proposed to other organisational contexts.” (Mateus & Pinho 2018, p. 3). The good practice can also take, according to Mateus and Pinho (2018, p. 3), the shape of a “process” or an “intervention”. What seems important is its transferability.

The International Organization for Migration (2004, p. 9) characterizes best practices additionally as “being innovative, developing creative solutions; showing a positive impact (...); having a

sustainable effect, especially by involving migrants themselves; and having the potential for replication”.

The Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (2016, p. 2) adds that a good practice “has been proven to work well and produce good results, and is therefore recommended as a model. It is a successful experience, which has been tested and validated, in the broad sense, which has been repeated and deserves to be shared so that a greater number of people can adopt it”. If the practice fulfills these criteria, it can be recommended as a model (Mateus and Pinho, 2018, p. 4). The recommendability itself serves as a criterion to classify a practice as a good practice. If a practice can serve as a model for others, the central aspect of mutual learning is stressed. To apply knowledge to new situations and to meet new challenges, based on existing good practices, can be seen as the heart of a good practices (Mateus and Pinho, 2018, p. 4).

To conclude based on the given definitions, a good practice can be an approach, experience or initiative, but also a process or intervention, or be in the shape of norms and principles, or directives. In the MATILDE project, however, we want to go one step further and consider also different forms of policies, as defined above, as good practices.

3. Criteria to serve as “good practices”

Following the definitions, the central criteria which have to be fulfilled by an approach, initiative, policy, etc. to be considered as a good practice, are:

- be innovative;
- develop creative solutions;
- succeed in achieving its objective(s);
- ethical (also in terms of participatory, based on/supporting democratic values strengthening empowerment);
- fair;
- proven (ideally: has been tested and validated) to work well and produce good results,
- replicable;
- serve as a model, which can be shared so that it can be adopted by a greater number of people.

When it comes to the topic of migration and integration, further criteria, as outlined by the International Organization for Migration (2004, p. 9), have to be considered:

- “showing a positive impact on the level of implementation of migrants’ rights;
- having a sustainable effect, especially by involving migrants themselves;
- and having the potential for replication.”

As mentioned before by (Mateus & Pinho 2018, p. 3), the good practice should also contribute to feel welcome and supports the integration processes.

OSCE/ODIHR (2018, p. 55ff.) have developed key principles for good practices in migrant integration:

- Participatory approaches to migrant integration policies by involving non-state actors, civil society organisations and trade unions in the process and in the implementation;
- Effective co-ordination mechanisms for the involvement of different governmental levels and various non-governmental actors;
- Financial backing, and effective funding distribution mechanisms in order to enable responsible actors for the implementation;
- Inclusiveness of migrant integration policies by taking their diversity and in consequence their needs and backgrounds into consideration;
- Gender sensitivity through the assessment of power relations, risks and vulnerabilities;
- Monitoring and evaluation in order to compare the initial aims with actual outcomes.

4. Procedure for selection “good practices”

For the selection of the MATILDE good practices, the research partner reviewed and evaluated practices and policy objectives along the aforementioned indications. However, not all listed indications have to be fulfilled, to consider it as a pre-selected good practice. Those pre-selected practices and policies were discussed and validated with different types of stakeholders in order to select those good practices, which are included in the European best-practices on integration of TCNs below.

In order to standardise the selected good practices, a template based on Mateus and Pinho (2018, pp. 40-43) was provided. The first section is served for general information about the type, area of action based on the mid-level theory of Ager & Strang (2008; adapted by Weidinger et al. 2017; further extended by Gruber et. al. 2020), adopting body, governmental level and location as well as responsibility and duration. The second section frames the content of the good/new practice by describing the main goals and target group(s) including information about the methodology,

background information as well as results and impacts, innovativeness and encountered challenges. The third section clarifies about the framework conditions for the implementation and possibilities of extension or up-scaling. The fourth section explains, why this good practice was selected, and includes information about its validation and evaluation. In the final section, the sources are provided. Additionally, most of the selected good practices are accompanied by a checklist, that includes the most important criteria and indicators questioning, if the selected example can be considered as good practice for the collection fo European best-practice on integration of TCNs. Hence, the checklist was intended to be a tool to critically evaluate, if the selected example meets the requirements and criteria. This evaluation was provided by the MATILDE research partners in cooperation with a responsible person of the selected examples and included additionally criteria such as gender sensitiveness, improvement of migrant's rights, inclusiveness with regard to people with a migrant background, or the ability to foster societal diversity. The results of this evaluation can be found after the description of the respective good practice example.

The good practices collected in this report can also be found on a map that displays the selected MATILDE good practices geographically and includes some basic information. This map is available online <https://www.camposaz.com/portfolio/2525-bussoleno/>.

5. Bibliography

Ager, A. & Strang, A. (2008): Understanding Integration: A Conceptual Framework. *Journal of Refugee Studies*, 21(2), pp. 166-191. DOI:10.1093/jrs/fen016.

Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (FAO) (2016): Good practices template. <https://www.fao.org/3/as547e/as547e.pdf> (last accessed: 5.8.2021).

Gruber, M./Lobnig, C./Scheiflinger, S./Stainer-Hämmerle, K. (2020): Stakeholder Involvement Plan. MATILDE Deliverable 2.8. Version 1.1. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.4005933. https://matilde-migration.eu/wp-content/uploads/2020/09/Stakeholder_Involvement_Plan.pdf (accessed last: 06.07.2022).

International Organization for Migration – IOM (2004): Glossary on Migration. International Migration Law. Geneva: IOM. https://publications.iom.int/system/files/pdf/iml_1_en.pdf (last accessed: 5.8.2021).

Global Migration Data Portal (2021): Migration data and the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGS). <https://www.migrationdataportal.org/sdgs?node=0> (accessed last: 6.8.2021).

Mateus, S. and Pinho, F. (2018): “Welcome!” – Collection of good practices already existing for refugees’ welcoming and first inclusion. http://www.pandpasproject.eu/wp-content/uploads/2018/10/Good_Practices.pdf (last accessed: 26.7.2021).

OSCE/ODIHR (2018): Good practices in migrant integration: trainee’s manual. Warsaw: OSCE/ODIHR. <https://www.osce.org/files/f/documents/a/2/393554.pdf> (accessed last: 5.8.2021).

Solano, G. & Huddleston, T. (2020): Migrant Integration Policy Index 2020. <https://www.mipex.eu/> (accessed last: 17.11.2022).

Weidinger, T., Kordel, S., & Pohle, P. (2017): Bleiben oder Gehen? Einflussfaktoren auf die Wohnstandortmobilität anerkannter Flüchtlinge in ländlichen Räumen am Beispiel des Bayerischen Waldes. Europa Regional, 24, 3-4, pp. 46–61.

Austria, Carinthia

Author: Isabel Brugger (CIC) with contributions from Kathrin Zupan (CUAS)

Dual Career Couples	
General information	
Type of good/new practice	The aim of the programme for Dual Career Couples is to support candidates on their way into the primary labour market through training, workshops and coaching, who want to expand their skills and work experience in an international environment.
Area of action	Language & culture (economy and employment)
Adopting body	Private actors (NGO)
Level of good/new practice	Regional
Location and geographical coverage	Carinthia
Responsibility for good practice	CIC plus its 39 member companies, City of Villach & Klagenfurt, Carinthian Economic Promotion Fund, Federation of Austrian Industries, Kärntner Berufsförderungsinstitut (Carinthian Vocational Training Institute), Austrian Public Employment Service, Regional Government of Carinthia
Duration	Programm Dual Career Couples → Unlimited (Start 2017)
Key words	Recruiting measure, sector-specific, tailor-made, qualification-adequate, intercultural
Content of the good/new practice	
Objectives of the good/new practice	<p>The aim is to accompany candidates in the Dual Career Couples Programme with tailor-made and sector-specific language courses, career workshops and career orientation programmes on their way into work and to match the partners' existing potential with vacancies in the labour market.</p> <p>CIC offers four different career paths, individually tailored to the personal development goals of the participants:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. coaching & training to accompany them on their way into the primary labour market;

	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 2. coaching & training to accompany them on their way to self-employment; 3. persons practising special professions for which a recognition process/nostrification of certificates is required (e.g. doctors, physiotherapists, speech therapists, psychologists, ...); 4. support on the way to achieving an additional university qualification.
Target group(s)	Partners of (international) employees
Methodology	Assessment, workshops, trainings; coaching, job placement
Key facts	After the assessment, tailor-made career path journey
Background information	The need to find a job / career in your new home. High potential for Carinthia
Achieved results	<p>Year 2021:</p> <p>21 persons successfully placed,</p> <p>4 persons in self-employment (e.g. DIP & More Villach Dip and more - Sweets And Dessert Buffet in Villach https://dipandmore.business.site/)</p>
Impacts of the good/new practice	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - New employees for companies - Finding a job AND a new home - Certification, prizes etc. - Inclusion of the aspect "Rural Development", gain for the region (also companies) through immigration - New perspectives through intercultural/multilingual settings
Innovativeness	<p>The focus is on the family members of internationally recruited employees and their integration processes.</p> <p>International employees tend to stay in a region like Carinthia, when the whole family feels at home and integrated. Hence, the Dual Career Couples Programme aims to support the integration of family members in order to increase the possibility of the international family to stay in Carinthia, which has a positive impact on the society, the region, the company, etc.</p>
Constraints	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Language (German) in the companies (different requirements men/women e.g. language level must perform better) - Mindset (Change)

	- Childcare (lack of places and flexible models, connection to language courses...)
Replicability	
Replication conditions and success factors	Dual Career Program, strong collaboration with the regional companies, strong network with the cities and the institutions
Replicability and/or up-scaling	Very high possibilities to extend it all over Austria. Then, CIC could possibly take over a advisory function for initiatives in other provinces/regions/countries, as the CIC-program in this form has a unique selling proposition in Austria. For a replicability process the tailor-made aspect needs to be considered to focus on the specifics of the respective region. Then the transferability is given, but not in an one-fits-all approach. The regional focus, the regional network as well as theregional economic prerequisite must be included.)
Selection of good practice	
Reasons for choosing the good/new practice	CIC makes the candidates visible – instead of staying at home, the full potential of the (mainly) women is unleashed. Through visibility, they get and connected proactively with the best fit company / work. This provides a strong impact also for the cities as well as the region of Carinthia.
Selection of European good/new practices	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Transferability to other regions; - All-encompassing offer in exchange with the companies, regional institutions etc.; - interconnection of different areas of integration; - individual approach and focus on the individual skills, strengths and aims of each participant - cooperation with many different companies and stakeholders in the region
Personal experiences	CIC and its different initiatives was involved in the MATILDE project from the beginning as a stakeholder, who provides information, expertise and support. Representatives of CIC and participants of the “Dual Couples Career” were participants of the action research and involved in the policy roundtables. Other interview partner referred to the CIC and its initiatives. The CIC’s relevance in the region and for the

	economy in Carinthia is confirmed by different stakeholder from CUAS.
Validation/evaluation external	Certification of CERT NÖ (University of Continuing Education Krems) already awarded and of ÖCERT (Qualitätsrahmen für Erwachsenenbildung in Österreich) in process. Both are certification bodies for quality assurance and development in educational institutions for adults.
Validation/evaluation by project team	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Interviews, focus groups → Reference to CIC; - Well-known in Carinthia; - Needs of important economic players are served;
Sources	
Source(s) to the good/new practice	https://www.cic-network.at/arbeit/karriere/cic-jobservice-programm/
Date of documentation	02.08.2022

Figure 1 – Dual Career Couples © Stefano Lunardi

Checklist for good/new practice selection

The selected good/new practice ...	
is innovative.	Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> In what way?: The program has an impact beyond it.
develops creative solutions.	Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> In what way?: Finding tailor-made solutions for our candidates.
succeeds in achieving its objective(s).	Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> In what way?: See success.
is ethical.	Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> In what way?: Focus on the needs of the person, not “one fits all” – taking the personal preferences and conditions into consideration.
is fair.	Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> In what way?: Giving a voice to those who are not heard and making visible all the potential.
Is been proven/evaluated (ideally: has been tested and validated) to work well and produce good results.	Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> In what way?: In the certification process.
is replicable.	Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> In what way?: Partially – the “tailor-made approach” needs to be created individually.
improves migrants’ rights.	Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>

	<p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?:</p> <p>Right to find an adequate job for the high qualified persons.</p>
is inclusive with regard to people with a migrant background.	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?:</p> <p>Most of our candidates have an international background.</p>
works with a whole of government approach.	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?:</p> <p>Strong collaboration with Land Kärnten, ABA (Austrian Business Agency), City of Villach and Klagenfurt.</p>
improves the well-being of migrants	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?:</p> <p>Finding a work is finding a home 😊</p>
is gender sensitive.	<p>Yes ABSOLUTLY YES</p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?:</p> <p>Most of our candidates are women.</p>
fosters societal diversity.	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?:</p> <p>By introducing intercultural and multilingual persons.</p>
develops possibilities for a safe and orderly regular migration.	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?:</p> <p>By supporting and accompanying the persons through a tailor-made process.</p>
realizes a participatory and/or multi-level governance approach.	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?:</p> <p>Working close together with companies and institutions.</p>
promotes effective funding mechanism.	<p>Yes <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?:</p>

Authors: Burgi Decker and Jacqueline ten Haken (PIVA) with contributions from Jessica Pöcher and Kathrin Zupan (CUAS)

Alpha Project	
General information	
Type of good/new practice	Education, Social Support and Counselling for everyone
Area of action	Education, social cohesion, language & culture, rights & citizenship
Adopting body	Non-governmental adopted by NGOs, volunteer- or other private actors
Level of good/new practice	Local
Location and geographical coverage	Villach, Carinthia (Austria)
Responsibility for good practice	PIVA (is Part of the Social Network in Carinthia)
Duration	Since 25 years and ongoing
Key words	Education, Social Support, Counselling
Content of the good/new practice	
Objectives of the good/new practice	Alpha Project of PIVA is a best practice. It offers language education for migrated mothers with simultaneous childcare for pre-kindergarten-kids. Additionally, educational support for school children, combined with social support through social workers, is part of the support. Once migrants speak German, PIVA also supports them in further education. The Alpha Project is successful due to teamwork with social workers within PIVA and with other organizations active in social work. PIVA even works with a pool of interpreters to support clients for example in court or in hospital if needed. One evening a week, the clients receive information on actual topics (e.g.: Corona, Tax, Housing etc.).
Target group(s)	Migrants: mainly mothers in need of childcare, but also male migrants and Austrians with migrant background
Methodology	Teaching German language courses; preparing students for exams; providing professional childcare (for 1 - 5-year-old) while mothers are attending language courses; preparing children to go to kindergarten; supporting school children with homework from school while parents are at work; supporting older pupils in the preparation of their final exams

	and adult students in vocational education; providing social support through in-house social workers; networking with other social workers in the region
Key facts	Small team of professionals in migrant's counselling and support: 3 social workers, 3 language teachers and 2 childcare workers. Support of long-term volunteers Networking in the region with other social workers, with the City of Villach
Background information	True integration is only possible when migrants speak the local language and know the rules and values of the local society. Therefore, they need to be supported.
Achieved results	One example: a young lady from Afghanistan and mother of 3 kids came to PIVA some years ago without any educational background. She learned German up to level B1 in the language courses there and was taught in primary school education during 1 year with one-on-one teaching from a former high school teacher and graduated afterwards successfully. Now, she wants to become a pharmacy assistant while learning on the job in a pharmacy and studying all needed theory in school. She hopes to get the apprentice at the pharmacy to learn and work there.
Impacts of the good/new practice	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Support for the family system • Long-term support • Fixed point of reference for clients • Prevent dropouts • Language courses are a neutral gateway to further counselling and support services
Innovativeness	Former clients become supporters/future staff and multipliers mainly through translating activities. Flexibility of PIVA's structure, organization size also has an impact on the given flexibility of PIVA ("self-supported team")
Constraints	Dealing with clients who have never been to school and who are in the need of literacy courses to learn, how to learn. No training available in Carinthia for language trainer. Cases where there is no sense of achievement

	<p>A lot of documentation and reporting work for funding agencies, long applications, disadvantage with projects lasting several years limits adaptations to current situations. Then changes are only possible with difficulties.</p> <p>Overlapping of systems, competition among providers resulting in constantly changing group dynamics</p>
Replicability	
Replication conditions and success factors	<p>Secure framework conditions and infrastructure (premises, funding, staff, (well-established) network).</p> <p>Constant team (building up expertise, clear roles and tasks, basis of trust in the network and with the clients)</p>
Replicability and/or up-scaling	<p>Rather at a local level, but there is a need for such counselling, support services in every district of Carinthia, for example.</p> <p>Local is an important factor, because the local structure is also a success factor → local conditions are included in the work, which cannot be transferred to all.</p>
Selection of good practice	
Reasons for choosing the good/new practice	Organization with unique selling proposition, with all-round advice and support, no one is left behind
Selection of European good/new practices	Continuous cooperation, commitment, Provision of expertise
Personal experiences	Both – the research and the local - partners know PIVA since years and are constantly cooperating with PIVA.
Validation/evaluation external	<p>Participation in well-known, large networks in Carinthia</p> <p>Since 2017 ÖIF certified (all trainers)</p> <p>2003 Human Rights Award for German courses with childcare</p> <p>2006 Prize of the “SozialMarie”</p> <p>2009 Medal of Honour of the City of Villach for the former chairwoman Dr. Hedwig Tortschanoff</p>
Validation/evaluation by project team	Long-term cooperation, expertise, fix player in the social network in Villach
Sources	
Source(s) to the good/new practice	Website: https://www.piva.or.at/
Date of documentation	02.08.2022

Figure 2 – Alpha Project © PIVA

Checklist for good/new practice selection

The selected good/new practice ...	
is innovative.	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?: Because the project evolves ongoing through adaptation to current needs.</p>
develops creative solutions.	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?: e.g. with the lockdown due to the COVID-19 measures, PIVA quickly transferred the language courses in online settings and still kept the contact and network with clients.</p>
succeeds in achieving its objective(s).	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?: Act according to the situation (legal framework, different migration flows).</p>
is ethical.	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p>

	<p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?:</p> <p>Yes, anyone can come and take advantage of the offer.</p>
is fair.	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?:</p> <p>Yes, anyone can come and take advantage of the offer.</p>
Is been proven/evaluated (ideally: has been tested and validated) to work well and produce good results.	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?:</p> <p>Reference to certifications and personal success stories and is also audited by the Ministry and different other funding representatives.</p>
is replicable.	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?:</p> <p>Yes, at local level.</p>
improves migrants' rights.	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?:</p> <p>Yes/No?</p> <p>Cannot improve rights, but supports clients; Nevertheless, PIVA constantly creates awareness among political representatives within their network and in official meetings, when they know about structural discrimination in law, authorities or regulations, etc.</p>
is inclusive regarding people with a migrant background.	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?:</p> <p>Inclusion is the aim of the organization, where many staff members also have a migration background, which additionally leads to synergy effects (e.g. when former course participants become multipliers etc.)</p>
works with a whole of government approach.	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?:</p>

	Close cooperation with the City of Villach, the provincial government, etc. but keeps a critical attitude towards legal frameworks.
improves the well-being of migrants	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?:</p> <p>Migrants look for help to help themselves. They make use of the offered services and support each other as multipliers in the PIVA network. Hence, they are able to participate in the local society.</p>
is gender sensitive.	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?:</p> <p>Special projects and offers for migrant women.</p>
fosters societal diversity.	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p>
develops possibilities for a safe and orderly regular migration.	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?:</p> <p>PIVA informs and helps their clients, when they get the chance of family reunification. For the newly arriving family members, language courses and childcare can be organized ahead.</p>
fosters preparedness and resilience to migration events/crises.	<p>Yes <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p>
promotes effective funding mechanism.	<p>Yes <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p>
fosters effective monitoring and evaluation approaches.	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?:</p> <p>Due to the funding of projects, PIVA is constantly evaluated and monitored by the funding representatives.</p>

Author: Lisa Fian (Diakonie de La Tour)

A:Life 2.0 – Asyl & Lehre in Kärnten	
General information	
Type of good/new practice	Training, coaching and follow up support for recognized refugees within the Carinthian labor market
Area of action	<p>Economy & employment: Since the project aims to match potential employees (pref. apprenticeships) with Carinthian companies in a sustainable way, it has two main impacts on different levels. (I) empowerment and self-reliance for a vulnerable target group in Carinthia and (II) it can be seen as an answer to the current skill shortage.</p> <p>Education: Throughout the project participants get to undergo a 4-month phase of formal qualification. During those four months subjects as German language, mathematics and computing are taught by professional trainers. In addition, participants learn about relevant topics such as rights and responsibilities as employees, dept prevention and so on.</p> <p>Safety & stability / social cohesion: During the whole project phase participants are supervised, coached and advised by a multiprofessional team consisting of social workers, social education workers and psychologists (i.T.) as well as language and culture interpreters. That way participants get a holistic support and mentoring which helps them to meet challenges regarding their very personal life world.</p> <p>Regional development: Within seven rounds of A:Life “Asyl & Lehre in Kärnten” since 2016 a very stable cooperation with industrial companies, such as small and middle businesses has been built up by the project team. That is why every year many participants get the chance to proof themselves in various working areas. P.e. through internships, practical training and more. In return those companies know about the holistic approach and like to use the team of social professionals as contact persons as well. That is why the</p>

	annual percentage of participants who get a sustainable job offer lies nearly at 80%.
Adopting body	Diakonie de La Tour (NGO) – Lead ESF – funding authority (I) Land Kärnten, Abt. 11 – funding authority (II) Austrian Employment Service (AMS) – cooperation and funding partner
Level of good/new practice	Regional (Centre of Carinthia)
Location and geographical coverage	Carinthia, especially Klagenfurt (Land), Villach (Land), St. Veit, Feldkirchen and Wolfsberg.
Responsibility for good practice	Diakonie de La Tour – social services for holistic support Bfi Klagenfurt – educational service for formal qualification Beirat – consisting of important stakeholder such as the AMS, the chamber of commerce (WKO), the Federation of Industry (IV) for exchange and valuable feedback throughout the whole project and beyond.
Duration	January 2021 – December 2022
Key words	Holistic support to enforce a sustainable placement of recognized refugees at the Carinthian labor market.
Content of the good/new practice	
Objectives of the good/new practice	Holistic support to enforce a sustainable placement of recognized refugees at the Carinthian labor market.
Target group(s)	Recognized Refugees in Central Carinthia from 16 to 30 years old.
Methodology	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> (I) Formal qualification of participants during a several months long training phase. Subjects are german language, mathematics, IT and workshops containing important subject matters of the Austrian labor market. (II) Individual case management with a holistic approach to coach and advice participants throughout different challenges. (III) Well approved linkage to various institutions of social services within Carinthia. (IV) Peer education by implementing former participants in actual project round as multipliers.

Key facts	Through the holistic approach regarding formal and informal support of participants, and the good linkage to Carinthian companies and key stakeholders the main goal of sustainable job placement gets achieved on a high percentage (around 80% each year).
Background information	Integration of migrants and refugees through sustainable job placement in order to pave the way for a self-determined life here in Austria. Furthermore the project also has a positive input for the Carinthian Economy.
Achieved results	Since 2016 (first round of “A:Life – Asyl & Lehre in Kärnten”) placement percentage of nearly 80% (of 30 annual participants) can be recorded..
Impacts of the good/new practice	Since 2016 the project takes place on an annual base and supports around 30 participants (mostly recognized refugees) to prepare for the Carinthian Labor market
Innovativeness	<p>Projects, regarding the labor market integration of recognized refugees do not always provide 6 months after care. Therefore A:Life can be considered as innovative because by providing this aftercare a sustainable job placement and support through any other situation regarding the living environment of participants (such as housing, financial struggles, relationships and so on) can be achieved more frequently.</p> <p>Furthermore the project is incorporated with a consistent Beirat where the project lead can discuss the actual situation on the labor market for recognized refugees with key stakeholders.</p>
Constraints	<p>In addition to constant constraints regarding recognized refugees and their integration on the Austrian labor market, the covid pandemic posed a main obstacle during the last two years.</p> <p>Internships couldn't be organized, the qualification was characterized by regular testing, a plus on paperwork, cancelled excursions and so on. But that is certainly a topic everybody had to deal with.</p>

Replicability	
Replication conditions and success factors	<p>Since the project A:Life has been carried out seven times already, the replication conditions seem fairly accurate.</p> <p>Through the holistic approach, the good working cooperation with companies, the implementation of the Beirat and the current situation of the Carinthian labor market, A:Life has quite some success factors.</p>
Replicability and/or up-scaling	
Selection of good practice	
Reasons for choosing the good/new practice	<p>The labour market in Carinthia and especially in tourism and gastronomy is lacking of skilled workers, even though it is an important economic branch in the province. In parallel, young refugees living in Carinthia are willing to work. Hence, the project A:Life is a win-win-situation at individual level for the refugees, at meta level for the companies (hotels, restaurants, etc.) and at meso level for the region.</p>
Selection of European good/new practices	<p>As many European rural and mountain regions are facing a lack of (skilled) workforce, the project might be leading by example for other European regions.</p>
Personal experiences	<p>The research partner knows Diakonie de La Tour and their integration projects since years and is constantly cooperating with Diakonie de La Tour.</p>
Validation/evaluation external	<p>The funding bodies (AMS, ESF and Land Kärnten) regularly evaluate the project via indicators and successes in job placements.</p> <p>Additionally, A:Life is the follow-up project of TourIK, which was scientifically evaluated by CUAS.</p>
Validation/evaluation by project team	<p>As the MATILDE interviews/focus groups have shown, important economic players in Carinthia are cooperating with Diakonie de La Tour, in order to young motivated refugees for apprenticeships.</p>
Sources	
Source(s) to the good/new practice	<p>(I) Annual reports by the AMS</p> <p>(II) Feedback from companies within the Carinthian Labor Market.</p> <p>(III) Feedback from former participants.</p>

	(IV) Active exchange with key stakeholders such as Carinthian industry, the WKO and others.
Date of documentation	05.08.2022/20.08.2022/15.09.2022/26.09.2022

Figure 3 - A:Life 2.0 (1) © Diakonie de La Tour

Checklist for good/new practice selection

The selected good/new practice ...	
is innovative.	Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> In what way?: The holistic approach regarding the coaching, support and advising participants by the social team can be seen as very innovative compared to similar projects in Carinthia. Furthermore the project implemented a regular Beirat consisting of key stakeholders of the Carinthian labor market.
develops creative solutions.	Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>

<p>succeeds in achieving its objective(s).</p>	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?:</p> <p>Percentage of placement report by the AMS and the fulfillment of indicators by the ESF in many parts. Placement report by the AMS (2021) = 79,4%</p>
<p>is ethical.</p>	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p>
<p>is fair.</p>	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p>
<p>Is been proven/evaluated (ideally: has been tested and validated) to work well and produce good results.</p>	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?:</p> <p>The project is evaluated on a yearly base by the AMS and the funding authorities. Furthermore the project team of Diakonie de La Tour is always aiming to improve their offers and services to participants and Carinthian companies.</p>
<p>is replicable.</p>	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p>
<p>improves migrants' rights.</p>	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?:</p> <p>Universal Declaration of Human Rights Art. 23</p> <p>Everyone has the right to work.</p> <p>Furthermore, having a regular income is one of the key features of social participation.</p>
<p>is inclusive with regard to people with a migrant background.</p>	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?:</p> <p>The main target group for the project are recognized refugees or people with a migrant background in central Carinthia.</p>
<p>works with a whole of government approach.</p>	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?:</p>

	Land Kärnten (Carinthia's government) as a main funding authority and partner.
improves the well-being of migrants	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?: Empowerment and self-reliance through education, work experience and sustainable placement. In addition participants get support in any challenges regarding their life world.</p>
is gender sensitive.	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?: Women get preferred regarding places within the project in case they are equally or almost equally qualified to participate.</p>
develops possibilities for a safe and orderly regular migration.	<p>Yes <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p>

Figure 4 - A:Life 2.0 (2) © Markus Korenjak

Austria, Vorarlberg

Authors: Lisa Bauchinger and Ingrid Machold (BAB)

Neighbourhood aid	
General information	
Type of good/new practice	Project
Area of action	Economy & employment
Adopting body	Non-governmental body Caritas Vorarlberg
Level of good/new practice	Regional
Location and geographical coverage	All private households in Vorarlberg could participate
Responsibility for good practice	Caritas Vorarlberg
Duration	1993-2016, Since 2017 the project continues in a modified form under the project title "Integration Activities"
Key words	Employment on an hourly basis for asylum seekers, integration, social connection
Content of the good/new practice	
Objectives of the good/new practice	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Enable employment while waiting for the interview for the recognition; • Provide asylum seekers with a modest remuneration
Target group(s)	Female and male adult asylum seekers
Methodology	Caritas matched asylum seekers with individuals in need of support in housekeeping and gardening; remuneration on an hourly basis
Key facts	Asylum seekers, who are not allowed to find regular work in Austria, were able to take on temporary jobs helping people in their homes and gardens. They were financially compensated for this work and received 4€ per hour. The money was raised from donations by Caritas.
Background information	Asylum seekers waiting for their asylum status in Austria (still) do not have a general access to the labour market. A labour market review is needed to ensure, that there are no other interested persons with access to labour market. For this

	reason, Caritas Vorarlberg initiated the project “Nachbarschaftshilfe” (neighbourhood aid).
Achieved results	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Facilitate and ameliorate the exchange between asylum seekers and locals; • The facilitation of exchange between locals and asylum seekers also supported asylum seekers in finding a job after recognition; • Giving asylum seekers some kind of regular structure in daily life; • Increase of visibility of asylum seekers in the municipalities and to reduction of prejudices;
Impacts of the good/new practice	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The visibility of their work was the most important feature besides having personal contact with predominately elderly locals. Neighbourhood activities contradicted the image of “being lazy” or “exploiters of the social system”. • Regular contacts/friendships were created between locals and asylum seekers, which helped the asylum seekers later on to find jobs, housing, etc.
Innovativeness	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Improve contact between locals and asylum seekers; • Asylum seekers were provided with a modest remuneration;
Constraints	In 2016, the Austrian Ministry of Social Affairs and the Financial Police saw a violation under the Aliens Employment Act and Federal Law on Basic Services and demanded the project to be terminated. Since then, the project continues in a modified form. Under the project title “Integration Activities,” asylum seekers can take on little jobs for federal, state and local government institutions as well as for private individuals with social need.
Replicability	
Replication conditions and success factors	Legal framework must allow asylum seekers to do jobs with remuneration
Replicability and/or up-scaling	Due to legal restrictions neighbourhood aid is not possible any more. However, the project continues in a “slimmed down” version, where direct exchange between locals and asylum seekers is strongly reduced: “Integration Activities,” asylum seekers can take on little jobs for federal, state and

	local government institutions as well as for private individuals with social need.
Selection of good practice	
Reasons for choosing the good/new practice	Almost all volunteers interviewed during the case study project mentioned this project as a very successful tool to integrate forced migrants in the local society.
Selection of European good/new practices	The project was a very important tool to foster social integration (direct contact between locals and asylum seekers, etc.).
Personal experiences	No.
Validation/evaluation external	No. However, interviewed regional stakeholders, such as Caritas, mayors, etc., as well as asylum seekers and volunteers mentioned the importance of the project.
Validation/evaluation by project team	Interviewed regional stakeholders, such as Caritas, mayors, etc., as well as asylum seekers and volunteers mentioned the importance of the project.
Sources	
Source(s) to the good/new practice	https://www.caritas-vorarlberg.at/hilfe-angebote/fluechtlinge/aufeinander-zugehen/integrationstaetigkeiten
Date of documentation	30.05.2022

Figure 5 – Neighborhood aid © Pexel Campus Production

Checklist for good/new practice selection

The selected good/new practice ...	
is innovative.	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?:</p> <p>The project improved exchange between locals and asylum seekers and asylum seekers were provided with a modest remuneration.</p> <p>It highlights the value of social integration, being visible and useful in a local community.</p>
develops creative solutions.	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?:</p> <p>Creative solutions for locals, mostly elderly, who needed help in the garden or in the house.</p> <p>Creative solution for asylum seekers to have an occupation, a small remuneration and social contacts with locals.</p>

succeeds in achieving its objective(s).	Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> In what way?: Very much, but legal restrictions were hindering.
is ethical.	Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/>
is fair.	Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> In what way?: The remuneration was small, but within the legal framework it was a fair agreement.
Is been proven/evaluated (ideally: has been tested and validated) to work well and produce good results.	Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
is replicable.	Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/>
improves migrants' rights.	Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
is inclusive with regard to people with a migrant background.	Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> In what way?: Increase of visibility, important to be of help and part of the local community.
works with a whole of government approach.	Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
improves the well-being of migrants	Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> In what way?: Asylum seekers a small remuneration, they gain structures in their daily life, they are able to be off help and return the friendliness they have encountered (be part of the local community).
is gender sensitive.	Yes <input type="checkbox"/>

	<p>No <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?: It referred to both men and women.</p>
fosters societal diversity.	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?: Increase of visibility of asylum seekers at the local level.</p>
develops possibilities for a safe and orderly regular migration.	<p>Yes <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p>
fosters preparedness and resilience to migration events/crises.	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?: Important for local development and visibility of forced migrants since the asylum seekers get in direct contact and exchange with locals. Time bridging for asylum seekers until their recognition.</p>
realizes a participatory and/or multi-level governance approach.	<p>Yes <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p>
promotes effective funding mechanism.	<p>Yes <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p>
fosters effective monitoring and evaluation approaches.	<p>Yes <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p>

Authors: Lisa Bauchinger and Ingrid Machold (BAB)

Regional and municipal coordinators of refugee integration	
General information	
Type of good/new practice	Service
Area of action	Social cohesion, language & culture
Adopting body	Provincial authority & municipalities
Level of good/new practice	Provincial
Location and geographical coverage	Almost all municipalities of Vorarlberg
Responsibility for good practice	Province of Vorarlberg
Duration	2015 until 2023
Key words	Coordination of refugee care, consultation, networking, local development
Content of the good/new practice	
Objectives of the good/new practice	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Consulting and accompanying activities for refugees (providing information, registration for German courses, support for administrative work needed for the authorities, such as explaining of official documents, filling out forms, etc., finding housing, job or an apprenticeship, etc.); • Implementation of projects for refugees (cycling courses, low-threshold German classes, etc.); • Coordination and support of volunteers engaged in refugee care (matching volunteers and refugees, supporting volunteers during the implementation of projects such as cooking groups, low-threshold German classes, encounter cafés, etc., intervision and reflection opportunities for volunteers in the context of one-on-one discussions and further training, etc.); • Constant information exchange between regional coordinators, municipalities and all relevant stakeholders engaged in integration work (providing information about integration activities and responsibilities, advising and accompanying municipalities in integration activities, supporting the conceptualization and implementation of

	<p>projects, and establishing networks between municipalities);</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Advising institutions of the regular system, such as schools and kindergartens. Joint implementation of projects, such as Parent Education Services; • Coordination with those organizations that are responsible for providing basic services such as Caritas, Red Cross, etc.; • Local and regional companies: By maintaining contact with companies, the regional coordinators support refugees in their search for internships, apprenticeships and jobs. They were and are also available to companies if they need support in integrating refugees into their companies (e.g. in the search for German language courses); • Answering general questions about asylum and integration (at organized public events); • Consulting associations with refugee members;
Target group(s)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Refugees; • Volunteers engaged in refugee care; • Municipalities; • Educational institutions; • Local and regional companies; • Locals and associations;
Methodology	<p>Regional coordinators are in direct contact with all target groups and provide information, advice and support.</p>
Key facts	<p>The position of regional coordinators of refugee care is financed by the social funds of the Federal state and municipalities. It has manifold tasks, such as advising communities, cooperating with partners and volunteers, as well as networking and developing new projects across regions.</p>
Background information	<p>In 2015 with the high influx of asylum seekers arriving in Vorarlberg, particularly small municipalities required coordination and support in refugee care.</p>
Achieved results	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Increase knowledge and competence in integration work, especially in those municipalities and regions where

	<p>there was previously no structure of responsibility for integration issues at the administrative level;</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Bridging function between refugees and local and regional stakeholder, authorities, etc; <p>A female refugee emphasizes the refugee coordinator's bridging function from the encounter café to other services: " [The refugee coordinator] helped me a lot, she registered me for the German course at the ÖIF. She gave me a bicycle course because I was not allowed to ride a bicycle in Iran. She gave me her number and told me that I could always contact her. She encouraged me to continue with the German course and registered me with the ÖIF."</p>
Impacts of the good/new practice	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • At the local level, forced migrants could be reached by direct contact and they could be supported by (re)integrating them in activities of the regular system (German classes, Public Employment Service etc.). • When engagement of volunteers declined regional coordinators were essential to keep up contact and reactivate certain local activities for forced migrants after Covid-19 measures took place (especially with regard to support during lockdowns, and general support for women with childcare obligations). • Ensure exchange of knowledge and good practice among small rural municipalities.
Innovativeness	Establishment of a comprehensive structure of coordination of refugee care with a focus on social integration issues, including the very local level in peripheral regions.
Constraints	The funding is secured only for a certain period of time and has already been extended two times (for a year) until the end of 2023. Long-term financing is not yet ensured.
Replicability	
Replication conditions and success factors	Long-term funding must be secured.
Replicability and/or up-scaling	Long-term funding is needed. So far, the project is only funded until 2023.
Selection of good practice	

Reasons for choosing the good/new practice	The regional coordinators play an important role in the (social) integration process of forced migrants, which was emphasized by several interview partners. One regional coordinator was part of our Case Study working Group and provided crucial information.
Selection of European good/new practices	By the establishment of the regional refugee coordinators, a step was taken in Vorarlberg that has been considered essential for the management of integration agendas in the professional-level debate in German-speaking countries for many years - especially in rural areas. Regional coordinators are responsible for tasks, which are essential for advancing integration issues and processes at municipal level.
Personal experiences	No. (the local partner “okay.zusammen leben” supports the refugee coordinators with know-how and expertise since 2016)
Validation/evaluation external	Yes, the local partner okay.zusammen leben describes and analyzes in a paper the experiences made with this new structure for strengthening municipal integration work in recent years.
Validation/evaluation by project team	Interviewed regional stakeholders, such as Caritas, mayors, etc., as well as asylum seekers and volunteers mentioned the importance of the regional coordinators.
Sources	
Source(s) to the good/new practice	https://www.okay-line.at/file/656/lernerfahrungen-fluchtlingskoordinationsstellen.pdf
Date of documentation	30.05.2022

Figure 6 – Regional and municipal coordinators of refugee integration © BAB

Checklist for good/new practice selection

The selected good/new practice ...	
is innovative.	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?:</p> <p>Establishment of a comprehensive structure of coordination of refugee care with a focus on social integration issues, including the very local level in peripheral regions.</p>
develops creative solutions.	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?:</p> <p>Regional coordinators adapt their activities to the needs of the target groups at a local level and are therefore challenged to constantly find creative solutions.</p>

succeeds in achieving its objective(s).	Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/>
is ethical.	Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/>
is fair.	Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> In what way?: The service is inclusive and all people, regardless of their social characteristics are welcome.
Is been proven/evaluated (ideally: has been tested and validated) to work well and produce good results.	Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> In what way?: The local partner okay.zusammen leben describes and analyzes in a paper the experiences made with this new structure for strengthening municipal integration work in recent years.
is replicable.	Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> In what way?: Long-term funding must be secured.
improves migrants' rights.	Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> In what way?: But the regional coordinators play a crucial role in translating and explaining migrants' rights to refugees.
is inclusive with regard to people with a migrant background.	Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> In what way?: The service is focused on people with a migrant background, especially forced migrants.
works with a whole of government approach.	Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
improves the well-being of migrants	Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> In what way?:

	The service is oriented to the needs of migrants and stakeholders who are engaged in integration work.
is gender sensitive.	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?:</p> <p>Yes, projects with a focus on female refugees were implemented.</p>
fosters societal diversity.	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?:</p> <p>A main task of regional coordinators is to provide information and raise awareness for the needs of refugees.</p>
develops possibilities for a safe and orderly regular migration.	<p>Yes <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?:</p>
fosters preparedness and resilience to migration events/crises.	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?:</p> <p>In recent years, a lot of experience and knowledge about integration work has been gained. This expertise is concentrated by the regional coordinators and can be retrieved at any time.</p>
realizes a participatory and/or multi-level governance approach.	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?:</p> <p>The regional coordinator is in contact with all relevant stakeholder at local and regional level and realizes therefore a multi-level governance approach.</p>
promotes effective funding mechanism.	<p>Yes <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p>
fosters effective monitoring and evaluation approaches.	<p>Yes <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p>

Authors: Lisa Bauchinger and Ingrid Machold (BAB)

Naflahus – Third Space	
General information	
Type of good/new practice	Project
Area of action	Social cohesion
Adopting body	Local authority and volunteers
Level of good/new practice	Local
Location and geographical coverage	Local
Responsibility for good practice	Municipality
Duration	2016 until today (2022)
Key words	Social cohesion, meeting place, participation opportunities
Content of the good/new practice	
Objectives of the good/new practice	Offering a low-threshold meeting place, where refugees and immigrants can participate on various activities, get into contact with other people, learn German, get support for different issues, such as translation of documents, finding a job or housing, etc.
Target group(s)	Refugees, immigrants and local population; in the beginning: most visitors of the first activities (e.g. clothing exchange) were only briefly in Austria, in the meantime many of the visitors presumably have the right of abode. At the moment, mainly refugee women between 40 and 50 years who are not in employment come to the meeting place.
Methodology	Volunteers offer activities for all interested people, especially forced migrants to enhance social cohesion. The target group is reached through contacts and channels of the city of Feldkirch as well as through the communal coordinator of refugee care and by word of mouth.
Key facts	Several activities have taken place since the opening, starting with the initiating activity of the provision of clothes and household goods, which was open for all interested forced migrants in the wider area. These activities were accompanied by the opportunity to meet at the “Monday’s café” (language café), which is still ongoing on a weekly basis. Another activity which is still in place, is the “sewing

	<p>workshop”. In addition, children can be brought along to most of the projects, where they are looked after by paid staff. All activities are run by volunteers, albeit supervised by the communal coordinator of refugee care. Additional activities are bicycle repairs, community gardening, etc.</p>
<p>Background information</p>	<p>This low-threshold meeting place was set into action in 2016 by the city of Feldkirch due to the high influx of refugees. The intention of the city of Feldkirch was to offer infrastructure (an old house that was bought for this purpose) and professional support to people willing to engage in volunteering activities.</p>
<p>Achieved results</p>	<p>Social connection: “The Naflahus is a meeting point to make contacts, especially for single parents, or women who are all day alone at home with their children. These people detach themselves from the offers again, when sufficient social exchange could be achieved, for example, contacts have been made or they have built up a support network.” (Coordinator of Naflahus)</p> <p>Providing a regular structure for refugees on a weekly basis: A female refugee emphasizes the importance of the Naflahus to her: “I come here with many women to drink coffee, and to not forget German. If you always stay at home, you feel weak. And when you go out, I have energy and strength to live.” (Refugee)</p> <p>Linking function: Low-threshold activities, such as offered in the Naflahus can help to (re)integrate target groups, particularly female forced migrants in activities by the regular system (German classes, Public Employment Service etc.). One interviewee told us, that she found temporary work at the Naflahus.</p>
<p>Impacts of the good/new practice</p>	<p>At the local level, forced migrants could be reached by low-threshold activities.</p> <p>Forced migrants received direct help when arriving in the municipality (provision of clothes and household goods)</p> <p>Meeting place which enables social contacts and exchange are especially important for women without employment</p>
<p>Innovativeness</p>	<p>It is an easily accessible meeting space where refugees can make contacts and ask for support on a day-to-day basis. No memberships condition needed.</p>

Constraints	The awareness of third places is only just emerging. Further awareness building is necessary. Long-term funding is necessary and volunteers are needed.
Replicability	
Replication conditions and success factors	Long-term funding and an appropriate venue must be secured. This initiative is based on voluntary work.
Replicability and/or up-scaling	Upscaling is not in the intention of this project but similar projects are implemented in other municipalities in Vorarlberg.
Selection of good practice	
Reasons for choosing the good/new practice	The Naflahus, as well as other “third spaces”, which are easily accessible meeting points beyond work and private homes, play an important role in the social integration of refugees. This was also emphasized by two female refugees, participating in several activities at the Naflahus.
Selection of European good/new practices	Easily accessible meeting points, which offer low-threshold activities are especially important for female refugees. Based on our interviews, women often lack contacts and language exposure due to child care obligations, child birth, limited employment integration and illness periods. Most of them are not employed and have little contact and contact opportunities with locals. Thus, particularly for women low threshold offers are an important possibility to socialize and practice German language in an informal surrounding, enabling also some exchange with the receiving society.
Personal experiences	No.
Validation/evaluation external	The federal state of Vorarlberg published a position paper about “third spaces” in general. See: https://vorarlberg.at/documents/302033/0/Positionspapier-Dritte+Orte+in+Vorarlberg.pdf/069390fc-eb34-9819-4ddb-31c16b0ce8c4?t=1643815418560
Validation/evaluation by project team	Interviewed refugees, volunteers and the regional coordinator of refugee as well as for the Naflahus mentioned the importance of this meeting place.

Sources	
Source(s) to the good/new practice	https://territorialagenda.eu/news-articles/new-publication-strategy-building-processes-in-lagging-regions/ ; https://www.feldkirch.at/leben/integration/ehrenamt-und-naflahus
Date of documentation	30.05.2022

Figure 7 - Naflohus – Third Space © okay.zusammen leben

Checklist for good/new practice selection

The selected good/new practice ...	
is innovative.	Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> In what way?: It is an easily accessible meeting space where refugees can make contacts and ask for support for day-to-day things.
develops creative solutions.	Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>

	<p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?:</p> <p>Various activities, offered in a low-threshold meeting place, enable to maintain exchange between volunteers and refugees and immigrants.</p>
succeeds in achieving its objective(s).	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?:</p> <p>Yes, the activities are adapted to the needs of the refugees.</p>
is ethical.	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?:</p> <p>The project is inclusive and all people, regardless of their social characteristics are welcome.</p>
is fair.	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?:</p> <p>The project is inclusive and all people, regardless of their social characteristics are welcome.</p>
Is been proven/evaluated (ideally: has been tested and validated) to work well and produce good results.	<p>Yes <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p>
is replicable.	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?:</p> <p>Long-term funding and an appropriate venue must be secured. This initiative is based on voluntary work.</p>
improves migrants' rights.	<p>Yes <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p>
is inclusive with regard to people with a migrant background.	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?:</p> <p>All activities are especially for people with migrant background.</p>
works with a whole of government approach.	<p>Yes <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p>

<p>improves the well-being of migrants</p>	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?:</p> <p>It is a place to meet people, to participate on activities and to learn German. Especially for women who are all day alone at home with their children it is a pleasant change in their daily life. For some people it provides a regular structure and helps to distract oneself from everyday problems or traumatic experiences.</p>
<p>is gender sensitive.</p>	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?:</p> <p>Yes, projects with a focus on female refugees were implemented.</p>
<p>fosters societal diversity.</p>	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?:</p> <p>Enhance the visibility of the needs of people with migrant background, particularly for female forced migrants.</p>
<p>develops possibilities for a safe and orderly regular migration.</p>	<p>Yes <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p>
<p>fosters preparedness and resilience to migration events/crises.</p>	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?:</p> <p>Experience and knowledge about integration work has been gained in the last years. Volunteers engaged at the Naflahus can be reactivated and activities can be adapted to different upcoming needs.</p>
<p>realizes a participatory and/or multi-level governance approach.</p>	<p>Yes <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p>
<p>promotes effective funding mechanism.</p>	<p>Yes <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p>
<p>fosters effective monitoring and evaluation approaches.</p>	<p>Yes <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p>

Bulgaria

Authors: Chaya Koleva with contributions from Vanina Ninova (NBU)

Harmanli Refugee Camp Playschool	
General information	
Type of good/new practice	Service
Area of action	Education, health, language & culture,
Adopting body	Non-governmental adopted by NGOs,
Level of good/new practice	Local
Location and geographical coverage	Harmanli, Bulgaria
Responsibility for good practice	Harmanli Refugee Camp Play School – Sadie Jarrous
Duration	Since 2014
Key words	Psychological support ; games; playschool ; refugees kids
Content of the good/new practice	
Objectives of the good/new practice	<p>Playschool has existed since 2014 in the Registration and reception Center (RRC) Harmanli and was created and implemented by a young English woman and her mother. This educational approach of Playschool focuses on the importance of play for the children, especially for those suffering from traumas. The lessons that the school provides are focused on children to develop personal, social and emotional skills as well as to learn English or math in a playful way with games and singing. The play school provides a safe, therapeutic environment in which children can play, relax and learn. They are taught or reminded of the learning behavior expected inside a classroom, to prepare them for school outside the camp, they learn skills to help them communicate and integrate with people from different cultures.</p>
Target group(s)	Refugee children residing in the Refugee Reception Center in Harmanli

<p>Methodology</p>	<p>The Playschool has a special spacious room in the Refugee Reception center. The room is colored and children friendly. It is turned into a safe play space and classroom! In the room they are toys, a play house, a quiet area, a sensory play area, a football table, a doll's house, a TV area for PlayStation games and movie afternoons, tables for art and craft activities, floor space for small world and construction play, a whiteboard and blackboard for lessons, and more.</p> <p>Both the founder and her mom are trained in playwork and have years of experience, and other training, in working with children. The focus of the project in the camp is play, but also taught English lessons that turned out to be quite useful for the children who stay only for a short time in the camp. Each session begins with 90 minutes of free play where children can choose from a wide range of art and craft activities, a mix of both educational and less educational toys and games, reading in the quiet area, sensory play, role play and more. This is followed by a 20 to 30 minutes informal lesson where basic English and maths are taught through games and songs</p>
<p>Key facts</p>	<p>Playing and learning/developing skills in a safe environment</p>
<p>Background information</p>	<p>The initiative meets the needs to overcome the high isolation of kids in the refugee camps. It provides mental health treatment for kids via games. In spring 2014 there were around 1000 children with no access to education, no activities, no playground and no toys. The founder was living in England and working as a primary school teacher but she visited Bulgaria and the camp on a holiday, and saw for herself just how much of a need there was for there to be something for the children. She then decided to move to Bulgaria in the summer of 2014 to start something (we didn't know what yet!) with her mum for the children living in Harmanli Camp.</p>
<p>Achieved results</p>	<p>The school supported many children through very difficult times in their lives. (For instance, when it opened in November 2014 very quickly the school received around 300 children who were attending 3 days a week)</p>

	The testimonies of the founder of the school as well as NGO's in the region could be used.
Impacts of the good/new practice	The play school has been a big success over the last 7 years! It is very popular with both children and their parents. The BG research team have been told by stakeholders that the play school plays a key role in the wellbeing of the children. As reported by the founder of the school all children show signs of trauma in their behavior. After just a few weeks attending the school they have made lots of friends, developed their confidence, social skills and ability to communicate with others who speak a different language.
Innovativeness	The practice is innovative for the local context, develops creative solutions in education and adaption of refugee children, has succeeded in achieving its objectives, has been proven to work well, has gained the trust of people in and outside the refugee camp and has produced good results since its beginning in 2014. It is participatory, considers inclusiveness and well-being, has a sustainable effect by involving refugee children and is effective in contributing to refugees welcoming and integration. The Playschool applies to the local level (Registration and reception Center (RRC) Harmanli), but can serve as a model and can be applied in other Registration and reception Centers in Bulgaria as well as in Bulgarian schools.
Constraints	1 The trainer faced with very hard psychological traumas that refugee kids experience 2. Financial stability and sustainability
Replicability	
Replication conditions and success factors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Motivated, very well trained and experienced teachers - Flexible trainers - Big enough room and play materials for kids
Replicability and/or up-scaling	This practice relies completely on the human potential of trainers.
Selection of good practice	

Reasons for choosing the good/new practice	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Proven high level of efficiency; - Strong motivation and personal investment of founders and teachers; - The practice is a unique model for a sustainable practice; - The practice is financially independent from the state – it exists through fundraising; - People from all around the world donate for the practice;
Selection of European good/new practices	It is sustainable, effective and very needed for the mental health and future realization of refugee kids.
Personal experiences	NBU has interviewed the founder of the school, social workers in the camp, NGO's who have all reported positively about the practice,
Validation/evaluation external	-
Validation/evaluation by project team	All of the interviewed NGO representatives confirmed the high efficiency of the practice and the team can confirm it as well.
Sources	
Source(s) to the good/new practice	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. https://www.marginalia.bg/aktsent/sejdi-klazbi-dzharus-detsata-bezhantsi-sa-bili-obekt-na-strelba-prezhivyavali-sa-rasistki-obidi/?fbclid=IwAR0rwjhuAoX1pfS4xaUVGJGTQBT31BI-WOXXtqow8-06halkWoUKvXdfujo article (portrait) on the website for Human right Marginalia about the woman who has created the Playschool as part of the series of portraits Faces of diversity 2. https://www.facebook.com/groups/HarmanliRefugeeCampPlaySchool Link to the Facebook group of the Playschool
Date of documentation	01/02/2022

Figure 8 - Harmanli Refugee Camp Playschool (1) © Sadie Clasby-Jarrous, 2021

Checklist for good/new practice selection

The selected good/new practice ...	
is innovative.	Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> In what way?: Model of financial sustainability (fundraising).
develops creative solutions.	Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> In what way?: Combines many creative methods and adapts to many specific situations.
succeeds in achieving its objective(s).	Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> In what way?: Improves the mental health and the feeling of socialization of refugee kids.

is ethical.	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?:</p> <p>All activities are transparent.</p>
Is been proven/evaluated (ideally: has been tested and validated) to work well and produce good results.	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?:</p> <p>All local and regional and national key actors involved in refugee integration confirm the efficiency of the practice.</p>
is replicable.	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?:</p> <p>It could be replicable but it is however very adapted to specific geographical situation.</p>
improves migrants' rights.	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?:</p> <p>It improves asylum seekers and migrant' kids right to play and learn while staying in the camp.</p>
is inclusive with regard to people with a migrant background.	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?:</p> <p>It targets only kids living in the refugee camp.</p>
works with a whole of government approach.	<p>Yes <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p>
improves the well-being of migrants	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p>
is gender sensitive.	<p>Yes <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?:</p> <p>The school receives all children without regards to their gender.</p>

fosters societal diversity.	Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/>
develops possibilities for a safe and orderly regular migration.	Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
fosters preparedness and resilience to migration events/crises.	Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> In what way?: It demonstrate a good method of treating together numerous migrant children of different ages and nationalities.
realizes a participatory and/or multi-level governance approach.	Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
promotes effective funding mechanism.	Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> In what way?: The organization uses its only channel to find donors and financial independence and sustainability.
fosters effective monitoring and evaluation approaches.	Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>

Figure 9 - Harmanli Refugee Camp Playschool (1) © Sadie Clasby-Jarrous, 2021

Authors: Chaya Koleva with contributions from Vanina Ninova (NBU)

Labor exchange for employers and refugees	
General information	
Type of good/new practice	Service
Area of action	Employment; rights & citizenship, rural/regional development
Adopting body	UNHCR in cooperation with NGO and the State Agency for Refugees
Level of good/new practice	Regional
Location and geographical coverage	Haskovo and Harmanli, Bulgaria
Responsibility for good practice	UNHCR Bulgaria
Duration	Since 2018
Key words	Inclusion; labor market ; refugees ; employment ; integration
Content of the good/new practice	
Objectives of the good/new practice	The second good practice is in the field of adaptation and integration - a labor exchange with the participation of employers and refugees. The labor exchange aims to connect refugees with employers in order to integrate them into the labor market which is a basic component of their integration. Organizers first study the needs of the labor market and try to match with migrants/refugees' professional experience and motivation.
Target group(s)	Refugee and migrants; Local and regional employers
Methodology	Labor exchanges are organized by UNHCR as well as by other nonprofit organizations working with refugees and in cooperation with the State Agency for Refugees. Social workers promote the event in the region. They contact employers and collect or create migrants' CVs. A list of refugees / migrants looking for jobs and employers looking for employees is drafted before the event.
Key facts	Matching process for refugees and jobs
Background information	

Achieved results	- Increased interest in employing refugees and migrants: During the first labor exchange in Harmanli organized in 2018 in the cultural center of the city 4 enterprises from different areas offered employment to people seeking protection. This year (2022) the number of enterprises participating in the labor exchange has grown to 20.
Impacts of the good/new practice	- Inclusion of refugees and migrants in the labor market - Meeting the needs of regional economy - The initiative promotes the idea of TCN's positive impact on rural economy.
Innovativeness	Different actors cooperate in this initiative – state institutions, international organizations, NGOs, private sector, refugees and migrants
Constraints	- It is difficult to motivate employers to participate again the labor exchanges if they have experienced a sudden leave
Replicability	
Replication conditions and success factors	
Replicability and/or up-scaling	
Selection of good practice	
Reasons for choosing the good/new practice	- Proven high level of efficiency; - Strong motivation and personal investment of founders and teachers; - The practice is a unique model for a sustainable practice; - The practice is financially independent from the state – it exists through fundraising; - People from all around the world donate for the practice;
Selection of European good/new practices	
Personal experiences	NBU interviewed the founder of the school
Validation/evaluation external	

Validation/evaluation by project team	All of the interviewed NGO representatives confirmed the high efficiency of the practice
Sources	
Source(s) to the good/new practice	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. https://sakarnews.info/rabotodateli-predlozhiha-zaetost-na-bezhantsi/ The local media Sakarnews about the first labor exchange for employers and refugees 2. https://bcrm-bq.org/wp-content/uploads/2021/09/21_Third_Newsletter_F.pdf Bulletin "Refugee Integration in Bulgaria: Opportunities for Development" for the period July - September 2021 with information about the labor exchange conducted in 2021 in Harmanli (p.6)
Date of documentation	1 – 10/09/2018 ; 2 – 01.09.2021

Figure 10 - Labor exchange for employers and refugees

© <https://sakarnews.info/rabotodateli-predlozhiha-zaetost-na-bezhantsi/>, 10.10.2018

Checklist for good/new practice selection

The selected good/new practice ...	
is innovative.	Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> In what way?: It is organized in collaboration with many different actors - NGOs, state institutions, international organizations, employers, refugees and migrants.
develops creative solutions.	Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> In what way?: Provides a possibility to meet the needs of local labor market.
succeeds in achieving its objective(s).	Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/>
is ethical.	Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/>
is fair.	Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> In what way?: Refugees and migrants are selected for open job positions with regards to their competences and motivation.
Is been proven/evaluated (ideally: has been tested and validated) to work well and produce good results.	Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/>
is replicable.	Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/>
improves migrants' rights.	Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> In what way?:

	It improves asylum seekers and migrant' right to work (even for those who have not been granted asylum yet).
is inclusive with regard to people with a migrant background.	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?:</p> <p>It targets only migrants and refugees.</p>
works with a whole of government approach.	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?:</p> <p>It works in collaboration with the state agency for refugees and state agency for employment.</p>
improves the well-being of migrants	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?:</p> <p>Labor integration is a key element in migrants well being and integration.</p>
is gender sensitive.	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?:</p> <p>It is open to everybody with no regards to gender.</p>
fosters societal diversity.	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?:</p> <p>Hired refugees and asylum seekers often work with local Bulgarians.</p>
develops possibilities for a safe and orderly regular migration.	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p>
fosters preparedness and resilience to migration events/crises.	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p>
realizes a participatory and/or multi-level governance approach.	<p>Yes <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p>
promotes effective funding mechanism.	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p>

<p>fosters effective monitoring and evaluation approaches.</p>	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?:</p> <p>It is possible to have a concrete picture of hired refugees / asylum seekers who stay in the country and are willing to integrate the labor market.</p>
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Authors: Chaya Koleva with contributions from Vanina Ninova (NBU)

Intercultural Gardens Initiative	
General information	
Type of good/new practice	Service; Initiative ; Creative Multicultural Event
Area of action	Social cohesion, language & culture, ecology, rights & citizenship, rural/regional development
Adopting body	[Governmental/public adopted by a state/provincial/local authority or other public institution, or non-governmental adopted by NGOs, volunteers or other private actors]
Level of good/new practice	Regional and Local
Location and geographical coverage	Harmanli, Haskovo region, Bulgaria
Responsibility for good practice	Conducted by the Bulgarian team of MATILDE, and local partner Caritas Harmanli in partnership with regional schools
Duration	The initiative took place in Autumn 2021 and in Spring 2022 – one afternoon in every school day
Key words	Intercultural; gardening; kids; ecology; creativity; integration
Content of the good/new practice	
Objectives of the good/new practice	<p>The Intercultural Gardens Initiative has been implemented in all schools in Haskovo and a neighboring village with refugee children. Participants gather in schools' green spaces in order to plant trees and flowers and share common experiences. The event is followed by an artistic intercultural programme including dances and poetry recitals in each school, performed by local and TCN kids together. 'Green intersectionality' initiative (Anna Krasteva) connects people (TCNs and local residents) but also nature and culture, different generations, girls and boys. It was introduced in 2021 by the BG team during Matilde Action Research.</p>
Target group(s)	The directly targeted groups of the 'Intercultural Gardens as Green Bridges' Initiative were TCNs and local residents – principals, teachers and students from five schools in the town of Harmanli and one primary school in the village of

	<p>Balgarin, Harmanli municipality, which have enrolled child migrants. Children from Bulgaria, Syria, Iraq, Iran, and Afghanistan took part in the initiative, planting flowers and saplings in their schools.</p>
Methodology	<p>Prior to the day of the initiative, a press release and programme of the event was sent to local and national media. The Bulgarian News Agency presented the forthcoming event on its website. It was also shared by the print and online editions of the local newspaper. The preparation of the participatory activity itself included intensive communication with a representative of Caritas Bulgaria, with whom the logistics and necessary materials for the activities were discussed. Caritas Bulgaria provided the necessary materials and products for the organisation of the initiative.</p>
Key facts	<p>The initiative took space in 6 schools in the region. It was successfully organized and it is sustainable in a way that children have to constantly care for the gardens after the event.</p>
Background information	<p>There are migrant children in all chosen schools. Specific attention was paid to migrants' kids' competences during the events.</p>
Achieved results	<p>The initiative has created, metaphorically and actually, a new shared reality and a new meeting place through social inclusion and transformation of the common public space. It highlighted the need to protect the environment and biodiversity in the region.</p>
Impacts of the good/new practice	<p>'Intercultural Gardens' is an activity designed to create a place where participants experience deep attachment, including a sense of belonging. Such activities, combining art and nature, help to minimize the risk of social exclusion of TCNs in the region, opening up space for rich interaction between them and local residents.</p>
Innovativeness	<p>The initiative has created, metaphorically and actually, a new shared reality and a new meeting place through social inclusion and transformation of the common public space.</p>

Constraints	-
Replicability	
Replication conditions and success factors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Reliable local partner; - Connections and partnerships with local schools; - Trees and plants;
Replicability and/or up-scaling	The nature of the practice allows to be extended more widely
Selection of good practice	
Reasons for choosing the good/new practice	There are TCN's children in selected schools.
Selection of European good/new practices	The practice is based on 'green intersectionality' because it connects people, nature and culture, different generations, girls and boys.
Personal experiences	The leader of the BG research team Anna Krasteva invented the method of applying this practice in the case study region.
Validation/evaluation external	Quite positive feedback was received by teachers, school principals and kids as well.
Validation/evaluation by project team	
Sources	
Source(s) to the good/new practice	https://matilde-migration.eu/blog/intercultural-gardens-as-green-bridges/ https://matilde-migration.eu/blog/two-creative-matilde-days-in-harmanli-bulgaria/
Date of documentation	04/11/2021; 09/06/2022

Figure 11 - Intercultural Gardens Initiative (1) © Vanina Ninova, 2021

Checklist for good/new practice selection

The selected good/new practice ...	
is innovative.	Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> In what way?: It provides a possibility for sharing moments in the community, fosters interculturality, learn about ecology.
develops creative solutions.	Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> In what way?: It addresses in a creative way ecological and climate issues.
succeeds in achieving its objective(s).	Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/>
is ethical.	Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/>
is fair.	Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/>

<p>Is been proven/evaluated (ideally: has been tested and validated) to work well and produce good results.</p>	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?:</p> <p>Positive feedbacks of all participants in the practice were received after the event.</p>
<p>is replicable.</p>	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?:</p> <p>The organization does not need many resources and is replicable everywhere.</p>
<p>improves migrants' rights.</p>	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?:</p> <p>It improves migrants kids participation in common events.</p>
<p>is inclusive with regard to people with a migrant background.</p>	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p>
<p>works with a whole of government approach.</p>	<p>Yes <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p>
<p>improves the well-being of migrants</p>	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?:</p> <p>Migrants / refugee kids feel empowered when put in a situation in which they demonstrate their skills of gardening.</p>
<p>is gender sensitive.</p>	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p>
<p>fosters societal diversity.</p>	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p>
<p>develops possibilities for a safe and orderly regular migration.</p>	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p>

fosters preparedness and resilience to migration events/crises.	Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
realizes a participatory and/or multi-level governance approach.	Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
promotes effective funding mechanism.	Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
fosters effective monitoring and evaluation approaches.	Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> In what way? It is easy to assess the development of the initiative.

Figure 12 - Intercultural Gardens Initiative (2) © Vanina Ninova, 2021

Finland

Authors: Lauri Havukainen and Pirjo Pöllänen (UEF)

VAHVA ÄIDINKIELI -VAHVA SUOMEN KIELI -project	
General information	
Type of good/new practice	A project in the municipal childcare system in Kitee.
Area of action	Education, social cohesion, language & culture, rights & citizenship
Adopting body	Public adopted by a local authority
Level of good/new practice	Local
Location and geographical coverage	City of Kitee
Responsibility for good practice	City of Kitee, funded by the Ministry of Education
Duration	1.9.2020-31.12.2021
Key words	Early language education, Russian language education, Childcare
Content of the good/new practice	
Objectives of the good/new practice	To establish a program for Russian speaking children in learning of their native language
Target group(s)	Immigrant children or children from multilingual families (mainly Russian speaking).
Methodology	Language teaching clubs integrated into kindergartens daily activities.
Key facts	Included hiring of Russian speaking childcare assistants and organizing weekly language clubs for (mostly) Russian speaking children.
Background information	The Project wanted to increase non-Finnish speaking children's language integration and native language skills.
Achieved results	The project managed to put in place a permanent structure for language education in the childcare services of Kitee. All the assistants hire through the project continued their work in the system.

Impacts of the good/new practice	It has increased the language skill of Russian speaking immigrants as well as provided working opportunities for Russian speakers.
Innovativeness	Very innovative in context Finland. While language education for children's native languages is mandated by the law in schools this kind of program in public childcare system is not common.
Constraints	While the idea was to cater to all immigrants the project focused mainly on the Russian speakers as they form a huge majority of the municipality's immigrant population.
Replicability	
Replication conditions and success factors	Yes, with the right funding and the political will from the municipality to continue the program after the project funding ends.
Replicability and/or up-scaling	We do not see a reason why his would not work in larger municipalities if there is political will. It could be practically harder to organize in more mixed kindergartens.
Selection of good practice	
Reasons for choosing the good/new practice	Good example of a local project that had an impact and was kept up after the project funding ended.
Selection of European good/new practices	Good example of a local project that had an impact and was kept up after the project funding ended.
Personal experiences	Just through interviews with few of the operatives in the project.
Validation/evaluation external	The project was funded by the Ministry of Education, and they have their own validation system. In Finnish: https://okm.fi/documents/1410845/3505134/Hakijan+opas.pdf/06389db2-40ec-9e9b-6484-8be39ef48595/Hakijan+opas.pdf?t=1656505405867
Validation/evaluation by project team	Just the interviews during the project and checking on one of them after the project ended.
Sources	
Source(s) to the good/new practice	https://www.kitee.fi/hankkeet1
Date of documentation	30.8.2022

Checklist for good/new practice selection

The selected good/new practice ...	
is innovative.	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?:</p> <p>In the childcare system these kinds of programs are rare, especially in rural surroundings.</p>
develops creative solutions.	<p>Yes <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?:</p> <p>The solution is not particularly creative but it is impactful.</p>
succeeds in achieving its objective(s).	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?:</p> <p>The program was established and continues after the project ended.</p>
is ethical.	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p>
is fair.	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p>
Is been proven/evaluated (ideally: has been tested and validated) to work well and produce good results.	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?:</p> <p>We have not seen the post project documents but considering the success it had with it's goal, we think it has worked well.</p>
is replicable.	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?:</p> <p>With the right funding.</p>
improves migrants' rights.	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?:</p> <p>Improves both the Finnish and Russian skills of the children.</p>

<p>is inclusive with regard to people with a migrant background.</p>	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?: Is focused specifically on immigrant / multilanguage families.</p>
<p>works with a whole of government approach.</p>	<p>Yes <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p>
<p>improves the well-being of migrants</p>	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p>
<p>is gender sensitive.</p>	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?: This is hard to say as we did not take part in the day-to-day activities of the project but as it is publicly funded project it has to be.</p>
<p>fosters societal diversity.</p>	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?: Empowers the Russian speakers.</p>
<p>develops possibilities for a safe and orderly regular migration.</p>	<p>Yes <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p>
<p>fosters preparedness and resilience to migration events/crises.</p>	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?: Through better language integration.</p>
<p>realizes a participatory and/or multi-level governance approach.</p>	<p>Yes <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p>
<p>promotes effective funding mechanism.</p>	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?: Funded by a ministry.</p>
<p>fosters effective monitoring and evaluation approaches.</p>	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?: As it is funded by a ministry it has strict guidelines to follow.</p>

Authors: Lauri Havukainen and Pirjo Pöllänen (UEF)

The immigrant association of Central Karelia, Aljans ry	
Aljans	
General information	
Type of good/new practice	Local NGO working on the integration and cultural preservation of Russian speaking immigrants
Area of action	Economy & employment, social cohesion, language & culture, rights & citizenship
Adopting body	Non-governmental adopted by NGOs
Level of good/new practice	Local
Location and geographical coverage	The city of Kitee, The adjacent municipalities
Responsibility for good practice	The immigrant association of Central Karelia, Aljans ry
Duration	Continuous from 2018
Key words	Community based integration, Leisure time activities, Language and culture
Content of the good/new practice	
Objectives of the good/new practice	Organizes different leisure time activities (sports, music, language education) and everyday assistance to Russian speaking immigrants. Also organizes group trips and summer camps.
Target group(s)	Russian speaking immigrants
Methodology	Community and work-based activities that improve social, cultural and linguistic integration
Key facts	While their house does not have regular opening hours, they run an information office which gives assistance in bureaucracy and other everyday matters. They also have afternoon and evening clubs with different leisure time and educational activities.
Background information	Founded in 2018 to help Russian speaking immigrants integrate better and to upkeep their own cultural traditions (e.g., Cyrillic alphabet).
Achieved results	Has grown into an NGO with over 100 members and many different activities for people of all ages.

Impacts of the good/new practice	A large community (considering the size of the area) that has brought better
Innovativeness	their activity as a community house is nothing innovative but they are the only such NGO to focus especially on Russian speaking immigrants that form the majority of the area's immigrant population. Their aim of helping integration and conservation of cultural traditions is also rare.
Constraints	While they advertise themselves as an immigrant association, they are only really for one group of immigrants: Russian speakers. There were also some political tensions within the NGO which has driven out some of those who are openly critical to the current political situation in Russia. Aljans has a ban on discussion about politics and religion, which from outside perspective seemed quite superficial.
Replicability	
Replication conditions and success factors	Can be replicated with a similar kind of community, with the right people and good funding.
Replicability and/or up-scaling	Upscaling is possible with good and stable funding. Aljans has struggled with the stability.
Selection of good practice	
Reasons for choosing the good/new practice	The only significant immigrant run NGO in the area (Central Karelia).
Selection of European good/new practices	It is an impactful NGO in very rural North Karelia and one of the rare cases of such.
Personal experiences	We visited them twice in late 2021. First on our field trip to get to know the NGO and then latter to organize a focus group with them. They had a representative in the roundtable in May 2021.
Validation/evaluation external	No
Validation/evaluation by project team	We acknowledge the impact Aljans has had in the Russian speaking community in Central Karelia. Their leisure time activities are low barrier and plentiful. Still, we cannot ignore the underlying political tensions within the NGO and especially after the Ukrainian war started.
Sources	

Source(s) to the good/new practice	https://www.aljans.fi/etusivu/
Date of documentation	30.8.2022.

Checklist for good/new practice selection

The selected good/new practice ...	
is innovative.	Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> In what way?: The combination of helping integration and conservation of Russian cultural features.
develops creative solutions.	Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> In what way?: While their approach is rare their activities are mostly quite simply.
succeeds in achieving its objective(s).	Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> In what way?: It has grown into a community of over hundred members and many more within their activities in just 4 years. While they have struggled with stable funding they have been able maintain and increase their operations.
is ethical.	Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/>
is fair.	Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> In what way?: In most cases. There is the issue of not being able to discuss politics while the politics in Russia still affects the atmosphere.
Is been proven/evaluated (ideally: has been tested and validated) to work well and produce good results.	Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> In what way?:

	While we do not have a lot of quantitative evidence you could still see the effect through all the activities they organize and people these attract.
is replicable.	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?: with a similar kind of community, with the right people and good funding.</p>
improves migrants' rights.	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?: They help with issues with Finnish bureaucracy and institution increasing the immigrants' possibilities within the Finnish society. The full impact of political tensions between the members remains to be seen.</p>
is inclusive with regard to people with a migrant background.	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?: Pretty much all the volunteers and members are immigrants.</p>
works with a whole of government approach.	<p>Yes <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p>
improves the well-being of migrants	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p>
is gender sensitive.	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p>
fosters societal diversity.	<p>Yes <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?: This one is difficult to say because of their rare approach to activities (integration and culture) and the political tensions within.</p>
develops possibilities for a safe and orderly regular migration.	<p>Yes <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p>
fosters preparedness and resilience to migration events/crises.	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?:</p>

	Through better integration into Finnish society.
realizes a participatory and/or multi-level governance approach.	<p>Yes <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?:</p> <p>While technically almost all the people doing active work within Aljans are volunteers there was still visible distribution of power to certain people in the in the NGO.</p>
promotes effective funding mechanism.	<p>Yes <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?:</p> <p>It is not a funding mechanism. Is dependent on the same project-based funding as almost all the other NGOs in the country.</p>
fosters effective monitoring and evaluation approaches.	<p>Yes <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?:</p> <p>Some of the results of Aljans's activities and their effects can be hard to quantify.</p>

Authors: Lauri Havukainen and Pirjo Pöllänen (UEF)

Metka Community House	
General information	
Type of good/new practice	NGO run community house
Area of action	Social cohesion, language and culture
Adopting body	Non-governmental adopted by NGOs, volunteers
Level of good/new practice	Local
Location and geographical coverage	City of Lieksa and Pielisen Karjala in general
Responsibility for good practice	Lieksa Somali Family Association, support from Riveria and JoMoni
Duration	Continuous from August 2015
Key words	Community based integration, Work based integration, Leisure time activities
Content of the good/new practice	
Objectives of the good/new practice	Organizes a lot of different activities and offer working and practical training possibilities. The activities range from music, language education, crafts and sports. The house has multiple employees most of who are immigrants.
Target group(s)	Immigrants and locals of different age groups
Methodology	Community and work-based activities that improve social, cultural and linguistic integration
Key facts	They are open for everyone 4 days a week and have open evenings once a week. They have different day time clubs. Takes part in multiple local and regional level projects.
Background information	Originally to help the Somali community to integrate better and establish better community relations, now works on a broader scale but still focusing on immigrants.
Achieved results	Has improved the community relations between different groups, the language skill of migrants and offers a place of support and community for people from all backgrounds.
Impacts of the good/new practice	Better language integration, working opportunities, better cohesion in the community
Innovativeness	The community house in itself is not new or very innovative but has a lot of integrated activities that are (e.g., different clubs).

Constraints	Not every migrant group uses its' services due to conflicts between some migrant groups. Has not always been in the best of terms with some of the other actors working on integration.
Replicability	
Replication conditions and success factors	Technically easy to replicate but needs the right people, space and funding in order be operational in the long run. Funding cannot be based on a single project and the operations cannot be run by single individuals. Could also be operated publicly similarly to municipal youth centres.
Replicability and/or up-scaling	Through networks and regional/national projects. Locally dependent on the size of the community.
Selection of good practice	
Reasons for choosing the good/new practice	NGO operated mostly by immigrant mainly for other immigrants in a rural town. Has good reputation and is both nationally and regionally well known.
Selection of European good/new practices	Is well known and has a good reputation. immigrants' self-involvement in the integration process together with the strengthening of community relations.
Personal experiences	We have attended both their house during normal operating hours as well as been part of events that they have helped to organize. We have kept contact with Metka even after our data collection phase.
Validation/evaluation external	No
Validation/evaluation by project team	We have seen the good that it has done to better community relations as well the integration work it does with different immigrant groups.
Sources	
Source(s) to the good/new practice	http://metkatalo.net/tietoa-meista/
Date of documentation	26.8.2022

Figure 13 - Metka Community House (1) © Metka

Checklist for good/new practice selection

The selected good/new practice ...	
is innovative.	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?: Lot of the integrated activities for example the different clubs are innovative in the broad scale they work on.</p>
develops creative solutions.	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?: Improves integration holistically.</p>
succeeds in achieving its objective(s).	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?: Has improved community relations and integration of immigrants.</p>

is ethical.	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p>
is fair.	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?:</p> <p>In most cases yes though there are some groups who do not want to attend and in some groups, we noticed a gender imbalance on those who take part in which activity.</p>
Is been proven/evaluated (ideally: has been tested and validated) to work well and produce good results.	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?:</p> <p>Yes as they have had continuous funding and enough people to run the activities.</p>
is replicable.	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?:</p> <p>There are similarly operated community houses elsewhere. Metka just has an immigrant focus.</p>
improves migrants' rights.	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?:</p> <p>Improves their language and societal skills and improves their chances in the labour market.</p>
is inclusive with regard to people with a migrant background.	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?:</p> <p>It is run mostly by immigrants, so yes. There are some groups who do not attend though.</p>
works with a whole of government approach.	<p>Yes <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?:</p> <p>It is local so no.</p>
improves the well-being of migrants	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?:</p>

	Increases their integration and provides social connections.
is gender sensitive.	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?:</p> <p>Mostly yes. Within some groups there are discrepancy in the way women can take part in activities.</p>
fosters societal diversity.	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?:</p> <p>Brings different groups together mostly quite well.</p>
develops possibilities for a safe and orderly regular migration.	<p>Yes <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?:</p> <p>It is not a migration-related operation.</p>
fosters preparedness and resilience to migration events/crises.	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?:</p> <p>Through better community relations and integration.</p>
realizes a participatory and/or multi-level governance approach.	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?:</p> <p>While some have more role in its governance it is still very participatory.</p>
promotes effective funding mechanism.	<p>Yes <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?:</p> <p>It is not a funding mechanism. Is dependent on the same project-based funding as almost all the other NGOs in the country.</p>
fosters effective monitoring and evaluation approaches.	<p>Yes <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?:</p> <p>Some of the results of Metka's activities and their effects can be hard to quantify.</p>

Figure 14 - Metka Community House (2) © Metka

Figure 15 - Metka Community House (3) © Metka

Authors: Lauri Havukainen and Pirjo Pöllänen (UEF)

Musikcafé After Eight r.f.	
After Eight	
General information	
Type of good/new practice	Youth work NGO with variety of modes
Area of action	Association that run's a café, workshops and events together with a more classical forms of youth center and youth assistance work.
Adopting body	Public adopted by NGO
Level of good/new practice	Local (some regional activities)
Location and geographical coverage	City of Jakobstad and the adjacent areas
Responsibility for good practice	Musikcafé After Eight r.f. with some of the operations run by the municipality
Duration	Has been in operation in one form or another for over 30 years.
Key words	NGO run youth center, Youth café, Youth work, Workshops
Content of the good/new practice	
Objectives of the good/new practice	Multifaceted youth work which aims to improve the situation of youth who might struggle with everyday life. This is combined with more traditional youth work and running a cafe.
Target group(s)	Youth in general, youth with social problems especially.
Methodology	Multiple forms from practical training (café, workshops) to youth activities
Key facts	The café is open everyday between 10 and 16 o'clock. Other activities vary but are located in the same premises.
Background information	Began work over 30 years ago with the current NGO was founded in 1997.
Achieved results	Our experience in the place comes from two of the employees we interviewed and thus we do not have broad view of the operations. Still, it has been operational for a long time and is the only place in the area to offer such services. The amount people they have given practical training positions throughout the years is in the hundreds.

Impacts of the good/new practice	Organizes opportunities and assistance to those youth who are most vulnerable. Hundreds of trainees over the years.
Innovativeness	While none of the activities are that innovative in themselves the combination and broadness are rare.
Constraints	Hard to say in our limited experience but at least some of the activities are funded through project funded and thus can be volatile.
Replicability	
Replication conditions and success factors	Yes, with proper funding. Could be fully organized through the public sector or through a mix of different sectors.
Replicability and/or up-scaling	No reason why it would not be possible with the right premises and funding.
Selection of good practice	
Reasons for choosing the good/new practice	Only such actor in the Jakobstad area.
Selection of European good/new practices	We would presume that this kind of broad and holistic approach is rare even in European level.
Personal experiences	Our experience is only through the single interview. We were supposed to go visit them during the project but that was not possible because of Covid and other practical reasons.
Validation/evaluation external	No that we know of.
Validation/evaluation by project team	The interview with the workers plus few recommendations from other interviewees.
Sources	
Source(s) to the good/new practice	https://www.aftereight.fi/om-aftereight?lang=fi
Date of documentation	1.9.2022.

Checklist for good/new practice selection

The selected good/new practice ...	
is innovative.	Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> In what way?: In this kind of holistic and broad way.
develops creative solutions.	Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> In what way?: It can offer help and assistance in such a broad scale in one place.
succeeds in achieving its objective(s).	Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> In what way?: Based on the interview and recommendations.
is ethical.	Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/>
is fair.	Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/>
Is been proven/evaluated (ideally: has been tested and validated) to work well and produce good results.	Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> In what way?: Hard to say with our limited experience but Based on the history, yes.
is replicable.	Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/>
improves migrants' rights.	Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> In what way?: Gives them opportunities to improve their life skills and integration.

<p>is inclusive with regard to people with a migrant background.</p>	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?: Many of the participants are from asylum or refugee background.</p>
<p>works with a whole of government approach.</p>	<p>Yes <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p>
<p>improves the well-being of migrants</p>	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?: Through the opportunities it gives.</p>
<p>is gender sensitive.</p>	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p>
<p>fosters societal diversity.</p>	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?: Yes, the activities are multicultural and multilingual.</p>
<p>develops possibilities for a safe and orderly regular migration.</p>	<p>Yes <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p>
<p>fosters preparedness and resilience to migration events/crises.</p>	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?: Yes, through better integration.</p>
<p>realizes a participatory and/or multi-level governance approach.</p>	<p>Yes <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?: Hard to say on our experience.</p>
<p>promotes effective funding mechanism.</p>	<p>Yes <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p>
<p>fosters effective monitoring and evaluation approaches.</p>	<p>Yes <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?: Hard to say on our limited experience.</p>

Free State of Bavaria

Germany

Authors: Tobias Weidinger with contributions from Stefan Kordel and David Spenger (FAU)

Lay Interpreters (Laiendolmetscher)	
L-INT	
General information	
Type of good/new practice	Project/training
Area of action	Language and culture, rights & citizenship
Adopting body	Non-governmental adopted by NGOs, volunteers or other private actors, and governmental/public adopted by a state/provincial local authority or other public institution
Level of good/new practice	Local
Location and geographical coverage	Rural district Berchtesgadener Land
Responsibility for good practice	Caritas Centre Berchtesgadener Land, Special Service Asylum and Migration, in close cooperation with the administration of the rural district and the local school authority
Duration	Since 2017
Key words	Interpreting, Language, Culture, Authorities, General Practitioners
Content of the good/new practice	
Objectives of the good/new practice	Lay interpreters are trained to interpret for rural newcomers at local authorities, at parents' evenings in schools and kindergartens, at police stations, at general practitioners, at counselling situations or at attorney's offices.
Target group(s)	Immigrants (TCN and EU citizens)
Methodology	Potential lay interpreters send applications, which are checked by the integration guide of the rural district. The measure is led by a sworn in interpreter and translator and organized on two weekends including three days each. It concludes with a theoretical exam and a practical exam at a school or at the authorities. Afterwards, participants, receive a certificate in the course of a small ceremony and can be

	appointed by request and availability (Landkreis Berchtesgadener Land 2021, Regierung von Oberbayern 2021).
Key facts	The contact details of trained lay interpreters are kept in a database at Caritas. They can be booked for appointments by means of contacting the responsible office at Caritas. For their service, the lay interpreters receive a volunteering allowance (Landkreis Berchtesgadener Land 2021).
Background information	Limited knowledge of German language among newcomers may be particularly detrimental in interactions at authorities, schools or kindergartens, general practitioners, counselling situations or attorneys. Children and family members, however, cannot adequately replace professionals. Professional interpreters cannot solve this structural challenge alone, too (Landkreis Berchtesgadener Land 2021). Therefore, the training of lay cultural interpreters was established.
Achieved results	So far, the rural district trained 24 lay interpreters that are able to interpret between German and Arabic, Dari, English, Farsi, Italian, Pashto, Punjab, Tigrinya and Turkish language (Regierung von Oberbayern 2021).
Impacts of the good/new practice	The lay interpreters are able to assist rural newcomers and reduce language and cultural hurdles and thus foster TCNs' access to their rights. Recently, they were also involved in the vaccination campaign against COVID-19. The formalization process by means of the training and the certificates contributes to a better quality of interpretation, while the obligation to secrecy safeguards the protection of data (Schuhegger 2022). Lay interpreters are also able to diminish gaps, which cannot be closed by professional interpreters. Simultaneously, they are compensated for their time and efforts by the volunteering allowance (Landkreis Berchtesgadener Land 2021). Finally, the lay interpreters represent role models of 'good integration' (Regierung von Oberbayern 2021).
Innovativeness	The training aims to compensate the lacking availability of professional interpreters in rural and mountain areas by means of training lay interpreters. The project/training,

	thereby, contributes to the interpreters' agency and capacity-building.
Constraints	<p>Caritas and lay interpreters criticize that requests for interpreting often arrive on short notice, which does not give Caritas the time to contact potential lay interpreters nor lay interpreters themselves to ask for time off from work. For lay interpreters with own flight experiences, emotionally upsetting situations may arise when being confronted with the flight of others (Landkreis Berchtesgadener Land 2019). Due to the arrival and settlement of immigrants speaking Burmese, Russian, Polish, and Spanish, interpreters who are able to interpret between German and the languages mentioned are lacking. There is also only one interpreter for Tigrinya, which may lead to overstress for the person (Landkreis Berchtesgadener Land 2021, Schuhegger 2022).</p>
Replicability	
Replication conditions and success factors	The replication conditions depend on the engagement of local stakeholders to establish such a training, the funding and financial means as well as the availability of trainers and facilities. In addition, immigrants need to be open to participate in the qualification measure and be able to allocate free time to do the interpreting.
Replicability and/or up-scaling	A similar project titled "Cultural interpreter plus - sharing empowerment®" was established by the Catholic adult education (<i>Katholische Erwachsenenbildung, KEB</i>) in the archdiocese Munich-Freising, the Dachau Forum and the Domberg Academy Freising since 2016. The three institutions developed a qualification measure encompassing about 40 hours of training and about three hours of practice that goes even further than the good practice presented. It focusses on the linguistic and cultural assistance of professionals, counselling on countries and cultures of origin as well as accompanying and supporting immigrants in everyday life (Katholische Akademie in Bayern 2021). The training is implemented jointly by the Bavarian Catholic working group for adult education (<i>Katholische Landesarbeitsgemeinschaft für Erwachsenenbildung in Bayern e.V., KEB</i>) and the

	Association of the Evangelical Lutheran Church in Bavaria (<i>Arbeitsgemeinschaft für Evangelische Erwachsenenbildung in Bayern e.V., AAEB</i>) in more than 15 locations all over Bavaria and is funded by the Bavarian State Ministry of the Interior, for Sport and Integration (StMI).
Selection of good practice	
Reasons for choosing the good/new practice	In this project, immigrants are not only people affected, but considered as important stakeholders with respective resources. Immigrants are empowered in the training to reflect about their own positionality and to support other newcomers. The training is very flexible as it can be implemented in the course of both block or regular courses, depending on the time schedules and preferences of the potential participants.
Selection of European good/new practices	The project/training targets an often neglected issue in rural areas, i.e. the language and cultural barriers in administration, kindergartens and schools, police, counselling or treatment.
Personal experiences	No
Validation/evaluation external	The training of lay interpreters in the MATILDE rural district Upper Bavaria was assigned the 2020 Upper Bavarian Integration Award in the category “social” (Regierung von Oberbayern 2021).
Validation/evaluation by project team	In the course of WP3/WP4, FAU conducted three interviews with three different local stakeholders, who mentioned or referred to the project.
Sources	
Source(s) to the good/new practice	Katholische Akademie in Bayern (2021): Kulturdolmetscher plus – sharing empowerment®. Qualifizierung von kulturkompetenten Vermittler*innen. <i>Zur Debatte</i> 2/2021, 32. https://www.kath-akademie-bayern.de/fileadmin/user_upload/Kurzbericht_Kulturdolmetscher_2021.pdf (accessed last, 09.06.2022) Landkreis Berchtesgadener Land (2019): <i>Fleißige Laiendolmetscherinnen und -dolmetscher im Dauereinsatz</i> . Press release, 10.07.2019 https://www.lra-bgl.de/lw/eu-buerger-drittstaater-

	<p>nationalitaet/integrationslotsin/aktuelles/detail/news/fleissige-laiendolmetscherinnen-dolmetscher-im-dauereinsatz/ (accessed last, 09.06.2022)</p> <p>Landkreis Berchtesgadener Land (2021): <i>Ausbildung neuer Laiendolmetscherinnen. Press release, 19.11.2021.</i> https://www.lra-bgl.de/lw/eu-buerger-drittstaater-nationalitaet/integrationslotsin/aktuelles/detail/news/ausbildung-neuer-laiendolmetscherinnen-2/ (accessed last, 08.06.2022)</p> <p>Regierung von Oberbayern (2021): <i>Oberbayerischer Integrationspreis 2020. Preisträger.</i> Regierung von Oberbayern: München. https://www.regierung.oberbayern.bayern.de/mam/dokument/e/presse/integrationspreise/integrationspreis2020-preistraeger.pdf (accessed last, 08.06.2022)</p> <p>Schuhegger, L. (2022): Wandelndes Wörterbuch im Einsatz – Nadeem Hassan übersetzt vom Pakistanischen ins Deutsche, <i>Berchtesgadener Anzeiger</i>, 03.01.2022 https://www.berchtesgadener-anzeiger.de/region-und-lokal/lokales-berchtesgadener-land/berchtesgaden_artikel,-wandelndes-woerterbuch-im-einsatz-nadeem-hassan-uebersetzt-vom-pakistanischen-ins-deutsche-_arid,673946.html (accessed last, 09.06.2022)</p>
Date of documentation	08-09.06.2022

Authors: Tobias Weidinger with contributions from Stefan Kordel and David Spenger (FAU)

Tenant qualification “Fit for the home” – Neusäss Concept (Mieterqualifizierung “Fit für die eigene Wohnung” – Neusäßer Konzept) TQ-FIT	
General information	
Type of good/new practice	Project/training
Area of action	Housing, language & culture, rights & citizenship
Adopting body	Non-governmental adopted by NGOs, volunteers or other private actors, often supported by local authorities
Level of good/new practice	National
Location and geographical coverage	Countrywide, with a focus on southern Germany
Responsibility for good practice	Development of exercise book and guide: Susanne Kern and Uwe Krüger from the refugee relief group Neusäss (near Augsburg, Bavaria) Support for implementation: Bavarian State Ministry of the Interior, for Sport and Integration
Duration	The project started in 2016, when the refugee relief group Neusäss developed an exercise book for participants and a guide for full-time or lay trainers. The trainings are on-going.
Key words	Housing, Refugees, Training, Empowerment, Certificate
Content of the good/new practice	
Objectives of the good/new practice	The aims of the project/training are to reduce prejudices of landlords towards refugees and other people in precarious living conditions, to empower them and improve their access to private housing (Mieterqualifizierung – Neusässer Konzept 2022).
Target group(s)	Refugees, other persons in precarious living conditions
Methodology	After the initial development of the training material, the focus was put on marketing the project to the general public, the local authorities, NGOs and landlords as well as on the distribution of the training material. Recently, an interactive online training and a specific handbook for living in multi-family houses was published. The latter can be used for self-training

	and specifically targets the time after the moving in (Mieterqualifizierung – Neusässer Konzept 2022).
Key facts	The refugee relief group provides an exercise book for participants and a guide for full-time or lay trainers. The training itself encompasses five modules (of around two hours each): (1) ‘good’ behavior as tenant, (2) understanding advertisements and contacting the landlord, (3) apartment inspection, (4), rental contract, and (5) development of an application to present oneself to the landlord. The application may include a copy of the residence status, the legal liability or the work contract. At the end of the training, participants need to pass an exam organized by the trainers in order to receive a certificate.
Background information	Access to private housing of refugees is hampered due to the fact that refugees often lack knowledge about the mode of operation of the German housing market or specific (German) domestic practices like waste separation, airing or heating. In addition, landlords may have certain fears towards refugee tenants.
Achieved results	More than 30,000 training guides were delivered to all over Germany (Sonntagsblatt Evangelisch 360° 2022). In the MATILDE rural district Berchtesgadener Land, for instance, 74 individuals participated in the training since autumn 2017, whereby the majority was able to access private housing afterwards (Berchtesgadener Anzeiger 2021).
Impacts of the good/new practice	The project/training is marketed as ‘good’ practice by the Bavarian State Government. It is also connected to similar projects such as “Housing space for individuals with a migration background – Housing Space for all – Integration needs a Home” (<i>Wohnraum für Menschen mit Migrationshintergrund - Wohnraum für Alle - Integration braucht ein Zuhause, WoFA</i>) of the Evangelical-Lutheran Church and the Diaconic work Bavaria.
Innovativeness	The training material has a practical orientation and is very much based on pictures and pictograms in order to reduce language barriers and even includes tips for everyday life.
Constraints	Following a survey of Bavarian integration guides in 2020, tenant qualification is considered less effective compared to personal contacts of stakeholders to potential landlords

	<p>(Wegner 2020). Initially, the project/training put its focus on the target group of refugees, but, later on, opened it to other German and foreign persons in precarious living conditions, who may also experience difficulties with regard to the apartment search. However, the unilateral focus on the demand side can be criticized, because the project does not address structural barriers with regard to access to housing and lacking intercultural competences and discriminatory practices by suppliers, i.e. landlords and real estate agents (cf. discussions in Meuth 2021).</p>
<p>Replicability</p>	
<p>Replication conditions and success factors</p>	<p>The replicability depends on the engagement of local stakeholders to order training material, the availability of the training material for delivery as well as the financial resources to purchase the exercise books (10€ each plus delivery) and handbooks (2,50€ each plus delivery). Due to the fact that – so far – it is only published in German language, it is not accessible for a wider audience. Immigrants need to be open to participate in the qualification measure, too.</p>
<p>Replicability and/or up-scaling</p>	<p>Given the precondition that the training material is translated to other languages, the project/training can easily be replicated. The advantage is that it can also be adapted to local specificities. In the MATILDE rural district BGL, for instance, the training was combined with excursions to relevant institutions such as the builder’s yard or the fire brigade (Berchtesgadener Anzeiger 2021).</p>
<p>Selection of good practice</p>	
<p>Reasons for choosing the good/new practice</p>	<p>The project/training is low-threshold and, thus, there is no extra qualification phase needed for trainers. The training is very flexible as it can be implemented in the course of both block or regular courses, online or face-to-face courses, depending on the time schedules and preferences of the potential participants.</p>
<p>Selection of European good/new practices</p>	<p>Despite its focus on Germany, the project/training could easily be up-scaled and transferred to other national contexts.</p>
<p>Personal experiences</p>	<p>No</p>

Validation/evaluation external	The project/training won the 2017 Integration Award of the administrative district Swabia (Sonntagsblatt 360° Evangelisch 2022).
Validation/evaluation by project team	FAU conducted three interviews with two commissioners for integration/integration guides as well as with a local administrative staff in three of the MATILDE rural districts in the course of WP3/WP4 respectively two field seminars with students (June 2021, May 2022). All of the interviewees bought the training material and regularly qualify refugees.
Sources	
Source(s) to the good/new practice	<p>Berchtesgadener Anzeiger (2021): Schulung zur Mieterqualifizierung nach dem „Neusässer Konzept“. <i>Berchtesgadener Anzeiger</i>, 29.10.2021. https://www.berchtesgadener-anzeiger.de/region-und-lokal/lokales-berchtesgadener-land_artikel,-schulung-zur-mieterqualifizierung-nach-dem-neusaesser-konzept-_arid,661970.html (accessed last, 01.06.2022)</p> <p>Meuth, M. (2021): Capabilities und Wohnen – eine Programmatik für erziehungswissenschaftliche Forschung und Praxis Sozialer Arbeit. <i>Soziale Passagen</i> 13, 213-233.</p> <p>Mieterqualifizierung – Neusässer Konzept (2022): <i>Homepage</i>. https://mieterqualifizierung.de (accessed last, 02.06.2022)</p> <p>Sonntagsblatt 360° Evangelisch (2022): Mieterqualifizierung hilft Geflüchteten bei der Wohnungssuche. <i>Sonntagsblatt 360° Evangelisch</i>, 17.01.2022. https://www.sonntagsblatt.de/artikel/bayern/mieterqualifizierung-hilft-gefluechteten-bei-der-wohnungssuche (accessed last, 01.06.2022)</p> <p>Wegner, M. (2020): <i>“Integrationslots*innen in Bayern”</i>. Abschlussbericht der Evaluation. Hochschule München: Munich. https://www.innenministerium.bayern.de/assets/stmi/mui/integrationspolitik/volltext.pdf (accessed last, 01.06.2022)</p>
Date of documentation	01.06.2022/02.06.2022

Authors: Tobias Weidinger with contributions from Stefan Kordel and David Spenger (FAU)

Therapeutic services for refugees (Therapeutische Angebote für Flüchtlinge) TAFF	
General information	
Type of good/new practice	Project/service
Area of action	Health, safety & stability
Adopting body	Non-governmental adopted by NGOs, volunteers or other private actors
Level of good/new practice	Regional
Location and geographical coverage	<p>The project/service is implemented at ten different localities in Bavaria, covering four out of the 25 cities and 14 out of the 71 rural districts</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • TAFF Allgäu, for city Kempten and rural districts Oberallgäu and Ostallgäu; • TAFF Freising, for rural district Freising; • TAF Hochfranken, for city and rural district Hof; • TAFF Mittelschwaben, for rural districts Dillingen, Günzburg and Neu-Ulm; • TAFF Mühldorf, for rural district Mühldorf; • TAFF Oberfranken-West, for city Coburg and rural districts Coburg, Kronach and Lichtenfels; • TAFF Regensburg; • TAFF Rosenheim, for city and rural district Rosenheim; • TAFF Starnberg, for rural district Starnberg; • TAFF Weilheim-Schongau/Landsberg, for rural districts Landsberg am Lech and Weilheim-Schongau;
Responsibility for good practice	<p>Diaconal work Bavaria (<i>Diakonisches Werk Bayern</i>) with support from the Evangelical Lutheran Church in Bavaria (<i>Evangelisch-Lutherische Kirche in Bayern</i>) and the Foundation Connecting Worlds (<i>Stiftung Welten verbinden</i>), consisting of the two former institutions.</p>
Duration	Developed in 2014, founded as pilot in 2015 in two model regions, solidified until the end of 2022

Key words	Counselling, Refugees, Traumatization, Mental Illness, Networking
Content of the good/new practice	
Objectives of the good/new practice	TAFF aims at improving the support for traumatized and mentally ill refugees and other migrants with mental disorders outside of Bavarian metropolises and big cities. In this realm, it seeks to establish a network of different actors in the health sector.
Target group(s)	Refugees, volunteers in refugee relief, psychotherapists, lay language and cultural interpreters, refugee and integration counsellors, priests and pastors
Methodology	The Diaconical work Bavaria established contact and coordination centres and hired staff who assist with accounting and liaise lay language and cultural interpreters. Psychologists, social workers and lay language and cultural interpreters are paid for individual and group counselling (respectively interpreting).
Key facts	The Diaconical work Bavaria established contact and coordination centres. Their main areas of work are <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Individual and group counselling and stabilization of refugees (including psychologists, social workers and lay language and cultural interpreters), • networking, i.e. connecting all stakeholders involved such as therapists, general practitioners, lay language and cultural interpreters as well as institutions in the health sector, and • qualification measures for employees and volunteers involved in refugee relief (e.g. with regard to recognition of mental illnesses or supervision).
Background information	The psychotherapeutic care of refugees in Bavaria is insufficient. Before the start of TAFF, there were only three centres specialized in refugees that were also situated in cities only. Accordingly, waiting times for therapy places were long (more than six months) and were hard to reach for refugees living in rural areas (Utler & Schmid 2014). Given the increasing arrival of refugees in 2015, a pilot started in two model regions.

<p>Achieved results</p>	<p>In 2020, every contact and coordination centre had, by average, 430 single appointments and took care of 47 to 170 clients (700-900 individuals by year in total). The majority of them (more than 70%) frequented the centre more than once. If needed, clients were also put in contact with medical psychotherapists (STIFTUNG WELTEN VERBINDEN 2021, Lohmann 2022). Due to its success, TAFF has lost its project character and has been established as a permanent offer within the Diaconical work Bavaria / The Evangelical Lutheran Church (STIFTUNG WELTEN VERBINDEN 2022).</p>
<p>Impacts of the good/new practice</p>	<p>The project/service fostered refugees' access to counselling offers in rural areas. It became also well-known to an European audience due to the project sponsor's embeddedness in the ERASMUS+ project SARAH (Social learning activities in rural areas for hidden people), where good practices were collected and exchange on them was nurtured.</p>
<p>Innovativeness</p>	<p>The project/service focuses rural areas instead of cities and follows a decentralized approach. It takes into account various stakeholders and their specific needs. To offer parents the opportunity to participate in group counselling, for instance, childcare is offered. The project/service also provided qualification measures for lay language and cultural interpreters and contributed to their agency and capacity-building.</p>
<p>Constraints</p>	<p>The project/service suffered from COVID-19 related social distancing, quarantining and the necessity to wear face masks during counselling (STIFTUNG WELTEN VERBINDEN 2020). The majority of the funding will expire at the end of 2022, which inhibits the sustainability of the project/service (Sonntagsblatt 360° Evangelisch 2022). In addition, the project/service does not follow a whole-of-society approach, but focuses on rather narrow target groups, e.g. refugees or volunteers involved in refugee relief.</p>
<p>Replicability</p>	
<p>Replication conditions and success factors</p>	<p>The replication conditions depend on the engagement of local stakeholders to establish a local contact and coordination centre, the funding and financial means, the availability of</p>

	<p>trained staff (psychologists, social workers, lay language and cultural interpreters) and facilities. In addition, refugees, volunteers, psychotherapists and refugee and integration counsellors need to be open to participate in counselling and qualification measures.</p>
<p>Replicability and/or up-scaling</p>	<p>Drawing on the lessons learned in TAFF, a praxis manual in German language will be published later in 2022, which aims at supporting the establishment of new contact and coordination centres and may thus foster replicability in other parts of the country (Schmid & Utler 2022, forthcoming). Up-scaling of the project/service is possible, if the conditions mentioned above are met.</p>
<p>Selection of good practice</p>	
<p>Reasons for choosing the good/new practice</p>	<p>The project started in two pilot regions and – due to its success – was up-scaled rather quickly and can now be found in many rural areas in Bavaria.</p>
<p>Selection of European good/new practices</p>	<p>The project/service targets an often neglected issue in rural areas, i.e. the availability and accessibility of counselling offers for individuals with mental illnesses.</p>
<p>Personal experiences</p>	<p>No</p>
<p>Validation/evaluation external</p>	<p>In 2019, the project/service fostered quality management and systematically evaluated qualification offers. In the pilot regions, two evaluations of networks were carried out in 2016 and 2019 (STIFTUNG WELTEN VERBINDEN 2019).</p> <p>Proposed by the local administration, the project/service in the Allgäu region received the 2019 Integration Award of the administrative district Swabia. The overall project/service was granted the 2022 Bavarian Integration Award (2nd price) by the Bavarian State Ministry of the Interior, for Sports and Integration (StMI), the Commissioner for Integration of the Bavarian state government and the Bavarian state parliament.</p>
<p>Validation/evaluation by project team</p>	<p>FAU conducted an interview with a psychologist Involved In TAFF in the course of WP3/WP4.</p>
<p>Sources</p>	

<p>Source(s) to the good/new practice</p>	<p>Lohmann, D. (2022): Hilfe bei Geburt, Gewalt oder Gefahr. <i>Bayerische Staatszeitung</i>, 29.04.2022. https://www.bayerische-staatszeitung.de/staatszeitung/landtag/detailansicht-landtag/artikel/hilfe-bei-geburt-gewalt-oder-gefahr.html#topPosition (accessed last, 31.05.2022)</p> <p>Schmid, S. & Utler, A. (2022, forthcoming): <i>Psychisch belastete und erkrankte Geflüchtete versorgen. Das TAFF-Praxismanual</i>. Vandenhoeck & Ruprecht: Göttingen.</p> <p>Sonntagsblatt 360° Evangelisch (2022): Diakonie: Psychische Betreuung von Flüchtlingen wird noch wichtiger. <i>Sonntagsblatt 360° Evangelisch</i>, 06.05.2022. https://www.sonntagsblatt.de/artikel/epd/diakonie-psychische-betreuung-von-fluechtlingen-wird-noch-wichtiger (accessed last, 01.06.2022)</p> <p>STIFTUNG WELTEN VERBINDEN (2019): <i>TAFF Newsletter Ausgabe Juli 2019</i>. STIFTUNG WELTEN VERBINDEN: Nuremberg. https://www.welten-verbinden.de/fileadmin/welten_upload/dateien/2019/TAFF_Newsletter_Juli_2019.pdf (accessed last, 31.05.2022)</p> <p>STIFTUNG WELTEN VERBINDEN (2020): <i>TAFF Newsletter Ausgabe Juli 2020</i>. STIFTUNG WELTEN VERBINDEN: Nuremberg. https://www.welten-verbinden.de/fileadmin/welten_upload/dateien/2020/TAFF_Newsletter_Juli_2020.pdf (accessed last, 31.05.2022)</p> <p>STIFTUNG WELTEN VERBINDEN (2021): <i>Initiative TAFF – Therapeutische Angebote für Flüchtlinge. Flyer</i>. https://www.welten-verbinden.de/uploads/media/Initiative_TAFF_2021.pdf (accessed last, 31.05.2022)</p> <p>STIFTUNG WELTEN VERBINDEN (2022): <i>Therapeutische Angebote für Flüchtlinge. Website</i>. https://www.welten-verbinden.de/taff/ (accessed last 01.06.2022).</p> <p>Utler, A. & Schmid, S. (2014): <i>TAFF – Therapeutische Angebote für Flüchtlinge. Zwischenbericht. Stand: 31.12.2014. Im Auftrag des Diakonischen Werkes Bayern mit Unterstützung der STIFTUNG WELTEN VERBINDEN</i>. STIFTUNG WELTEN VERBINDEN: Nuremberg. https://www.welten-</p>
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	verbinden.de/uploads/media/Projektabschnitt_1.pdf (accessed last, 31.05.2022)
Date of documentation	31.05.2022/01.06.2022

Italy, South Tyrol

Authors: Mia Scotti (UniTo) with the contribution from Monica Gilli and Andrea Membretti

Domus Sportello (DS)	
General information	
Type of good/new practice	Project
Area of action	Employment & housing
Adopting body	Non-governmental ecclesiastical body adopting a local initiative/project
Level of good/new practice	Local
Location and geographical coverage	Implemented in Italy in the province of Bolzano, Trentino Alto Adige region.
Responsibility for good practice	Caritas Diocesi Bolzano-Bressanone
Duration	Started in July 2020 and still ongoing
Key words	Integration, housing, employment, empowerment
Content of the good/new practice	
Objectives of the good/new practice	The Domus Sportello project aims to support people housing and job opportunities access, and to raise citizens and local institution awareness of vulnerability and poverty conditions in their community. The project works to foster a co-responsibility path by all with respect to people suffering such problems.
Target group(s)	DS activities are targeted to help homeless and people living in insecure accommodation by no distinction of race, age or origin. The service is related to other Caritas services such as CAS centers (extraordinary reception centres) or temporary house and hosting houses. Through this interaction, the DS may intercept potential beneficiaries and people in need.
Methodology	The DS service is located in Bolzano and is open with a flexible timetable to reach as many potential beneficiaries as possible. An individual inclusion path is settled for each recipients, which can also include targeted training sessions. The project aims to go beyond implementing actions to support people involved by activating resources and building a network around them.

Key facts	<p>The Domus Sportello project supports people finding accommodation and employment: these are two key factors in promoting people inclusion into local communities, especially for people living in vulnerable and poor conditions. These services are targeted to both foreigners and Italians. To reach its objectives, DS also manages two housing first apartments in Bolzano, which can be offered to people in need.</p>
Background information	<p>The Domus Sportello project started in July 2020 as a response to a social emergency boosted by the economic and social crisis linked to Covid-19 pandemic. The initiative aims to respond to the scarcity of employment and housing that characterized chronically the Province of Bolzano bearing down particularly on people in vulnerable conditions.</p> <p>High rental costs, precarious employment conditions, low wages along with prejudices or fears make access to adequate housing facilities almost impossible.</p>
Achieved results	<p>In 2021, the Domus Sportello service made 350 contacts reaching totally 16 families and 13 individuals.</p> <p>The DS representatives testified that beneficiaries highly appreciated the projects strategy and approach: <i>“feedback received from accompanied persons proved that their individual educational projects are effective and became much more efficient during time. This is mainly due to the introduction of a self-assessment step, which increases self-awareness and leads to more empowerment”</i></p> <p>For 2022, the service planned to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - To open the DS services to beneficiaries from all Caritas Housing services available locally, but also to referrals from social districts and associations; - to widen the network of active citizenship and collaboration with them; - to verify and act with other institutional or private social subjects.
Impacts of the good/new practice	<p>This project created individual support pathways for beneficiaries. The local community welcomed the initiative as an additional service in favour of inclusion and social cohesion that can help in avoiding homelessness. Collaborations and</p>

	links with other local offices and services (public and private) were strengthened through the initiative.
Innovativeness	The project is designed accordingly to the local context characteristics and through individual inclusive paths is an effective tool to support fragile subjects' inclusion and integration into local community. The service acts to improve recipients' access to basic essential services like housing and instrumental ones like jobs thus improving their wellbeing and empowerment.
Constraints	The Covid-19 pandemic changed many past paradigms modifying social intervention daily actions and activities: the computerisation' of social relations has particularly hit socially vulnerable people who are normally the weakest in telematics relations (e.g. migrants who already have difficulties in the spoken language and serious difficulties in writing, and has fewer internet opportunities and instruments).
Replicability	
Replication conditions and success factors	To allow a successful replication of the initiative, a deep analysis process is needed to understand which local features may reduce people's access to jobs and housing facilities.
Replicability and/or up-scaling	As the project tends to give an immediate response to housing and employments needs while structuring and supporting a local network around beneficiaries, it seems hard to extend these two specific actions to a regional or even national level. Nevertheless, the method, on which the project is based, can be replicated on a larger scale through: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Local context understanding (which strengths, opportunities, challenges and threats can be revealed and solved?); - Promoting an integrated intervention that offers complimentary services (e.g. offer job placement services together with vocational training services, housing support services alongside with inclusive pathways and community networking.)
Selection of good practice	
Reasons for choosing the good/new practice	Caritas is active worldwide with several years of experience in supporting integration processes and projects at local level. In

	<p>Italy, Caritas Italia is present with 50 years of experience in supporting people in need. It works with several types of beneficiaries in different sectors (health, accommodations, welcoming, peace etc.) targeting actions and projects on local contexts specificities and beneficiaries' needs. For such reasons, its activity may be considered a best practice in promoting inclusive bottom-up initiatives and projects. The bottom-up approach characterized strongly the Domus Sportello service. DS originated from local challenges considering each beneficiary's needs and difficulty to support his/her inclusion process. Access to work and a decent house are two vehicles of empowerment, inclusion and wellbeing. Additionally, DS can be considered an example of integrated process due to its connection with other Caritas services.</p>
Selection of European good/new practices	<p>Caritas is present worldwide, in Europe and Italy as relevant institution promoting inclusion, integration and fighting vulnerability with its projects. In respect to this case-specific best practice, it must be worth considering that access to work and a decent house are two vehicles of empowerment, inclusion and well-being and this is true beyond Italy's borders.</p>
Personal experiences	<p>The Italian MATILDE research team had not a direct experience with this practice. However, Caritas Bolzano, an active local research partner in Matilde, reported this experience as good practices suitable candidate. After some in-depth analysis, the practice was selected as one of the Italian good practices. Moreover, CARITAS representative involved in the DS are the same involved during the MATILDE action research activities which in the check of competences tool application which will be also used in the activities of the Sportello.</p>
Validation/evaluation external	None external evaluation.
Validation/evaluation by project team	CSWG representative, Domus Sportello representative and research team have analysed jointly this practice to validate it
Sources	
Source(s) to the good/new practice	Not available at the moment
Date of documentation	15 April 2022

Figure 16 - Domus Sportello (DS) © Caritas Bolzano

Checklist for good/new practice selection

The selected good/new practice ...	
is innovative.	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?: DS is a relatively new project linked to other Caritas initiatives and based/motivated by local conditions that hinder inclusion.</p>
develops creative solutions.	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?: DS is interested in developing also new accommodation models or in testing innovative tools for job seekers.</p>
succeeds in achieving its objective(s).	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?: The project started in 2020 and reached already some beneficiaries. The project is achieving its expected goals and the service will be extended to more beneficiaries in 2022.</p>
is ethical.	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p>

	<p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?:</p> <p>It is ethical because its goals include improving access to work, promoting equality, respect for certain basic rights: access to housing and work.</p>
is fair.	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?:</p> <p>The project promotes fragile people empowerment improving their access to jobs and housing facilities.</p>
Is been proven/evaluated (ideally: has been tested and validated) to work well and produce good results.	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?:</p> <p>CARITAS promotes an annual based relation and analysis of its projects. Through this instrument, CARITAS finds the project successful and decided to extend it to 2022.</p>
is replicable.	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?:</p> <p>The method, on which the project is based, can be replicated on a large scale.</p>
improves migrants' rights.	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?:</p> <p>Finding housing and work is linked to the exercise of people's basic rights.</p>
is inclusive with regard to people with a migrant background.	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?:</p> <p>Yes it is because the service is open to everyone who needs.</p>
works with a whole of government approach.	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?:</p> <p>DS also considers other related topics, such as education, health, mobility etc.</p>

<p>improves the well-being of migrants</p>	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?:</p> <p>Access to housing and jobs are two fundamental means of wellbeing.</p>
<p>is gender sensitive.</p>	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?:</p> <p>The service provided is targeted and defined by the personal recipients' characteristics and needs. So it is gender sensitive.</p>
<p>fosters societal diversity.</p>	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?:</p> <p>The service is targeted and defined by the personal recipients' characteristics and needs. By involving also other parts of the population, it promotes societal diversity.</p>
<p>develops possibilities for a safe and orderly regular migration.</p>	<p>Yes <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p>
<p>fosters preparedness and resilience to migration events/crises.</p>	<p>Yes <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p>
<p>realizes a participatory and/or multi-level governance approach.</p>	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?:</p> <p>The project promotes also sensibilisation activities with local community and stakeholders.</p>
<p>promotes effective funding mechanism.</p>	<p>Yes <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p>
<p>fosters effective monitoring and evaluation approaches.</p>	<p>Yes <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p>

Authors: Mia Scotti (UniTo) with the contribution from Monica Gilli and Andrea Membretti

MARKAS	
General information	
Type of good/new practice	Private company recruitment and employment policy
Area of action	Employment
Adopting body	Markas: Private service company
Level of good/new practice	National
Location and geographical coverage	Italy, area of Bolzano
Responsibility for good practice	Markas company and its managers
Duration	Ongoing
Key words	Inclusion, employment, empowerment
Content of the good/new practice	
Objectives of the good/new practice	<p>Markas is a service company with multi-ethnic staff. In Italy the company has 6903 employees, 29% of whom are foreigners coming from 91 different countries. If we refer to Markas South Tyrol alone, the percentage of foreign workers is very high: out of the 870 workers, 461 (53%) are foreigners. Nevertheless, as reported by its managers, Markas pursues an equity policy in its management, without being concentrated only on migrants but being focused instead of not making a difference of age, race, ethnicity, gender or provenience in its recruitment policy. Markas has been part of the action research activities conducted under the MATILDE project testing the tool “check of competences” (CoC) that aims to foster and capture migrants’ soft skills and professional abilities.</p>
Target group(s)	All Markas employees and migrants/foreigners employees to test and use of the tool “check of competences”.
Methodology	<p>Markas pursues an equity management policy without making difference of age, race, ethnicity, gender or provenience. The Company has a high rate of foreign employees and through its activities (such as its involvement in the MATILDE project and the application of the “check of competences”) fosters an inclusive policy among its staff. The Company promotes other initiatives/activities to support an</p>

	<p>inclusive work environment such as: - engagement in workspace atmosphere surveys to understand how employees perceived their work environment and how it can be improved; - staff training services to support talent development; workers psychological support (during the COVID 19 pandemic, Markas established this type of support for its employees; adoption of visual communication tools to enable not native speaker (often migrants) in their daily working activities. A system of coloured dots is used to enable cleaning and sanitation staff to better understand products use and toxicity.</p>
<p>Key facts</p>	<p>Markas is a company that offers specialised complementary services to public and private customers. Examples are sanitization and catering, logistics and reception in hospitals and floor management in hotels. The company works in Italy, Austria and Germany and has approximately 9,000 employees and 30 years of experience. Markas pursues an inclusive policy and promotes a culture of exchange and growth within its group. It has been a field partner of the MATILDE project in South Tyrol, promoting the use of the Check of Competences tool with its migrant workers.</p>
<p>Background information</p>	<p>Markas promotes an inclusive workspace as a central value of its activities. This approach is based on the recognition of the unique strengths, skills and talents of each employee with no specific reference to foreign workers although it certainly concerns them.</p>
<p>Achieved results</p>	<p>Markas with the engagement of its director and head of personnel tested the “check of competences” tool with some already employed TCN workers and migrants looking for employment. The overall feedback on the tool implementation was positive and gave the chance to Markas managers to better understand migrants’ employees’ backgrounds, skills and ambitions.</p> <p>Within its activities, Markas promotes also training initiatives with a high rate of participation among its employees.</p>
<p>Impacts of the good/new practice</p>	<p>Markas representatives reported a positive impact of their “inclusive” initiatives among their employees both in the case of CoC and in the other activities (e.g training; bonus;</p>

	<p>workspace atmosphere survey). The CoC experience has been the chance to better understand the inclusion topics with specific reference to people with a migrant background. Beneficiaries appreciated the tool as means to valorize their skills and experiences.</p>
Innovativeness	<p>The innovativeness of the practice is related to the way the CoC has been proposed and used to make a connection between Markas, migrants background employees, job-seeker migrants and third sector associations (e.g. Caritas) that support the testing and participated in the selection of migrants willing to be included in this experimentation. The CoC in this case created a “common language” between the people involved. The “Balance of competences” tool was indeed already utilized by Markas in a more general perspective without targeting the instrument for a specific group.</p>
Constraints	<p>CoC needs time to be implemented and some preliminary activities made to select the right participants. This may be a challenge for recruiters as for migrants. Furthermore, the languages in which the instrument is available should be increased to be used with people coming from different countries.</p>
Replicability	
Replication conditions and success factors	<p>Companies and/or communities to whom inclusion is an added value.</p>
Replicability and/or up-scaling	<p>The experience may be replicated up- scaling institutionalizing the instrument.</p>
Selection of good practice	
Reasons for choosing the good/new practice	<p>Markas company has been a MATILDE active participant in the action research activities with its managers and employees. The company participated in the testing of the check of competences tool to improve and better understand foreign employees’ skills and backgrounds. Markas promotes an equity policy between its employee and inclusive paths for those who needs it.</p>

Selection of European good/new practices	Access to work is an essential empowerment and inclusion means for TCNs and people in general (this is particularly true for adults). On the other side, the employment of foreign workers may stimulate innovation in a company's production and management chains through diversity and heterogeneity.
Personal experiences	Markas managers have participated actively in the field research activities of MATILDE. This research covered particularly employment inclusion matters.
Validation/evaluation external	None
Validation/evaluation by project team	Matilde researchers with a Markas representative.
Sources	
Source(s) to the good/new practice	case study
Date of documentation	03/04/2022

Figure 17 - MARKAS © Daria Akimenko

Checklist for good/new practice selection

The selected good/new practice ...	
is innovative.	Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> In what way?: In its application to specific target groups (e.g. migrants).
develops creative solutions.	Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> In what way?: With the use of supporting visual cards, the CoC develops creative solutions to capture a person soft skills.
succeeds in achieving its objective(s).	Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> In what way?: It gives to both the parts involved (Interviewers and respondents) the opportunity to better understand and valorize the respondents skills.
is fair.	Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> In what way?: Trying to go beyond formal recognition of skills and competences.
Is been proven/evaluated (ideally: has been tested and validated) to work well and produce good results.	Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> In what way?: It has been tested by Markas.
is replicable.	Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/>
improves migrants' rights.	Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
is inclusive with regard to people with a migrant background.	Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> In what way?: It is targeted to migrants.

works with a whole of government approach.	Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
improves the well-being of migrants	Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> In what way?: Indirectly, improving their opportunity to enter in the job market.
is gender sensitive.	Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
fosters societal diversity.	Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> In what way?: It is made to capture diversity and valorize it.
develops possibilities for a safe and orderly regular migration.	Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> In what way?: It is not focused on this.
fosters preparedness and resilience to migration events/crises.	Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
realizes a participatory and/or multi-level governance approach.	Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> In what way?: Involving different partners in setting up the activities.
promotes effective funding mechanism.	Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
fosters effective monitoring and evaluation approaches.	Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>

Authors: Mia Scotti (UniTo) with the contribution from Monica Gilli and Andrea Membretti

La Strada - Der Weg	
General information	
Type of good/new practice	Non-profit organization offering innovative inclusion services (e.g. ethno-clinical” training, language training services and childcare nursery service for 0-3 years old babies)
Area of action	Education, health, social cohesion, safety & stability
Adopting body	ONLUS
Level of good/new practice	Local
Location and geographical coverage	Via Visitazione 42 Bolzano, Trentino Alto Adige, Italy
Responsibility for good practice	La Strada Der Weg
Duration	Not applicable/ongoing
Key words	Health, access to health care, safety, language training
Content of the good/new practice	
Objectives of the good/new practice	<p>La Strada – Der Weg Onlus offers a wide range of services to migrants and people in difficult situations. Among these, an ethno-clinical training service is offered to improve migrants’ access to health care. This service is provided in collaboration with the GriS (immigration and health group) promoted locally by The Italian Society of Medicine of Migration. The service aims to overcome and reduce possible constraints suffered by migrants in access to medical treatments (e.g. difficulties in receiving blood transfusion due to religious or cultural beliefs). Another service offered by La Strada is the language-training support. Its prime objective is to empower migrant people to communicate with the hosting communities promoting inclusion and exchange.</p> <p>The third service to be mentioned is called “Giovani Madri” and is dedicated to improve women’s inclusion and empowerment. Projects are developed with mothers and, experimentally, with family units, to foster women’s parental responsibility, autonomy, self-determination and self-management capacity in everyday life, reconciling childcare with home management, work and any other commitments. Additionally, the project aims to help women escape from</p>

	<p>loneliness and isolation and to strengthen their social and family networks. Among the initiatives taken, baby nursery access is implemented to help young mothers to start a path of progressive autonomy (sometimes protecting them from not infrequent cases of domestic violence)</p>
Target group(s)	<p>Migrants with no distinction of race, age or origin. Giovani Madri is targeted to migrant women.</p>
Methodology	<p>All the offered services are planned with a bottom – up approach to address recipients needs.</p>
Key facts	<p>La Strada - Der Weg is a non-profit organisation offering a wide range of support services to Italians and foreigners experiencing difficult situations. The Organization offers assistance to children, minors and women victims of trafficking and exploitation; it supports youngsters in drugs and addiction rehabilitation paths; it supports families, communities and individuals through informative activities; it promotes services for those with special educational needs. The organization is active in promoting a service called "ethno-clinical" training, which aims to improve the accessibility to social and health care services for immigrant citizens.</p>
Background information	<p>Migrants' backgrounds and history may affect their inclusion path. To investigate and understand such exogenous conditions is the preliminary step to offer effective inclusion support services and projects.</p> <p>The "ethno-clinical" training aims to reduce possible boundaries to migrants' access to health care services (e.g. linked to cultural, religious and ethnic reasons).</p> <p>The language training and educational support aim to improve migrants' inclusion in local communities and in the job market escaping from segregation and, sometimes, violence situations.</p> <p>The Giovani Madri project supports women with children empowerment helping them to start a path of progressive autonomy and foster women's parental responsibility, autonomy, self-determination and capacity for self-management in everyday life.</p>

<p>Achieved results</p>	<p>The achieved results are implementing projects that improve gender empowerment and access to services like health care. Projects activities showed how language is a fundamental initial tool for creating empowerment and strengthening the network on territories.</p>
<p>Impacts of the good/new practice</p>	<p>The projects impact has mainly been related to highlight territorial realities that are part of the social system and cannot be ignored. Awareness-raising gave roots to the structuring of these services, starting from the need to arrive at programming the projects with the territorial services. In this way, we are not talking about categories but about people.</p>
<p>Innovativeness</p>	<p>As mentioned, La Strada offers a wide range of services. Locally the Onlus acts in response to particular challenges and needs of migrants who arrived in the area of Bolzano. The links with the migrants' backgrounds, which origins in different services provided, constitute a bottom-up initiative example. Is it then possible to consider the projects set-up process as innovative. Among the diverse services provided, the three services mentioned before can be considered all innovative due to their capacity to improve empowerment, access to health and offering inclusion means as language knowledge it is.</p>
<p>Constraints</p>	<p>A different attitude between migrant groups has been revealed in respect to language learning. This seems to be influenced by a wide range of factors. In some cases, language ignorance is used as control means by criminal associations who naturally reject all forms of possible means of interaction and inclusion for people they are controlling.</p>
<p>Replicability</p>	
<p>Replication conditions and success factors</p>	<p>A deep knowledge of migrant profiles, provenience, culture, religion, needs, possible psychological trauma etc. is a replication condition and success factor of the practice.</p>
<p>Replicability and/or up-scaling</p>	<p>The principle that motivates the projects and the belief that access to housing, language training, health services, jobs and family and women support are basic essential conditions of freedom can be replicated at an up-scaling rate. The</p>

	possibilities of expend the practice locally will depend on the actual results and the participation of more and more target users.
Selection of good practice	
Reasons for choosing the good/new practice	La Strada – Der Weg Onlus is a 50 years active actor of development and inclusion at local level in the province of Bolzano, where the Association works. It has a strong knowledge and experience on the inclusion topics also referring to migrants. La Strada has been also a precious CSWG partner in MATILDE research activities giving insights and highlighting particular issues in dealing with migrant inclusion into the local community.
Selection of European good/new practices	MATILDE’s Italian researchers consider it a good practice because it particularly takes into account the needs of migrants and their cultural backgrounds.
Personal experiences	MATILDE Italy’s team has worked with some La Strada Der Weg representatives to investigate about inclusion, employment and women empowerment during the action research activities.
Validation/evaluation external	None external evaluation
Validation/evaluation by project team	CSWG representative and research team
Sources	
Source(s) to the good/new practice	https://www.lastrada-derweg.org
Date of documentation	11/04/2022

Figure 18 - La Strada - Der Weg © Daria Akimenko

Checklist for good/new practice selection

The selected good/new practice ...	
is innovative.	Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> In what way?: The project considers the particular features of the target groups and includes their participation.
develops creative solutions.	Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
succeeds in achieving its objective(s).	Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> In what way?: The projects tend in progress to improve its action areas, counting positive processes. Projects results are visible in term of inclusion and access to the territory.

<p>is ethical.</p>	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?:</p> <p>Implemented projects respect people's diversity, backgrounds and feelings. This association shows to be trying to overcome the somewhat Eurocentric and secular perspective that characterizes many good development and inclusion projects: the tendency to not keep in proper weight the religious sphere of recipients that instead weighs heavily in the individual experience of those who come from other countries.</p>
<p>is fair.</p>	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?:</p> <p>Implemented projects respect people's diversity, backgrounds and feelings.</p>
<p>Is been proven/evaluated (ideally: has been tested and validated) to work well and produce good results.</p>	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?:</p> <p>Projects are active with good results.</p>
<p>is replicable.</p>	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?:</p> <p>The methodological approach is replicable in every place: it should be based on highlighting local available territorial resources and be oriented to establish projects that sustain personal autonomy.</p>
<p>improves migrants' rights.</p>	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?:</p> <p>Access to health and education are fundamental rights and some La Strada projects act directly to improve them.</p>
<p>is inclusive with regard to people with a migrant background.</p>	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?:</p>

	La Strada works directly with migrants to improve their inclusion in to local communities.
works with a whole of government approach.	Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
improves the well-being of migrants	Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> In what way?: Supporting access to language training, health care services, jobs, housing etc.
is gender sensitive.	Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> In what way?: La Strada Der Weg implements projects targeted to women empowerment.
fosters societal diversity.	Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> In what way?: By working with different background recipients.
develops possibilities for a safe and orderly regular migration.	Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
fosters preparedness and resilience to migration events/crises.	Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
realizes a participatory and/or multi-level governance approach.	Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> In what way?: Every level of the governance is involved and actively participates in project planning and meetings to reach the needs of the target groups and the territory. The approach is fully transversal.
promotes effective funding mechanism.	Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
fosters effective monitoring and evaluation approaches.	Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>

Italy, Metropolitan City of Turin

Authors: Mia Scotti (UniTo) with the contribution from Monica Gilli and Andrea Membretti

Diaconia Valdese and its hosting services	
General information	
Type of good/new practice	Hosting service
Area of action	Housing, health, safety & stability, rights & citizenship
Adopting body	Ecclesiastical body
Level of good/new practice	Local
Location and geographical coverage	Torre Pollice, Piemonte, Italy
Responsibility for good practice	Diaconia Valdese
Duration	Ongoing
Key words	Assistance, fair employment policy, inclusion
Content of the good/new practice	
Objectives of the good/new practice	<p>The Diaconia Valdese (DV) is a non-profit ecclesiastical body that links and coordinates the social activities of the Waldensian Church in Italy. It manages structures and assistance services for elderly, minors, disabled, adults in difficulty and migrants. Among its services, the DV offers assistance and housing support through Assisted Living Residences (RA).</p> <p>The DV RA service aims to host and support self-sufficient and partially self-sufficient elderly. In developing such activities, DV adopts an inclusive recruitment approach recruiting several migrants and foreigners (e.g. In the RA Rifugio Carlo Alberto the 15% of the employees are foreigners).</p>
Target group(s)	Elderly, minors, young people, disabled and migrants.

<p>Methodology</p>	<p>DV places the dignity of human beings at the centre of its activities, intervening in favour of the elderly, young people, the disabled and adults in difficulty, committing itself to bring relief in situations of suffering. Its services are open to all without discrimination of gender, affiliation, culture or religious belief. DV manages its services according to the principle of transparency, quality and effectiveness of interventions, without any confessional imposition. It is worth observing that their sensitivity to issues of inclusion and welcome is due to their not-so-recent past as persecuted and migrants (in VAI Pellice there are routes in the mountains that recall the exile of Waldensians who fled Piedmont as persecuted)</p>
<p>Key facts</p>	<p>The Diaconia Valdese is a non-profit ecclesiastical organization that offers, connects and coordinates social services and manages around 15 care and welcome facilities in various regions of Italy. Among its housing facilities, four are in the province of Turin. These are Rifugio Carlo Alberto, La casa delle Diaconesse, Uliveto and Asilo dei Vecchi. The RA Rifugio Carlo Alberto is also an example of an adopted inclusive recruitment policy with the 15% with 15% of staff being immigrants.</p>
<p>Background information</p>	<p>The RA services are implemented to support people in need, their families and the community. Those are open to all even if mainly directed to elderly and disabled people. The activities respond to inclusion, empowerment and support needs.</p>
<p>Achieved results</p>	<p>The Rifugio Carlo Alberto can accommodate up to 84 people in in-patient care and 12 in the day Centre. It employs 12 foreigners within its staff.</p> <p>L'asilo dei vecchi accommodates up to 94 self-sufficient and non-self-sufficient guests.</p> <p>La Casa delle Diaconesse offer 29 places. The Casa delle Diaconesse offers a 24-hour care service with qualified OSS (Operatore Socio Sanitario) staff.</p> <p>The Uliveto can accommodate up to 21 people with severe and very severe physical and mental disabilities divided into two communities: Comunità Aria (11 people) and Comunità Terra (10 people).</p>

Impacts of the good/new practice	<p>As reported by a the former Rifugio Carlo Alberto director ” recruitment of foreigners or migrant background people happens with an open mind approach, not being focused directly on this aspect.” What always counted was to capacity to work well of each of the new employees.</p> <p>People enter the job often after several years living in Italy and after completing a professional course and therefore speaking and understanding Italian well.</p> <p>RA Rifugio Re Carlo Alberto is a place with a welcoming history: Several foreign volunteers have been hosted in the years, sometimes for 9/12 months, even without knowing Italian language. Is it possible to speak of an habit of leaving with different backgrounds people and of a practice to catch this as an opportunity.</p> <p>The impact on social cohesion has been positive.</p>
Innovativeness	In respect to migrants’ target group, the services impact on them indirectly through migrants’ employment in the housing services facilities.
Constraints	The interaction between older people and sometimes black foreigners represented a potential difficulty. However, this aspect did not represent any difficulty.
Replicability	
Replication conditions and success factors	Adequate hosting facilities availability.
Replicability and/or up-scaling	An open and not discriminatory recruitment practice should be common practice everywhere.
Selection of good practice	
Reasons for choosing the good/new practice	This service is aimed at helping and supporting people who are not self-sufficient. The way it is implemented, also through a non-discriminatory recruitment policy, is an example of how things should normally work.
Selection of European good/new practices	This practice and approach can be replicated everywhere so it worth to be mentioned.
Personal experiences	The MATILDE research team worked with DV representatives during the action research activities. DV representatives bring their experience and insights regarding migrant employment

	in the DV. Access to employment is a particularly relevant issue for the inclusion of migrants in Piedmont.
Validation/evaluation external	none external evaluation.
Validation/evaluation by project team	Matilde Italy research team and DV representative.
Sources	
Source(s) to the good/new practice	https://dvv.diaconiavaldese.org/
Date of documentation	28/04/2022

Figure 19 - Diaconia Valdese and its hosting services © UNITO Team

Checklist for good/new practice selection

The selected good/new practice ...	
is innovative.	Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
develops creative solutions.	Yes <input type="checkbox"/>

	No <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
succeeds in achieving its objective(s).	Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> In what way?: The experience works well and both RA beneficiaries and employees seem to benefit from the initiative.
is ethical.	Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> In what way?: DV manages its services according to principles of transparency, quality and effectiveness of interventions.
is fair.	Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> In what way?: It is open to all without discrimination of gender, affiliation, culture or religious belief.
Is been proven/evaluated (ideally: has been tested and validated) to work well and produce good results.	Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/>
is replicable.	Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> In what way?: The approach is replicable.
improves migrants' rights.	Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> In what way?: Support their access to work and employment.
is inclusive with regard to people with a migrant background.	Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> In what way?: Yes, in respect to migrant employees.
works with a whole of government approach.	Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
improves the well-being of migrants	Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> In what way?:

	Yes, in respect to migrant employees.
is gender sensitive.	Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
fosters societal diversity.	Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> In what way?: Yes, through the recruitment of migrants and hosting foreigners volunteers.
develops possibilities for a safe and orderly regular migration.	Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
fosters preparedness and resilience to migration events/crises.	Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
realizes a participatory and/or multi-level governance approach.	Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
promotes effective funding mechanism.	Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
fosters effective monitoring and evaluation approaches.	Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>

Authors: Mia Scotti (UniTo) with the contribution from Monica Gilli and Andrea Membretti

CRI SUSA support and information service to prevent illegal crossing of the Alps over to France (MigrAlp)	
General information	
Type of good/new practice	MigrAlp: Support and information project by Cri Susa
Area of action	Security, health, safety & stability, rights & citizenship, first aid
Adopting body	Non-governmental voluntary association
Level of good/new practice	Local
Location and geographical coverage	Corso Stati Uniti, 5, 10059 Susa Susa Valley, Piedmont
Responsibility for good practice	CriSusa Comitato di Susa - ODV, Voluntary association
Duration	CRI Susa has been formally established in 1998. Its activity is still ongoing. The MigrAlp project started in 2017
Key words	Asylum seekers, security, safety
Content of the good/new practice	
Objectives of the good/new practice	CRI Susa association is committed to: offering support and assistance to people in vulnerable conditions, preventing in collaboration with local institutions new vulnerability cases and situations, responding to emergencies, promoting inclusion across local communities, supporting people in a rehabilitation and inclusion paths, promoting a culture of solidarity, not violence and peace. It acts with the dual goals of 1. helping migrants move on and 2. trying to convince others to stay, linking them to projects developed by them or in association with other local entities.
Target group(s)	CRI Susa activities are varied and targeted to diverse beneficiaries. CRI Susa offers health support services, social inclusion projects, responses to crises and emergencies and projects focused on increasing communities' resilience by prevention and disaster preparedness. The MigrAlp project based in Susa Valley supports asylum seekers with particular reference to the problem of illegal crossing over to France through the Alps. In this case, beneficiaries are migrants and asylum seekers that wish to

	<p>join France by passing through the Italian Alps (irregularly and mainly during the night risking their own life).</p>
Methodology	<p>Assistance in the border area, safe Point and emergency reception facilities are some of the activities offered by Cri - Susa to concretely help thousands of people over the years. In this case, the CRI Susa operates by giving information, the chance to take a shower and rest, a glass of hot tea, a thermal blanket or accompaniment to a safe place to spend the night. The idea is to offer small gestures to rest human and help people in need.</p>
Key facts	<p>CRI (Croce Rossa Italiana) Susa is part of the Italian Red Cross a voluntary association active in the humanitarian field. The Association carries out various activities such as reception, inclusion, social and health care services. In Susa Valley (Piedmont), in relation to the migratory situation of the area characterized by migrants trying to cross illegally the Alps over to France, CRI Susa is particularly committed to preventing this phenomenon through information, support activities in the Valley and offering aid and shelter to asylum seekers (project MigrAlp).</p>
Background information	<p>From 2017, the province of Turin was particularly stressed by an high risk practice known as "La Via delle Apli", the illegal border crossing of the Alps to reach France.</p> <p>Crossing the Alps in winter under challenging weather conditions (snow and temperatures reaching -15°) putted many migrants' life in danger while attempting to reach the French soil by foot, often at night.</p> <p>Since the beginning, the Italian Red Cross has been active to provide assistance and help migrants in difficulty in this attempt.</p>
Achieved results	<p>The project aims to provide assistance and relief to migrants in transit on the Italian/French border; the main mission is to protect the health and integrity of people trying to cross the border through the mountains.</p> <p>The beneficiaries positively perceive the intervention, which is often essential, especially when reaches the most fragile situations.</p>

Impacts of the good/new practice	<p>The impact on the direct beneficiaries (migrants) and indirect ones (the entire community living and staying in the area) was positive.</p> <p>The project intervention has always been appreciated locally despite the generalized difficulties in approaching the topic of "migration".</p>
Innovativeness	<p>The "good practice" improves the livelihoods of beneficiaries as it is often the only real source of support and assistance when they transit that Apls area. The practice acts on the primary livelihoods needs of migrants present temporary on the territory to cross the near borders with France.</p>
Constraints	<p>The main challenges are related to the difficulties (but at the same time the opportunities) of working in partnership with other partners and institutions and the complexity of finding economic resources to make the project sustainable.</p>
Replicability	
Replication conditions and success factors	<p>The project is strictly connected with the Alps crossing phenomenon. The project offers a first aid and support to migrants who are trying to reach France. An empathy approach could be advocated for all integration projects, but the project itself seems hard to be replicated out of a very similar situation.</p>
Replicability and/or up-scaling	<p>The project is activated in response to an emergency need and is strictly connected with local features so it is hard to imagine its replicability up-scaling</p>
Selection of good practice	
Reasons for choosing the good/new practice	<p>MigrAlp project answers to an emergency need but it is also related to the reflection on migrants' aspirations and settlement desires. Migrants attempting to reach France irregularly do not consider Italy (and particularly the Val di Susa area) a possible settlement territory for their future. The project giving support and information is sometimes the first vehicle to let migrants aware of settlement opportunities in Italy and the first step of their inclusion in the local community.</p>

Selection of European good/new practices	The irregular border transit under dangerous conditions can matter also in other local contexts. The phenomenon also deals with complex aspects and migrants settlement desires, expectations, migration routes, reception system and opportunities. This experience highlights these problems, its potential consequences and opens a road to overcome the problems causing it.
Personal experiences	A CriSusa operator involved in the project MigrAlp participated in the action research activity of Matilde in the Italian case study “Metropolitan City of Turin”.
Validation/evaluation external	None external evaluation
Validation/evaluation by project team	Matilde Italy research team and Cri – Susa representative
Sources	
Source(s) to the good/new practice	https://www.cri-susa.it/
Date of documentation	26/04/2022

Figure 20 - CRI SUSA support and information service to prevent illegal crossing of the Alps over to France (MigrAlp)©
Municipality of Bussoleno and Bussoleno Red Cross

Checklist for good/new practice selection

The selected good/new practice ...	
is innovative.	Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
develops creative solutions.	Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
succeeds in achieving its objective(s).	Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> In what way?: The project helped a high number of migrants in difficulties. About 18,000 beneficiaries have been reached since the start of the activities.
is ethical.	Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> In what way?: It gives primary livelihood support to migrants who need it beyond the illegal action that they are trying to commit.
is fair.	Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> In what way?: The project supports migrants crossing the Alps route without discrimination of gender, affiliation, culture or religious belief.
Is been proven/evaluated (ideally: has been tested and validated) to work well and produce good results.	Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> In what way?: The project started five years ago and is still working well.
is replicable.	Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
improves migrants' rights.	Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> In what way?: The project acts to save migrants' life.

<p>is inclusive with regard to people with a migrant background.</p>	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?: It is dedicated to migrants.</p>
<p>works with a whole of government approach.</p>	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?: Cri-Susa tries to act in partnership with other local associations, volunteers and institutions to support migrants in the emergency but also to include them in an integration path.</p>
<p>improves the well-being of migrants</p>	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?: Through first aid support.</p>
<p>is gender sensitive.</p>	<p>Yes <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p>
<p>fosters societal diversity.</p>	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?: The project gives first aid and support to migrants crossing the Alps to join France (often saving their life). In addition to this first help, information and support are offered to improve their settlement opportunities in Italy.</p>
<p>develops possibilities for a safe and orderly regular migration.</p>	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?: The project acts to prevent irregular migration by enhancing safety and regular migration.</p>
<p>fosters preparedness and resilience to migration events/crises.</p>	<p>Yes <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p>
<p>realizes a participatory and/or multi-level governance approach.</p>	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?:</p>

	It tries to build a local network of person, associations, institutions working to help migrants in the area.
promotes effective funding mechanism.	Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
fosters effective monitoring and evaluation approaches.	Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/>

Authors: Mia Scotti (UniTo) with the contribution from Monica Gilli and Andrea Membretti

Morus Onlus and its projects and services	
General information	
Type of good/new practice	Association
Area of action	Social cohesion
Adopting body	Non-governmental voluntary association organized in the form of ONLUS
Level of good/new practice	Local
Location and geographical coverage	Piazza Europa 22, Ceres, Piedmont, Italy
Responsibility for good practice	Morus Onlus
Duration	The association was born in 2014. It is still active with its activities and projects
Key words	Inclusion, social cohesion, migrants support
Content of the good/new practice	
Objectives of the good/new practice	Moro Onlus supports migrants in their inclusion path through projects and activities that foster social cohesion, exchange activities and work inclusion. The Onlus promotes inclusivity, antiracism and welcoming values.
Target group(s)	Migrants and asylum seekers in the Val di Lanzo area.
Methodology	The activity and projects promoted by the Moro Onlus originated in order to support the relationship and exchange among migrants, asylum seekers and the local community of Val di Lanzo in Piedmont. To do so, several projects have been implemented to bring together locals and newcomers through leisure and free time activities (this is the case of the experience of Coro Moro (a choral activity), and Moro Team (a football team) or through work support activities as Moro Style tailoring activities that enhance the fabrics and creativity of the migrants involved. So, the method adopted is based on a bottom - up approach that aims to support migrants in their inclusion path through employability and social inclusion.
Key facts	Morus Onlus intends to help migrants and people in need in their social and working inclusion path in Italy. It also supports local projects in migrants' origin countries. It was founded by active volunteers in the Lanzo Valley, Piedmont,

	Italy. Among its initiatives, it is worth mentioning the Coro Moro, a successful activity that brought together migrants and locals in a choral activity to facilitate the learning and practice of the Italian language and through this, the inclusion of migrants into the local community.
Background information	Moro Onlus originated from the initiative of some volunteers inhabitants of the Lanzo Valley. In 2014 a first group of asylum seekers has been hosted in Ceres, a small municipality of the Valley. By this way, some local citizens took the chance to offer their support to this group of migrants through language training and general support. Over time, with a progressively increasing number of new migrants arriving in the area, volunteers decided to start the Association giving more stability to their initiatives.
Achieved results	Thanks to the activity of Morus Onlus, a large group of migrants decided to settle in the Valley. Some got married and formed new families. Everyone works stably
Impacts of the good/new practice	The residency of migrants with their family and their work stability has made possible to radically change the perception that people had of them. Now they are seen as villagers and no longer as foreigners
Innovativeness	The innovativeness of this practice is related to the single projects activated by the ONLUS: e.g. the case of CoroMoro reveals to be extremely helpful in favouring the migrants learning of the Italian language. This method, founded on leisure and contact with the local community through singing tradition is an example of a good bottom-up practice that may enforce the link between migrants and communities.
Constraints	The initial distrust of migrants was overcome by making them perceived as an integral part of society
Replicability	
Replication conditions and success factors	To be replicable, the activities to be implemented should be related to particular features/traditions/characteristics of the context considered.
Replicability and/or up-scaling	The experience can be replicated but needs to be tailored to the context where it has to be implemented.

Selection of good practice	
Reasons for choosing the good/new practice	MoroOnlus has been chosen as a best practice due to its peculiarities, its voluntary base, and its projects closely linked to the characteristics of the territory.
Selection of European good/new practices	MATILDE should bring attentions on local, small practices and experiences giving a broad view of the inclusion experiences and their application in the various territories
Personal experiences	A MoroOnlus representative participated in the MATILDE research activities of WP3
Validation/evaluation external	None external evaluation
Validation/evaluation by project team	MATILDE research team in collaboration with a MoroOnlus representative
Sources	
Source(s) to the good/new practice	https://www.facebook.com/morusonlus/
Date of documentation	12/04/2022

Figure 21 - Morus Onlus and its projects and services ©Metropolitan City of Turin

Checklist for good/new practice selection

The selected good/new practice ...	
is innovative.	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?:</p> <p>It is a particular example of activities and projects to support inclusion in different dimensions (e.g. community, employability).</p>
develops creative solutions.	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?:</p> <p>E.g. It adopts creative methods to support language learning.</p>
succeeds in achieving its objective(s).	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p>

is ethical.	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?: E.g in the tailoring project which enhance the fabrics and creativity of the migrants involved.</p>
is fair.	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?: It is open to migrants who wish to be involved. All those who had the desire to participate in activities with Morus Onlus were involved.</p>
Is been proven/evaluated (ideally: has been tested and validated) to work well and produce good results.	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?: The activities gave good results giving the root to the Association establishment.</p>
is replicable.	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?: Projects and activities are replicable by tailoring them to the context considered.</p>
improves migrants' rights.	<p>Yes <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p>
is inclusive with regard to people with a migrant background.	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?: Projects and initiatives are dedicated to migrants.</p>
works with a whole of government approach.	<p>Yes <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p>
improves the well-being of migrants	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?: Promoting their inclusion in to the local community and work market.</p>
is gender sensitive.	<p>Yes <input type="checkbox"/></p>

	<p>No <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?:</p> <p>There are no barriers to gender differences in Morus' activities. Everyone can participate</p>
fosters societal diversity.	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p>
develops possibilities for a safe and orderly regular migration.	<p>Yes <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p>
fosters preparedness and resilience to migration events/crises.	<p>Yes <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p>
realizes a participatory and/or multi-level governance approach.	<p>Yes <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p>
promotes effective funding mechanism.	<p>Yes <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p>
fosters effective monitoring and evaluatio approaches.	<p>Yes <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p>

Norway

Authors: Maria Taivalsaari Røhnebæk

Language Friend	
General information	
Type of good/new practice	Service
Area of action	Language and Culture
Adopting body	Volunteer organizations, volunteers
Level of good/new practice	Local
Location and geographical coverage	The example of the use of language friends was in our research identified in the municipalities located in the region of Midt-Gudbrandsdal, but it is also a broader national initiative organized by different NGOs such as the Norwegian Women's Public Health Association (N.K.S).
Responsibility for good practice	Norwegian Women's Public Health Association (N.K.S.) or more informally organized volunteers.
Duration	The initiative is ongoing, the starting date is not clear but N.K.S. has gradually built up the initiative and 65 local associations were running 'Language Friend' at the end of 2019.
Key words	Meeting place, socializing, informal language training
Content of the good/new practice	
Objectives of the good/new practice	Low threshold services created to built trust, create a sense of belonging and foster participation and social inclusion through the use of the Norwegian language in relation with activities and informal conversations.
Target group(s)	Immigrants and particularly women with immigrant background. 'Language friend' is largely offered to forced migrants / refugees but work migrants can also be participants
Methodology	A guide and handbook have been developed to support and prepare participants

<p>Key facts</p>	<p>Språkvenn (= Language friend) activities are low-threshold services adapted to local conditions and reflect the wishes and needs of the participants. The activities are based on the women's resources and interests so that they can use their abilities while at the same time learning Norwegian and building networks. These activities can be anything from cooking classes to swimming lessons, knitting evenings, theme classes, pure language training, tea and game nights, etc.</p>
<p>Background information</p>	<p>Social inclusion and labour market inclusion are highly dependent on mastering the Norwegian language. With this initiative, migrants are introduced to networks, recreational activities and are provided with opportunities to practice everyday language at the same time. This is an important supplement to the more formal language training offered by local government to forced migrants through the introduction program.</p>
<p>Achieved results</p>	<p>The Directorate of Integration and Diversity assesses this initiative as successful means for stimulating fellowship, building trust and creating a sense of belonging to local communities. It is seen as strengthening social capital both in terms of bridging and bonding social capital. Participants meet others in similar situation, but also people they would otherwise not associate with. See also: https://www.imdi.no/en/sprakvenn-language-friend--a-meeting-place-that-helps-integration Informants and participants in the participatory action research of Matilde, highlighted as the value of having a language friend. This is for instance illustrated with the following quote from one of the interviews: <i>"I am very found of my language friend. We meet up every week and talk about our different cultures and about Norway. We address one specific theme each time"</i></p>
<p>Impacts of the good/new practice</p>	<p>The language friend initiative can be expected to strengthen social and labor market inclusion among inclusion thereby contributing to social cohesion. However, there has not been systematic evaluations of the initiative documenting results and impact.</p>

Innovativeness	The initiative can contribute to built trust and strengthen social capital (bridging and bonding) among migrants. It is a low threshold service, which is easy to adopt and implement. It can be more or less formalized and has existed in various forms for a long time, and in that sense, it is not particularly innovative practice.
Constraints	Constraints relate mainly to challenges of recruiting volunteers and there can be some challenges related to having resources to coordinate and ensure good matching in language friended relationships.
Replicability	
Replication conditions and success factors	The initiative is fairly simple and can be easily described and thus presented and adopted by others. A small guide has been developed by N.K.S that can help others to adopt the initiative, the organization also offers different kinds of training materials that can support the work available through the website. The organization also offers guidance and support for communities that want to offer and organize 'language friend'.
Replicability and/or up-scaling	The practice has already been scaled and replicated in various local communities. The challenge is to sustain the service which rely on access to eligible volunteers.
Selection of good practice	
Reasons for choosing the good/new practice	The initiative was highlighted as particularly valuable among migrants taking part in the participatory action research conducted in the Norwegian Matilde study, and the offering of different kinds of mentorships, like språkvenn was the most commonly suggested 'solution' in the workshops (World Cafes) organized in two regions in the Norwegian study. Thus, it was chosen as a good practice because it was highly valued and called for by the migrants themselves.
Selection of European good/new practices	And because it is a low threshold initiative which is fairly easy to implement and replicate and it is not costly. There are potentially a series of win-wins for the migrants and the host community since it contributes to build trust and strengthens

	social capital and social cohesion. It is also identified as 'Good Practice' by IMDi.
Personal experiences	The local partners have experience with the use of language friends in their communities and as a supplement to government integration services.
Validation/evaluation external	An assessment of the initiative has been made by The Directorate of Integration and Diversity (IMDi) but we have not found any systematic external evaluations of 'language friends' specifically.
Validation/evaluation by project team	The initiative has not been validated or evaluated by the Matilde team, we have only learned about the initiative through the stories of informants and participants participatory workshops, and through secondary sources online.
Sources	
Source(s) to the good/new practice	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) The Directorate of Integration and Diversity (IMDi) https://www.imdi.no/en/sprakvenn-language-friend--a-meeting-place-that-helps-integration https://www.imdi.no/lar-fra-andre/sprakvenn--en-moteplass-som-bidrar-til-integrering/ 2) Norwegian Women's Public Health Association (N.K.S) https://sanitetskvinnene.no/medlemsnett-grunnleggende/sprakvenn
Date of documentation	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Last updated August 23rd 2022 2) Not stated

Figure 22 - Language Friend (1) © Per Åge Eriksen

Checklist for good/new practice selection

The selected good/new practice ...	
is innovative.	Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> In what way?: The practice is not particularly innovative since different forms mentorships or 'language friend' has been offered for a long time in the communities in more or less structured and formalized manners. It can still be an innovative practice in communities that have not offered this kind of service before. As always, the innovativeness depends on the context.
develops creative solutions.	Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> In what way?: Not relevant.
succeeds in achieving its objective(s).	Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/>

	<p>In what way?:</p> <p>As described above.</p>
is ethical.	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?:</p> <p>It is ethical as long as there are certain structures that help safeguard the establishment of language friend relations and resources available to prepare participants.</p>
is fair.	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?:</p> <p>Because it is a low-threshold service which is easily accessible. However, the focus is mainly on providing language friends for women with forced migrant backgrounds. This is 'fair' in the sense that they are more commonly excluded from the labor market than and may need more support to access arenas for practicing Norwegian and be active outside the home which is prerequisite for social inclusion. Still, there may be other migrant groups that are not prioritized and which could also benefit from the language friend service.</p>
Is been proven/evaluated (ideally: has been tested and validated) to work well and produce good results.	<p>Yes <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?:</p> <p>No, not systematically and comprehensively to our knowledge.</p>
is replicable.	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?:</p> <p>Yes, it is replicable as described above.</p>
improves migrants' rights.	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?:</p> <p>Yes, because language competence is key to participation.</p>
is inclusive with regard to people with a migrant background.	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p>

	<p>In what way?:</p> <p>Yes, because it targets people with migrant background, but it can be less accessible for certain migrant groups – see comment above regarding ‘fair’.</p>
works with a whole of government approach.	<p>Yes <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?:</p> <p>No, it is a service offered by volunteers or volunteer organizations in some collaboration with the government.</p>
improves the well-being of migrants	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?:</p> <p>Yes, is seen to strengthen social capital, enhances trust and sense of belonging, improves language skills and even health competence.</p>
is gender sensitive.	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?:</p> <p>It is gender sensitive in the sense that is mainly targeting Migrant women which face more obstacles for labor market inclusion compared to men. The labor market disadvantageous for migrant women and there is need for initiatives to counter act these tendencies and lower the thresholds for labor market inclusion.</p>
fosters societal diversity.	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?:</p> <p>I don't find this relevant.</p>
develops possibilities for a safe and orderly regular migration.	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?:</p> <p>It represents resource that may contribute to integration and social inclusion (but the statement is unclear).</p>
fosters preparedness and resilience to migration events/crises.	<p>Yes <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p>

realizes a participatory and/or multi-level governance approach.	Yes <input type="checkbox"/>
	No <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
promotes effective funding mechanism.	Yes <input type="checkbox"/>
	No <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
fosters effective monitoring and evaluation approaches.	Yes <input type="checkbox"/>
	No <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>

Figure 23 - Language Friend (2) © Per Åge Eriksen

Authors: Kristin Utby Telneset (Cocreating inclusive access to activities)

Cocreating inclusive access to activities	
General information	
Type of good/new practice	Service
Area of action	Strengthen opportunities for social inclusion and activation of children and youth in migrant families
Adopting body	Municipality/ local government in collaboration with local clubs and associations
Level of good/new practice	Local
Location and geographical coverage	Tynset municipality, Nord Østerdal Region
Responsibility for good practice	Tynset Municipality in collaboration with Tynset Sports association and the Regional Council (The Mountain region)
Duration	The project was initiated in March 2018 and is ongoing
Key words	Social inclusion for children and youth, participation through sports, activities, sponsorships
Content of the good/new practice	
Objectives of the good/new practice	To provide more children and youth in migrant households with good and suitable leisure time offerings that are experienced as safe and including. Participation in organized activities is important for feeling of belonging, coping, identity and self esteem and can be important for physical and mental health.
Target group(s)	Children and youth in low-income families
Methodology	Individual tailored information and follow-up of eligible families.
Key facts	The project offers individually tailored information about opportunities to take part in organized activities such as sports and provides support to get familiar with different options. It also provides support to apply for an 'activity card' a service provided by the municipality which gives access to sponsoring of participation in one activity (for instance membership fees).
Background information	The project was initiated in March 2018 and it has led to mobilization of various interconnected initiatives to enhance access to organized activities for children and youth in low income families. It is based in a partnership between regional and local government bodies, the local sports association, the international council,

Achieved results	<p>One of the project's subgoals was to recruit more girls with migrant backgrounds to participate in sports. After four years, there were four times as many girls receiving activity cards as when the project started.</p> <p>The project has contributed to make information about opportunities for activities more accessible, since lack of access to information was identified as hindrance for recruitment of migrant youth and children in activities.</p>
Impacts of the good/new practice	<p>The initiative has potential to strengthen social inclusion among youth and children with migrant backgrounds, and to support good physical and mental health. However, the project is still developing, and systematic evaluations and assessment of impacts has been conducted.</p>
Innovativeness	<p>The project is innovative in the sense that it is based on more active partnerships between a sports association and local and regional government bodies, and it forwards a more individually tailored service provision and follow-up of eligible recipients compared to established practice. Yet, it should still be perceived as an incremental innovation; it is not a radically new way of working with recruitment of children and youth in sports and activities.</p>
Constraints	<p>The project faced setbacks and constraints due to the pandemic, which paused a lot of activities and progress in the project.</p>
Replicability	
Replication conditions and success factors	<p>The project has not yet been fully developed and concretized. Certain guidelines on what the initiative needs to be formalized and made accessible to make replication possibility. The project also rely on the willingness and opportunities of local governments to sponsor activities for children and youth from low income families.</p>
Replicability and/or up-scaling	<p>When the project has been fully developed and described through some key principles and guidelines, this has potential for replication in other municipalities and regions.</p>
Selection of good practice	
Reasons for choosing the good/new practice	<p>Because it was highlighted as a successful and important initiative in one of the case regions, and because previous research on settlement and integration of refugee rural and remote areas in Norway has shown that the enrollment of children and youth in sports and</p>

	<p>activities have a positive effect for social inclusion and integration for the whole family. Getting access to sponsoring of activities can thus be important means for integration. By taking part in organized activities, the whole family get access to networks and friends. The initiative takes this seriously and work systematically and comprehensively with ensuring better access to suitable activities for alle, making it also more likely that the engagement will sustain.</p>
Selection of European good/new practices	<p>This may be relevant as a European good practice because it addresses the well-being of youth and children through activities and recreation which may particularly important for integration and social inclusion in rural and remote areas with more limited access to arenas for socializing compared to more urban settings.</p>
Personal experiences	<p>The local partner has experience with this practice in the sense that it has been developed and implemented in one of the regions and municipalities (Tynset) of the County.</p>
Validation/evaluation external	<p>It has not yet been externally evaluated</p>
Validation/evaluation by project team	<p>It has not been validated or evaluated by the project team in any systematic manner, we have only learned about the project through interviews, and the participatory workshop and through some project documents.</p>
Sources	
Source(s) to the good/new practice	<p>A yearly report has been produced for 2021 which is available in Norwegian at: https://tynsetidrett.spoortz.no/kx/resources/files/NmPWwwlacysq.pdf</p> <p>A project plan is also available from 2020 is also available in Norwegian at: https://www.fjellregionen.no/_aurora/media/c053b64c-6bb8-411b-8797-963a09af77c0?74b618f3-79b5-4813-b560-e0c13ccc2747?74b618f3-79b5-4813-b560-e0c13ccc2747</p>
Date of documentation	<p>Not dated, 2022.</p>

Figure 24 - Cocreating inclusive access to activities © Anne Skjøtskift

Checklist for good/new practice selection

The selected good/new practice ...	
is innovative.	Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> In what way?: New kinds of partnership more tailoring of information and support.
develops creative solutions.	Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> In what way?: Not relevant.
succeeds in achieving its objective(s).	Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> In what way?: It seems to do so, but the results and possible impact has not been systematically documented.
is ethical.	Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/>

	<p>In what way?:</p> <p>Because it supports children and youth in low income families and support their ability to participate.</p>
is fair.	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?:</p> <p>Because it targets children and youth from low-income families regardless of background. It is fair that this group receives support because they are disadvantageous when it comes to participation in activities which often are costly.</p>
Is been proven/evaluated (ideally: has been tested and validated) to work well and produce good results.	<p>Yes <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p>
is replicable.	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?:</p> <p>See descriptions above.</p>
improves migrants' rights.	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?:</p> <p>Yes indirectly because it strengthen opportunities for participation.</p>
is inclusive with regard to people with a migrant background.	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?:</p> <p>Because it is targeting low income families and migrant families that are categorized as low income families in particular.</p>
works with a whole of government approach.	<p>Yes <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?:</p> <p>No, it is based in a partnership between the local government and a sports association.</p>
improves the well-being of migrants	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p>

	<p>In what way?: May strengthen social inclusion and improve physical and mental health.</p>
is gender sensitive.	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?: Targets girls that are under-represented in organized sports.</p>
fosters societal diversity.	<p>Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?: Not relevant.</p>
develops possibilities for a safe and orderly regular migration.	<p>Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p>
fosters preparedness and resilience to migration events/crises.	<p>Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p>
realizes a participatory and/or multi-level governance approach.	<p>Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p>
promotes effective funding mechanism.	<p>Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p>
fosters effective monitoring and evaluation approaches.	<p>Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p>

Authors: Maria Taivalsaari Røhnebæk

Module-based approaches to vocational education	
General information	
Type of good/new practice	Service
Area of action	Education
Adopting body	Central government and selected counties
Level of good/new practice	Regional (County level) and national
Location and geographical coverage	Five counties are taking part in the piloting and testing of the new practice
Responsibility for good practice	Ministry of Education and Research, and Skills Norway which is a unit under The Directorate for Higher Education and Skills.
Duration	The piloting started in 2017 - the project is ongoing
Key words	Vocational training and education, module-based programs, piloting and testing.
Content of the good/new practice	
Objectives of the good/new practice	To develop educational programs for adults that are better suited to the needs and situation of adults. The project is anchored in the White Paper Meld. St.15 (2015-2016) 'Fra utenforskap til ny sjanse – Samordnet innsats for voksnes læring'
Target group(s)	Adults eligible for vocational education and training, and which aims to obtain a trade certificate
Methodology	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Changing the vocational education program to module structured curriculums making it possible to gain documentation of obtained competencies from smaller parts of a more comprehensive educational program. This makes it more feasible to complete the education in a stepwise manner in combination with work practice.
Key facts	The project aims to provide adults with more flexible opportunities to complete a vocational educational program and obtain a trade certificate. The flexibility will be better adjusted to the life situation of adults. The project involves 13 different programs (for instance logistics, sales and service, chef, health care worker and more). The curriculum for the

	<p>different programs has been structured in 4 to 7 modules. Documentation of acquired competencies will be issued by completion of each module.</p>
<p>Background information</p>	<p>The thresholds for labour market inclusion have become increasingly high in Norway, and formal education is largely required to perform various types of work. There are few opportunities for unskilled labour, and workers without formal education have poor opportunities for a long-term labour market inclusion. Thus, the aim of the project is to provide adults with access to education and development of competencies that are in needed in the labour market. Migrants are an important target group, and the project is connected to new priorities in a new Integration Act (from 2020) which places emphasis on education and training as means for integration.</p> <p>https://lovdata.no/dokument/NL/lov/2020-11-06-127</p>
<p>Achieved results</p>	<p>Evaluation and documentation of results take times since the students have to complete the modules and the whole program to assess results, and a certain volume is needed to evaluate results. Still, a quantitative report assessing the progress for the first three years of piloting indicate good results. 448 modules have been completed, and 438 of these passed and only nine participants failed. Still, only 53 percent has been issued with a certificate documenting the competencies acquired from the modules. It is not clear why the schools fail to issue these certificates. 33 of the students that have completed all necessary modules have registered for the exam to obtain a trade certificate. Only one of these failed, while 9 passed and 23 passed with honors. However, the progress differs between the counties enrolled in the pilot, and two counties are responsible for 90 percent of the completed trade certificates. More detailed discussions of results are available in Norwegian in the external evaluation report produced by Ideas2Evidence</p>
<p>Impacts of the good/new practice</p>	<p>There are indications that the program will contribute to strengthen opportunities for adults with migrant background to obtain a vocational training and a trade certificate. This may support more long-term labor market inclusion, and</p>

Innovativeness	Adjustments are made in existing systems for vocational education so the initiative can be perceived as incremental innovation, but it is not radical innovation
Constraints	Difficult to change existing structures in the educational programs throughout the country, and it is resource intensive to change curriculums. Ability to complete the education depend on the life situation of the students and their relation to the labor market. The progress of the program differs across the piloting counties.
Replicability	
Replication conditions and success factors	The project can be replicated to all counties in Norway and this is also the plan of the government. Replication conditions and success factors is being assessed through the ongoing evaluation, but they are not yet clearly identified.
Replicability and/or up-scaling	The program can potentially be replicated to all counties, and the plan is to scale and replicate so that the module structured programs become the way of providing vocational education for adults. Elements or principles of the initiative can be relevant to adopt in other European countries, but whether this is relevant or not depend on how existing systems for vocational education is set up and organized.
Selection of good practice	
Reasons for choosing the good/new practice	The practice can make a significant impact on integration and labor market inclusion by making it more feasible to gain formal education and competencies that are needed in the labor market.
Selection of European good/new practices	Whether this is eligible as a European good practice depends on the situation in the labor market and how the educational system on vocational education is structured and organized.
Personal experiences	Innlandet county (local partner) is one of the piloting counties in this project
Validation/evaluation external	Yes, it is evaluated by external evaluators, (consultancy in collaboration with research institutions) https://www.ideas2evidence.com/publications/deltakere-opplaeringslop-resultater-erfaringer-fra-tre-ar-med-modulstrukturert-fag-og

	<p>Authors of the evaluation report:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Jostein Ryssevik - Malin Dahle - Hanna Jones
Validation/evaluation by project team	The project has not been evaluated through Matilde, only identified and assessed through documents (policy documents, plans, evaluation reports) The relevance of the project has been highlighted in interviews and in roundtables.
Sources	
Source(s) to the good/new practice	<p>https://www.kompetansenorge.no/Norsk-og-samfunnskunnskap/modulforsoket/modulstrukturert-fag-og-yrkesopplaring-mfy/</p> <p>Evaluation report: https://www.ideas2evidence.com/publications/deltakere-opplaeringslop-resultater-erfaringer-fra-tre-ar-med-modulstrukturert-fag-og</p>
Date of documentation	August 2022

Checklist for good/new practice selection

The selected good/new practice ...	
is innovative.	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?: It can be seen as incremental innovation, but not radical. See also comment above.</p>
develops creative solutions.	<p>Yes <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?: Not relevant.</p>
succeeds in achieving its objective(s).	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?: So far it seems to give results as intended but it is too early to asses impact.</p>

is ethical.	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?: Because it is targeting disadvantageous groups in regard to labor market inclusion.</p>
is fair.	<p>Yes <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?: Because the plan is to offer this program to all adults eligible for vocational education throughout the country. It is gradually rolled out and piloted and tested before it is scaling at a national level.</p>
Is been proven/evaluated (ideally: has been tested and validated) to work well and produce good results.	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?: It is being evaluated, but it takes time to assess results in a solid manner and the evaluation is still ongoing.</p>
is replicable.	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?: In Norway yes, but not necessarily in other countries. See comment on this above.</p>
improves migrants' rights.	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?: Yes, indirectly because it enhances opportunities for labor market inclusion and participation more generally.</p>
is inclusive with regard to people with a migrant background.	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?: Yes, adult migrants are in the target group of the initiative.</p>
works with a whole of government approach.	<p>Yes <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p>
improves the well-being of migrants	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?:</p>

	Presumably, since completed education and labor market inclusion is likely to enhance wellbeing.
is gender sensitive.	<p>Yes <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?:</p> <p>Not discussed particularly.</p>
fosters societal diversity.	<p>Yes <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?:</p> <p>Not relevant.</p>
develops possibilities for a safe and orderly regular migration.	<p>Yes <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p>
fosters preparedness and resilience to migration events/crises.	<p>Yes <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p>
realizes a participatory and/or multi-level governance approach.	<p>Yes <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p>
promotes effective funding mechanism.	<p>Yes <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p>
fosters effective monitoring and evaluation approaches.	<p>Yes <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p>

Spain

Authors: Raúl Lardiés Bosque, Nuria del Olmo Vicén and Sergio Larraz (UNIZAR)

The 'Living villages' project, Local Action Group (LAG)	
General information	
Type of good/new practice	Service and Project
Area of action	Transversal, but mainly economy & employment, housing, education, social cohesion, language & culture, safety & stability, mobility, rights & citizenship, rural/regional development
Adopting body	Local Action Groups (LAG) work -called CEDER, so it is paid by LEADER funds and co-financed by the European Feader funds and the Government of Aragón. Also the provincial government (Huesca Provincial Council) help with an aid program for funding the supply of housing for municipalities and villages normally with less than 1,000 inhabitants
Level of good/new practice	Local
Location and geographical coverage	This initiative if developed in 8 out of the 33 comarcas in Aragón
Responsibility for good practice	Local Action Groups (LAG) involved
Duration	From 2016 onwards, and expanding
Key words	The project offers orientation, information and accompaniment on various aspects related to life in small towns, to help potential immigrants to settle in rural areas and small villages
Content of the good/new practice	
Objectives of the good/new practice	This project develops actions to curb depopulation and promote the installation of new settlers in the province of Huesca. It takes place in rural areas where some Local Action Groups (LAG), so it is paid by LEADER funds and co-financed by the European Feader funds and the Government of Aragón. The initiative began in three LAG of the Pyrenees in 2016, and

	<p>has subsequently been extended to other comarcas such as Alto Gállego in 2022 (LAG: Adecuara). The objective is to help to settle population in the area, improving the capacity for attraction, reception and integration: potential settlers are contacted, they are helped to select the territory, housing and employment are sought for them, to develop a professional activity and they are encouraged to participate in social life. For this, the comarcas and municipalities that participate in the initiative organize dynamic workshops and seminars. As one of the functions is to help find housing, the supply of housing is carried out thanks to an aid program from the Huesca Provincial Council: this provincial government offers interest-free loans to municipalities and villages mainly with less than 1,000 inhabitants, to encourage new inhabitants to settle in the province's smallest municipalities and keep the population from shrinking even more</p>
Target group(s)	Potential new immigrants -national or international- who wish to settle in small towns
Methodology	Censuses of available housing have been carried out in the areas covered by the LAGs, which are offered to interested parties through the LAGs and municipalities
Key facts	The project offers orientation, information and accompaniment to potential immigrants on various aspects related to life in small towns (housing, jobs, schools, services, etc.)
Background information	The project was developed due to the lack of existing information on the process of settling in small towns, and due to the lack of information on procedures, available housing or services like schools, jobs, etc.
Achieved results	The experience has been very positively valued by users, and because it collects useful and unknown information for the population that comes from outside a territory
Impacts of the good/new practice	Very positive impact for immigrants who seek practical information to live in towns, since it is information that is hardly available in any other way. Furthermore, with this practice, LAGs systematically gather information that would otherwise be scattered or inaccessible

Innovativeness	Innovative practice because they generate information not available in other ways
Constraints	Risk of not keeping up with time or of not continuing to update this information
Replicability	
Replication conditions and success factors	High replicability, since all LAGs can develop the initiative, or even other Provincial governments
Replicability and/or up-scaling	Economic and human resources are needed to maintain the project/initiative and to keep the information updated, but the project is highly replicable in many other territories
Selection of good practice	
Reasons for choosing the good/new practice	This initiative provides practical information and help not offered by other administrations or organizations
Selection of European good/new practices	This initiative comes from local action groups (LAGs) and not from administrations or civil society, and offers practical information for potential future residents of rural areas
Personal experiences	Not direct experience
Validation/evaluation external	Not externally evaluated
Validation/evaluation by project team	Not externally evaluated
Sources	
Source(s) to the good/new practice	Websites of the initiative and of the LAGs, and of the government of Aragon. Also, news from regional and local newspapers, and blogs. http://www.pueblosvivosaragon.com/ https://pueblosvivosaltogallego724132618.wordpress.com/ https://aragondesarrollorural.es/archivos/10296
Date of documentation	[23/09/2022]

Figure 25 - The 'Living villages' project, Local Action Group (LAG) © Pueblos Vivos Aragon

Checklist for good/new practice selection

The selected good/new practice ...	
is innovative.	Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> In what way?: Innovative practice because they generate information not available in other ways
develops creative solutions.	Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> In what way?: Provides solutions and practical information to the population to settle in rural areas
succeeds in achieving its objective(s).	Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> In what way?: It achieves practical objectives by providing information, tools and support to new settlers who want to settle in rural areas
is ethical.	Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>

	<p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?: It does not generate any conflict; on the contrary, it contributes to helping the population settle and use the territory</p>
is fair.	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?: It is information and help available to the entire population, and contributes to giving opportunities to rural areas</p>
Is been proven/evaluated (ideally: has been tested and validated) to work well and produce good results.	<p>Yes <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?: As a quite new experience, has not been tested and validated, but well valued by users/immigrants, local residents and politicians</p>
is replicable.	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?: Totally, in many other territories and comarcas, or even other parts of the country</p>
improves migrants' rights.	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?: Not only migrant's rights, but for all the population, because it allows the best access to services, education, employment and housing.</p>
is inclusive with regard to people with a migrant background.	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?: (See previous answer). Yes, because it contributes to best access to services, education, employment and housing</p>

<p>works with a whole of government approach.</p>	<p>Yes <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?: No, because it does not correspond to a government initiative, but to rural development and local action groups (LAGs)</p>
<p>improves the well-being of migrants</p>	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?: It improves the well-being of all the population (migrants and natives, being both immigrants arrived)</p>
<p>is gender sensitive.</p>	<p>Yes <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?: Not especially</p>
<p>fosters societal diversity.</p>	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?: It helps to fix any type of population, regardless of its origin and characteristics</p>
<p>develops possibilities for a safe and orderly regular migration.</p>	<p>Yes <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p>
<p>fosters preparedness and resilience to migration events/crises.</p>	<p>Yes <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p>
<p>realizes a participatory and/or multi-level governance approach.</p>	<p>Yes <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?: Not especially, but any citizen and population group can be part of the initiative</p>
<p>promotes effective funding mechanism.</p>	<p>Yes <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?: It does not require high funding, but sustained funding over time in order to maintain the initiative</p>

<p>fosters effective monitoring and evaluation approaches.</p>	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?:</p> <p>Requires monitoring and updating by Local Action Groups (LGAs)</p>
--	--

Authors: Raúl Lardiés Bosque, Nuria del Olmo Vicén and Sergio Larraz (UNIZAR)

The 'comarcas'	
General information	
Type of good/new practice	Policy
Area of action	Economy & employment, housing, education, health, social cohesion, language & culture, safety & stability, mobility, rights & citizenship, rural/regional development social services,
Adopting body	Adopted by a local authority
Level of good/new practice	Local
Location and geographical coverage	Counties (comarcas) and municipalities of all the region of Aragón
Responsibility for good practice	Presidents of the counties (comarcas)
Duration	From 2006
Key words	Planning, Social Services, Inclusion, Social Action
Content of the good/new practice	
Objectives of the good/new practice	Providing services facing to inclusion of population.
Target group(s)	Local population (included foreign immigrants).
Methodology	Transfer and development of competencies from the regional government (Aragón) for planning, management and coordination of activities, to develop them in municipalities.
Key facts	Urban planning, transport, environmental protection, agriculture and livestock, culture, etc. In particular, they develop skills in the field of 'social action.
Background information	Basic services for the population
Achieved results	This 'intermediate' level of the administration has brought many services closer to the citizens, since they are offered by a close administration.
Impacts of the good/new practice	This 'intermediate' level of the administration has brought many services closer to citizens, as they are offered by a close and friendly administration. All this has allowed greater development, particularly in rural areas, and greater territorial cohesion, from which all social groups benefit. In the future, this could lead to a greater settlement of the population in less populated rural areas, although the county seats continue to play a leading role.

Innovativeness	It has allowed the settlement of foreign population in the territory, by providing the population better access to basic services
Constraints	Difficulties of coordination and transfer of powers from the regional government administration, for example related to connectivity (internet development), infrastructures, communication services and housing policies
Replicability	
Replication conditions and success factors	Coordination between the different levels of administration and transfer of economic and management skills
Replicability and/or up-scaling	High. Only some Autonomous Communities in Spain (Catalonia, Aragón...) have developed and implemented comarcas, as a way of bringing public administration services closer to citizens. The experience can be extended, but it depends on political-administrative and investment decisions, since there has to be a transfer of competences from the Autonomous Communities to the comarcas.
Selection of good practice	
Reasons for choosing the good/new practice	It is an example of good practice because: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. It is developed from the Public Administration and brings services and the Administration closer to citizens 2. It has also had satisfactory results since 2006 3. It affects the entire population, mainly settled in rural areas and further away from the administrative centers
Selection of European good/new practices	Because the decentralization of the administration offers greater accessibility of services to the citizen and allows for an increase in settlements in rural and remote areas
Personal experiences	Yes, both of them
Validation/evaluation external	No validation
Validation/evaluation by project team	Through the focus of discussion and round tables we have learned about the satisfaction with it
Sources	
Source(s) to the good/new practice	Website of public administrations: https://www.comarcas.es/

	https://comarcas.aragon.es
Date of documentation	[27/09/2022]

Figure 26 - Regional map of Aragón

<https://www.comarcas.es/index.php/mod.documentos/mem.listado/reCategoria.1507/chk.9029ed77f167e8ed11d2f9e6a3fae2bc.html.%201%20d>

Checklist for good/new practice selection

The selected good/new practice ...	
is innovative.	Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> In what way?: The comarcas have favored the provision of services to the citizens, at the local level; this has allowed the managing and settlement of (foreign) population in the territory, given that its population has better access to basic services
develops creative solutions.	Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> In what way?: For the same reason, the comarcas have favored the access of the rural population to many services in the territory
succeeds in achieving its objective(s).	Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> In what way?: See previous two aspects
is ethical.	Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> In what way?: Not especially ethical
is fair.	Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> In what way?: It is fair, since it offers the same opportunities to the population that resides in rural areas, with respect to the urban
Is been proven/evaluated (ideally: has been tested and validated) to work well and produce good results.	Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> In what way?:

	Not specially tested/evaluated, but the existence of the comarcas has been considered as something very positive for the rural population in the last two decades
is replicable.	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?:</p> <p>Only some Autonomous Communities in Spain (Catalonia, Aragón...) have developed and implemented comarcas. The experience can be extended to other territories, but it depends on political-administrative and investment decisions, since there has to be a transfer of competences from the Autonomous Communities to the comarcas.</p>
improves migrants' rights.	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?:</p> <p>Improving access to services benefits not only immigrants, but the entire population, and allows them to have more dignified living conditions</p>
is inclusive with regard to people with a migrant background.	<p>Yes <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?:</p> <p>Not especially inclusive with regard to people with a migrant background, but with the entire population</p>
works with a whole of government approach.	<p>Yes <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?:</p> <p>It is each autonomous government (of each region) that must promote and establish the development of the counties</p>
improves the well-being of migrants	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?:</p> <p>The comarcas improve the well-being of migrants and the total population by improving access to services</p>

	(accessibility, social, health, education, etc.) and their living conditions
is gender sensitive.	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?:</p> <p>The comarcas and the services offered pay special attention to women and their role in rural areas</p>
fosters societal diversity.	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?:</p> <p>Related to the previous section, the comarcas watch over and defend the principle of universality in the population's access to services, thus promoting diversity</p>
develops possibilities for a safe and orderly regular migration.	<p>Yes <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?:</p> <p>Not especially</p>
fosters preparedness and resilience to migration events/crises.	<p>Yes <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?:</p> <p>Not especially</p>
realizes a participatory and/or multi-level governance approach.	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?:</p> <p>The comarcas are part of the local level of the administration (together with municipalities and provinces), so their operation requires a multi-level governance approach, as well as coordination with the other levels of administration (especially the regional/Community Autonomous).</p>
promotes effective funding mechanism.	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?:</p> <p>The existence of the comarcas requires financing from the Autonomous Community</p>

fosters effective monitoring and evaluation approaches.	Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> In what way?: Not especially
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Authors: Raúl Lardiés Bosque, Nuria del Olmo Vicén and Sergio Larraz (UNIZAR)

Adult Education Centers (CPEPA)	
General information	
Type of good/new practice	Training of people over 18 years of age and for minors with an employment contract
Area of action	Economy & employment, education, social cohesion, language & culture
Adopting body	Adopted by a regional and local authorities: Government of Aragón, the Provincial Provincial Councils (Provincial Governments) and the comarcas (counties)
Level of good/new practice	Regional and local
Location and geographical coverage	Implemented throughout the autonomous community of Aragon
Responsibility for good practice	Comarcas (counties)
Duration	This service began in the 1980s
Key words	Education, training, job inclusion, official degree
Content of the good/new practice	
Objectives of the good/new practice	To obtain an official degree (e.g. 'Certificates of Professionalism'), increase their basic training and promote job inclusion, along with knowledge of language and social relationships
Target group(s)	People over 18 years of age and for minors with an employment contract. They are native population and foreign immigrants
Methodology	Courses
Key facts	Courses are also offered in different villages and towns of the comarcas. The courses usually last one academic year (from October to June)
Background information	Coordination of the different administrative levels
Achieved results	-Training courses, -Learning Spanish for foreigners, -'Certificates of Professionalism' such as those for socio-health care for dependent people in social institutions, workers in bars and restaurants, community mediation, or promotion of free time activities for child and youth education, etc.

Impacts of the good/new practice	Labour integration of people, social cohesion and territorial and economic development
Innovativeness	In addition to allowing better labour integration, it improves the social relations of the foreign population and the feeling of belonging
Constraints	The main difficulty is related to the lack of public transport and/or the need to use private cars to go to the centres. It was solved by extending the network of centers to more municipalities. The main challenge is to get women from Arab countries to attend language classes and training courses
Replicability	
Replication conditions and success factors	Available centers, public transport and dissemination tasks to publicize the service
Replicability and/or up-scaling	High
Selection of good practice	
Reasons for choosing the good/new practice	Because all stakeholders mention knowledge of the language and training for job placement as a basic aspect for integration
Selection of European good/new practices	Because they are needs common to the entire territory in order to integrate its immigrant population, particularly unskilled workers
Personal experiences	Yes, both of them
Validation/evaluation external	Not externally evaluated
Validation/evaluation by project team	Through the focus of discussion and round tables we have learned about the satisfaction with it
Sources	
Source(s) to the good/new practice	Department of Education, Government of Aragón: https://epa.educa.aragon.es/educapermanente/ https://educa.aragon.es/centros-epa#centros https://sites.google.com/view/cpepa-alto-gallego/ofertativa/certificados-de-profesionalidad https://cpepamonegros.catedu.es/
Date of documentation	[28/09/2022]

Figure 27 - Adult Education Centers (CPEPA) © Sergio Larraz

Checklist for good/new practice selection

The selected good/new practice ...	
is innovative.	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?:</p> <p>Innovative practice because it allows a large population outside the usual educational channels to receive training and education, as a way to integrate into society</p>
develops creative solutions.	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?:</p> <p>This practice generates solutions so that a large population with learning problems, foreigners, or vulnerable, can receive training</p>

<p>succeeds in achieving its objective(s).</p>	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?:</p> <p>In general, although there are no objective data in this regard</p>
<p>is ethical.</p>	<p>Yes <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?:</p> <p>It is an initiative that promotes learning, training, integration, the development of people, good behavior and coexistence</p>
<p>is fair.</p>	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?:</p> <p>In addition to the above, this initiative promotes justice among the population, especially with the most vulnerable and needy (e.g., immigrants)</p>
<p>Is been proven/evaluated (ideally: has been tested and validated) to work well and produce good results.</p>	<p>Yes <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?:</p> <p>Not formally tested/evaluated</p>
<p>is replicable.</p>	<p>Yes <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?:</p> <p>It is applicable in any territory, developing the same network of adult education centers</p>
<p>improves migrants' rights.</p>	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?:</p> <p>This experience contributes to improve migrants' rights, because many of the students are immigrants with difficulties to access the regular educational system. However, this service is offered to the entire population that needs it</p>

<p>is inclusive with regard to people with a migrant background.</p>	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?:</p> <p>It is inclusive with regard to people with a migrant background, because it favors their training, integration, and the search for a job, or improve it</p>
<p>works with a whole of government approach.</p>	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?:</p> <p>These centers are co-financed by the regional government (of Aragón) and the counties, in Aragón</p>
<p>improves the well-being of migrants</p>	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?:</p> <p>These centers contribute to improving the well-being of migrants (and the population in general), to the extent that they offer qualifications and training, and improve the chances of having a better job</p>
<p>is gender sensitive.</p>	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?:</p> <p>These centers are equally open to men and women, but there are more female students, and above all of foreign origin, since their access to the labor market is more complicate</p>
<p>fosters societal diversity.</p>	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?:</p> <p>These centers are open to train/educate the entire population, but students of foreign origin and the less favored (more vulnerable) are the usual students. Therefore, it is a tool that favors diversity and integration</p>
<p>develops possibilities for a safe and orderly regular migration.</p>	<p>Yes <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?:</p>

	Not especially
fosters preparedness and resilience to migration events/crises.	<p>Yes <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?:</p> <p>Not especially</p>
realizes a participatory and/or multi-level governance approach.	<p>Yes <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?:</p> <p>Not especially</p>
promotes effective funding mechanism.	<p>Yes <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?:</p> <p>These centers receive funding on a regular basis from the regional government (Aragón) and from the counties</p>
fosters effective monitoring and evaluation approaches.	<p>Yes <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?:</p> <p>No specific evaluation, although the teachers of these centers, the students, and society, value them very positively and with good results</p>

Sweden

Authors: Sheyma Sheikhnour, Nana Heinberg, Åsa Norrman (Region Dalarna)

Dalaidrotten	
General information	
Type of good/new practice	Working method and strategy
Area of action	Health and social cohesion
Adopting body	NGO
Level of good/new practice	Regional
Location and geographical coverage	Dalarna County
Responsibility for good practice	RF-SISU Dalarna
Duration	Ongoing
Key words	Including sports. Seize opportunities and remove obstacles
Content of the good/new practice	
Objectives of the good/new practice	An increased number of people want and are able to do sports together throughout life.
Target group(s)	Children, young people and adults regardless of background. Asylum seekers as well as newcomers and Swedish-born.
Methodology	Five development plans, where the one we focus on in this example is “inclusive sports for everyone”. Sports movement should be an actor in the establishment of newcomers.
Key facts	Dalaidrotten (Dala sports) work with norm conscious sport which means to be aware of what norms that affect us and how we deal with it. They highlight and make visible prevailing privileges and restrictions for practitioners and leaders. They work very active with leadership, resource allocation and representation that minimizes inequality.
Background information	Since 2015, the sports movement has worked to develop and offer activities and basic introduction to association life for newcomers. Sports movement should be an actor in the establishment of newcomers in the Swedish society. Physical activity and the association as a place, provide opportunities

	for health, community, commitment, personal growth and democracy.
Achieved results	The project has contributed to increased understanding and knowledge among associations (board and leaders). Several account-free activities for children, e.g. skiing, soccer school for foreign-born girls, “Health for all”. Newly arrived adults get the opportunity for physical activity and knowledge about the Swedish sports movement and club life. Within the project, meeting places have been created. Speed dating. Young leaders from other cultures have been recruited, which facilitates the recruitment of foreign-born participants. However, it is still a challenge to get foreign born women to engage in a leading role.
Impacts of the good/new practice	The girls in the soccer school get in touch with adults other than their family. In some cases, this has given the girls insight that they are living in an oppressed situation and they have been able to seek help from the social services in the municipality.
Innovativeness	“Soccer for girls” in disadvantaged areas. In Borlänge, is a project to increase the number of girls with a foreign background in the sports movement. Today, approx. 100 girls is active in the project. In direct connection at the end of the school day, training starts. Only girls can participate and only women are leaders. The project provides for shoes, ball and leg protection. After one year, one half of the participants are members of a local association or club. Through this way of working, a relationship and trust is created for the parents, this benefits the girls in all parts of life in Sweden.
Constraints	It is a challenge to get parents of foreign born girls to realize that the sports movement is a safe place. Finances are a challenge. Many families are unable to pay training fees when the girls move on to other clubs.
Replicability	
Replication conditions and success factors	Diversity and representation of different cultures are important in all parts of the sports movement, from the board

	and management to leaders and parents' associations. Knowledge of norm awareness is also of great importance.
Replicability and/or up-scaling	The association gains trust from parents. Sponsors from business and more members, which makes the business even more visible, and more and more young people want and can participate.
Selection of good practice	
Reasons for choosing the good/new practice	The Swedish sports movement is a large organization. Reaching new target groups is a challenge. Getting those born abroad to be physically active is an investment for public health in Sweden.
Selection of European good/new practices	Physical health of the population also increases mental health. Association life is an excellent forum for integration. People come together around an interest despite age and ethnicity.
Personal experiences	The local partner has followed the project over time, but not participated in the actual implementation.
Validation/evaluation external	The national sports association has published several reports on the integration work. Both on a local and national perspective.
Validation/evaluation by project team	The project group has read the reports mentioned above.
Sources	
Source(s) to the good/new practice	Report and case study.
Date of documentation	05.09.2022

Figure 28 - Dalaidrotten © RF-SISU Dalarna

Authors: Birgitta Hägg, Åsa Norrman, Nana Heinberg (Region Dalarna)

Who are we?	
General information	
Type of good/new practice	Project
Area of action	Social cohesion
Adopting body	Local authority, municipality
Level of good/new practice	Regional and local
Location and geographical coverage	Avesta and Orsa municipalities, Sweden
Responsibility for good practice	Avesta municipality
Duration	March 2018 until March 2021
Key words	Inclusive and sustainable working life, increase the cohesion of society
Content of the good/new practice	
Objectives of the good/new practice	Inclusive workplaces with good cohesion. Well-functioning working groups where we exchange each other's differences and see similarities by collaborating based on competence, interest and needs.
Target group(s)	The project has involved all municipal employees in the municipality of Avesta and in the municipality of Orsa. That means just over 2700 employees. The participants were from widely different professional fields such as health care staff, school staff, the technical unit and the dietary unit, as well as administrative staff.
Methodology	A deliberative conversation method has been used in the project. That means open and permissive calls where different arguments are given space and different points of view may be discussed. The goal is to be able to function together with our differences.
Key facts	An educational material consisting of five one-hour films. In the films, facts are interspersed with questions based on five themes with the aim to evoke discussions and reflection. How do I think? Who am I?
Background information	Many newcomers have come to Avesta municipality from many parts of the world. The municipality has invested a lot of resources in helping them in various ways, and staff has done

	<p>and is doing a great job in this. New people mean a new situation. This project wants to meet the questions; How can we create a climate where everyone's voices are heard? How can we deal with our differences? How can we have an inclusive community?</p>
<p>Achieved results</p>	<p>This project has involved all municipal employees in Avesta municipality and in the partner municipality Orsa. It means that more than 2 700 employees have received training in issues related to integration och inclusion, with a focus on the joint conversation. The project has been much appreciated, especially because the participants had the opportunity to talk about issues that are rarely given space for. Examples from participants: "Think more about how I say things and how I treat others and I am not as quick to jump to conclusions." "It creates reflection. Not only from a societal perspective, but also from an individual perspective. What do I do? How to act? What can I think of?" "There have been very good conversations at the film meetings. Previously, Swedes and immigrants socialized differently, now it is more mixed. Previously. I think it depends on the project."</p>
<p>Impacts of the good/new practice</p>	<p>The project has created better conditions for inclusion in the workplace, which affects social cohesion in a positive way. Inclusive workplaces find it easier to recruit people who are far from the labour market, as these people get jobs, they no longer need financial support from the municipality. The project has led to increased collaboration regionally through both Avesta and Orsa working with Who Are We?</p>
<p>Innovativeness</p>	<p>The project has shown a new way of working with integration issues as both Swedish-born and immigrants have been involved and jointly discussed inclusion issues. For many, the idea that integration also concerns indigenous people has been new. The project has opened the eyes to the fact that Swedish-born people also need to be involved in the integration process. This way of working has also attracted attention regionally and influenced the way they view their integration work. Involving Swedish born</p>

	<p>people in the conversation around integration reduces the fear of employing foreign-born, the target group "people who are far from the labor market" has thereby gained improved opportunities to be included in working life.</p>
Constraints	<p>Those people who had a negative attitude towards integration issues were initially hesitant and questioned the usefulness of the project. But when the project meetings started, most people changed their attitude.</p> <p>The films were described as interesting and the conversations gave the opportunity to ask the questions that no one had dared to raise before. But there are still people who have maintained their negative attitude, which is a challenge.</p>
Replicability	
Replication conditions and success factors	<p>Before the project starts, a local needs inventory should be made in order to be able to adapt the effort to the local conditions. It is important to anchor the project in the organization's management team. Sufficient time also needs to be allocated for the operation and there should be mandatory participation. There also needs to be project staff who can train the conversation leaders and support them during the project. The project has contributed to an increased understanding of the world around us, an increased knowledge of what it means to be a migrant and an increased understanding of why we think the way we do. The tools that were in the project have supported a better climate for discussion and increased cohesion.</p>
Replicability and/or up-scaling	<p>According to the external evaluator, it has a quality that allows it to be used in other municipalities and at a national level. There are good opportunities to expand the new way of working, both geographically and in new contexts. This has already happened when both Falun and Borlänge municipality use the training material in their activities. The education can be used anywhere and is available on the internet. Avesta municipality also have another project in the pipeline aimed at entrepreneurs. Even there, the material will</p>

	<p>be used to create better conditions for hiring and including foreign born people in the labor market.</p>
<p>Selection of good practice</p>	
<p>Reasons for choosing the good/new practice</p>	<p>This project is unique in our region as it focuses on the actual meeting between people with different backgrounds and values. It is also unique as the project involves such a large number of municipal employees as 2 700 people.</p>
<p>Selection of European good/new practices</p>	<p>For the same reason as above.</p>
<p>Personal experiences</p>	<p>The local partner has followed the project over time, but not participated in the actual implementation.</p>
<p>Validation/evaluation external</p>	<p>Throughout the project period, an external evaluator, VETA Advisor AB, followed the project. Their conclusions are that the subject is based on real needs. They also write that many of the participants have gained knowledge, understanding and increased insight into – for them and for the organization – important issues. The material produced in the project has been perceived as a great asset by staff and managers. It has been a great advantage that all staff have been able to access and be able to use the same material. In this way, the project has created a common platform for dialogue. A summary assessment of the interview and survey responses shows that the project engages many employees and managers. A large number of comments show that the project has touched and even led to changes. It may be that the issues are now raised at workplace meetings and in employee conversations. The participants feel that the municipalities have given a clear signal that a change should take place and that the issues are important. The evaluation from the VETA advisor is available from Avesta municipality.</p>
<p>Validation/evaluation by project team</p>	<p>The researchers and local part in Dalarna agree that this is a good practice because it is unique in our region through its extent and the number of people involved.</p>

Sources	
Source(s) to the good/new practice	Case study.
Date of documentation	05.09.2022

Figure 29 - Who are we? © Avesta kommun

Authors: Malin Hedlund, Åsa Norrman, Nana Heinberg (Region Dalarna)

Sätters carpentry	
General information	
Type of good/new practice	Carpentry service
Area of action	Economy & employment
Adopting body	Private actor
Level of good/new practice	Local and regional
Location and geographical coverage	Hedemora municipality and the region of Dalarna
Responsibility for good practice	Sätters snickerifabrik (Sätters carpentry)
Duration	Ongoing
Key words	Taking advantage of newcomers' expertise in a professional way.
Content of the good/new practice	
Objectives of the good/new practice	To take advantage of newcomers' expertise in a professional area with a shortage of staff.
Target group(s)	Newcomers with skills and expertise that is needed in the company. The target group is cabinetmakers and painters who are already trained. They must have basic education or experience from their home country. So far only men aged 35-55 years have been in the target group, but it is open for anyone. Most live nearby or in neighboring areas.
Methodology	To see migrants as a resource that is needed in a profession that has a shortage of staff. The company helps with language training and education. They also validates the migrant's skills on site at the workplace. If a person does not pass the validation, they are not allowed to continue working.
Key facts	Sätters carpentry works with inclusion of migrants with the aim of improving the company's operations. Instead of seeing obstacles in hiring migrants, they try to find solutions to any problems that may occur. They make the same demands on everyone and also give everyone the same opportunities. In this way, everyone in the company experiences greater participation.

Background information	The shortage of staff with expertise and skills that are needed in the company has led Sätters carpentry to find new target groups to recruit and new ways to introduce and educate new staff. Some of the recruitments have taken place via recommendations from others, and some through the usual application process.
Achieved results	Increased turnover is the clearest result. It is possible to continue developing the company and take larger orders. The migrants get a job, can support themselves and become part of society. They feel pride and gain more status.
Impacts of the good/new practice	The company is a door opener for other companies to dare to hire foreign-born people. They started this work in 2014 and during that time they have removed some barriers and given more people the chance to work. The CEO of Sätters carpentry has taken an active role in spreading information about their working methods around the county. The migrants in the area stay when they become employed.
Innovativeness	There is a great interest at the company in teaching the employees Swedish. They have arranged their own language training as well as their own validation. Those who do not meet the requirements are denied employment. The company is very active in spreading information and tries to influence other companies in the same direction.
Constraints	Jokes and slang can be difficult to understand. As nuances in language can be a challenge. At work we solve most things, but in social contexts it can become an obstacle and create a certain alienation.
Replicability	
Replication conditions and success factors	It is important to make the same demands on all employees. The company receives financial support, for a period of time, to hire foreign-born people. Everyone in the company knows about this and understand that the grant provides the opportunity to include language training in working hours and also support for new employees to get used to work routines and language.

Replicability and/or up-scaling	Sätters carpentry has grown in turnover and scope thanks to this example. This best practice can be spread to other companies through the CEO's commitment and interest in participating in different contexts.
Selection of good practice	
Reasons for choosing the good/new practice	The company acts in an active and innovative way to help themselves as a company to grow as well as to help migrants into work. It is a win-win situation. The CEO of Sätters carpentry takes an active part in spreading information about this good practice.
Selection of European good/new practices	For the same reason as above.
Personal experiences	The local partner team have met and heard the CEO talk about the company and the way they work during various occasions. The CEO has also been involved in the action research in the Matilde-project.
Validation/evaluation external	No evaluation has been done.
Validation/evaluation by project team	The researchers and the local team have selected this to be a good practice from the business sector in our region, mainly due to the CEO's commitment.
Sources	
Source(s) to the good/new practice	Case study.
Date of documentation	05.09.2022

Figure 30 - Sätters carpentry © Malin Hedlund

Turkey

Authors: Fatma Yilmaz-Elmas and Ayhan Kaya (BILGI)

Improving access of Rural Refugees to Health and Protection Services in Turkey (Health to Rural, Support to Rural)	
General information	
Type of good/new practice	Project
Area of action	Health and protection
Adopting body	Financed by The Directorate-General for European Civil Protection and Humanitarian Aid Operations (ECHO)
Level of good/new practice	National
Location and geographical coverage	Five provinces in Turkey: Bursa (the Matilde region), Adana, İzmir, Mersin and Şanlıurfa
Responsibility for good practice	United Nations Population Fund (UNFPA) in Turkey in cooperation with the Republic of Turkey Ministry of Health
Duration	18 months (January 2019 – April 2021)
Key words	health, protection, refugees, rural, mobile services
Content of the good/new practice	
Objectives of the good/new practice	<p>The project basically aims to provide emergency response to the health needs of the residents and refugees living in the rural areas of five provinces of Turkey, through mobile service units.</p> <p>Its objectives are:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ensuring that rural residents and migrants are in a state of complete physical, mental and social well-being; • Increasing their access to basic health and protection services, making these services more accessible to everyone and increasing the demand for these services through “Health to Rural and Support to Rural” service units.
Target group(s)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Primary beneficiaries: rural migrants, including seasonal agricultural migrant workers and their families; local

	<p>seasonal agricultural workers and their families working in the same areas;</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Secondary beneficiaries: Ministry of Health (central and provincial levels), local seasonal agricultural workers working in the same regions and their families;
Methodology	<p>Within the scope of the project, orientation and capacity building trainings were first given to the field personnel on the provision of primary health care and protection services in rural areas. The orientation meeting took place in November 2019 in Istanbul. A total of 83 field personnel completed their training, which was also attended by observers from the Ministry of Health. The field personnel includes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 12 Health to Rural and Support to Rural service units, each of them composing of doctor, midwife/nurse, social service worker, interpreter and driver. • 6 referral/transfer vehicles composing of a driver and health mediators.
Key facts	<p>“Health to Rural, Support to Rural” project aims to improve access of rural refugees to health and protection services. Mobile service units reached thousands of seasonal agricultural workers and migrants who live in the tent settlements in rural areas as well as local seasonal agricultural workers.</p>
Background information	<p>Hundreds of thousands of seasonal agricultural workers and migrants live in the tent settlements, in rural areas. Life conditions to both live and work are difficult for all, women, men, youth, elderly and children. They have limited access to health and protection services. COVID-19 has made things even more difficult. In such conditions, mobile service teams that can reach to remote villages has vital importance to touch the lives of those who live in rural.</p>
Achieved results	<p>Since the beginning of the project, in five provinces those benefited from the services in total are:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 106,857 people from “Health to Rural, Support to Rural” services; • 64,579 people from healthcare services (the project target was 50,000);

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 55,053 people from protection services (the target was 40,000); <p>In addition, 405 people composing of service providers, public personnel and health managers were supported in seasonal agricultural work and migrant health issues (project target: 500).</p> <p>Awareness raising and information sharing in health (40,048 people) and protection (38,133 people) issues are among the achieved results during the project.</p> <p>During the COVID-19 pandemic process:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • COVID-19 scanning, filiation and nasal swab testing services were provided to 50,611 people. • 39,456 people participated in COVID-19 prevention activities (Covid-19 and Hygiene training, brochure and soap distribution). <p>In addition, right after the earthquake in the city of İzmir occurred during the Pandemic in October 2020, needs assessment was carried out for the victims.</p> <p>Anecdotal evidence points to the satisfaction of the target groups. Several beneficiaries, in different interviews, indicate the valuable help by the mobile health service providers and health mediators in terms of a broad range of primary services from obtaining ID cards, delivering patients to the hospital, identifying psychological problems of migrant children and guiding them to informing about the pandemic measures.</p> <p>The MATILDE field research in Bursa also reveals how valuable reaching a prescription written by the doctor in the mobile service team, especially for the seasonal agricultural migrant workers having no access to the city hospitals in harvesting seasons.</p>
<p>Impacts of the good/new practice</p>	<p>Rural migrants, including seasonal agricultural migrant workers and their families, are the ones who do not easily access to the primary healthcare services. To overcome the legal and practical barriers for those working and seasonally residing away from their residents they have registered, the role of mobile service providers makes huge contribution in gatekeeping access to different types of services for seasonal and even irregular migrants. Making healthcare services more</p>

	<p>accessible to rural workers and residents is of importance not only in terms of personal physical well-being but also in terms of a complete social well-being and rural development. Considering dependence on the migrant labor force in rural areas due to the shrinking local population, healthy working environment is vital for a sustainable development in rural. The Project, in this sense, means a lot for the beneficiaries. Especially the services provided for the vulnerable groups in the field is specifically worth to be mentioned. The field personnel divided their follow-ups into groups such as 15-19 aged-women follow-up, pregnant follow-up, child follow-up, pre-school, after school and infant follow-ups. The teams followed up their vaccinations, and if necessary, they supported the District Health Directorates in their implementation in rural. They made referrals or transfers to the related institutions.</p> <p>MATILDE field observations also reveal that healthcare services seem to be the most important field to be socially engaged with immigrants in the district where the locals and immigrants do not normally interact to a great extent. Seasonal immigrants in the agriculture sector particularly rely on the mobile health services to meet their primary healthcare needs. This makes healthcare personnel a facilitator in confidence-building between immigrants residing and working in the district and any other actors willing to reach out to them.</p>
<p>Innovativeness</p>	<p>The Project improves the livelihood of the target groups in a way that the services are provided regardless of any ID card and status for either residents or the migrants. There is no legal and/or official restriction and barrier in front of providing primary healthcare service. Embracing a rights-based approach and considering access to healthcare as a human right, the mobile health units reach any person in need just by being informed or hearing about the case.</p>
<p>Constraints</p>	<p>The main challenge encountered in implementation was the first touch and people's hesitation in the first place. The first impression seems hard to overcome and it is hard to break people's perception, especially in the sensitive subjects such</p>

	<p>as family planning due to the cultural differences and perceptions. The migrant-background health mediators and other personnel in service units played considerable importance to facilitate the communication and overcome any misunderstanding.</p> <p>The second challenge is to supply enough medicines and materials from the mobile medical vehicle. Also, the environmental conditions in tent settlements do not help a lot for a proper medical process, e.g. pollution causing infectious diseases. People could have higher expectations about their life conditions from medical personnel more than they can do. The failure of the solving problems in this context causes people to mislead their reactions to the health personnel they reach. To overcome this challenge, the team tried to reach the relevant institutions and informed the local situation, problem and needs.</p> <p>Another important challenge is to come up against the local reactions while providing services to the migrant seasonal workers. The locals and immigrants in rural areas as well do not interact to a great extent and live as two separate groups. For the seasonal agricultural workers, the lack of communication is the same. The Turkish workers and the migrant-background ones often live separately in different tent settlement areas. They may also sometimes be in a race in terms of access to health services. In particular, they may react by having the misperception that the migrant agricultural workers, especially the Syrians, are being prioritized. The fair treatment in practice was the main way to overcome such perceptions in time.</p>
<p>Replicability</p>	
<p>Replication conditions and success factors</p>	<p>The project helped the Ministry of Health to create an infrastructure in Bursa (the Matilde region), Adana, İzmir, Mersin and Şanlıurfa to reach out to the migrants in rural and urban spaces.</p>
<p>Replicability and/or up-scaling</p>	<p>The Project ended on 30 April 2021. At the end of the Project, the model (service tools, equipment, service providers,</p>

	developed materials and training modules) has already been transferred to the Ministry of Health.
Selection of good practice	
Reasons for choosing the good/new practice	Embracing a rights-based approach, the project contributed to an accessibility of health care services for rural migrants.
Selection of European good/new practices	It is a project directly implementing in rural areas, the focus of the MATILDE. A specific assessment on health services provided to rural migrants would be useful for mapping a multidimensional approach.
Personal experiences	The MATILDE research team conducted a focus group meeting with the field officers of the project.
Validation/evaluation external	Like all the other EU funded projects, this project was also reviewed by external reviewers.
Validation/evaluation by project team	MATILDE research team and local team observed the field (Karacabey) that the project successfully reached out to the migrants and refugees in need of health services.
Sources	
Source(s) to the good/new practice	MATILDE field research, focus group meeting in 12 March 2021 with UNFPA “Health to Rural, Support to Rural” field officers (composed of 2 nurses, 5 health mediators and 1 social service worker); Website (https://turkiye.unfpa.org/en/video/health-rural-support-rural); primary documents, presentations provided by the UNFPA Humanitarian Aid Program in March 2022.
Date of documentation	29/08/2022

Figure 31 - Improving access of Rural Refugees to Health and Protection Services in Turkey (Health to Rural, Support to Rural) © UNFPA Turkey

Checklist for good/new practice selection

The selected good/new practice ...	
is innovative.	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?:</p> <p>Considering the nature of seasonal agricultural labor, mobile health services are quite necessary and innovative. In addition, the provided services go beyond the primary healthcare; it also provides guidance and raises awareness in rural.</p>
develops creative solutions.	<p>Yes <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?:</p> <p>The project reached out to the migrants and refugees in rural spaces that are often not easily accessed by the public officers.</p>
succeeds in achieving its objective(s).	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?:</p>

	<p>At the end of the project, thousands of people were reached much more than the targeted ones. More than 65 thousand people were reached in terms of healthcare services, while the target of the project was 50 thousand. In addition, the protection services were provided more than 55 thousand people whereas the target was 40 thousand.</p>
<p>is ethical.</p>	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?:</p> <p>Project team has been very much aware of the ethical concerns that apply to the vulnerable groups and individuals.</p>
<p>is fair.</p>	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?:</p> <p>The Project team aims to reach people who cannot access health services in any way and to do their medical screening in rural areas. In the field, the health personnel treat everybody equally, there is no such discrimination according to nationalities, age or gender.</p>
<p>Is been proven/evaluated (ideally: has been tested and validated) to work well and produce good results.</p>	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?:</p> <p>The Project was conducted for 18 months between January 2019 and April 2021.</p>
<p>is replicable.</p>	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?:</p> <p>As far as a sustainable and sufficient fund is allocated for the mobile health units, the project is applicable. The project has already been handed over the Ministry of Health to be re-implemented.</p>
<p>improves migrants' rights.</p>	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?:</p> <p>The Project provides and improves access to rights to healthcare and protection services. Especially considering the migrants under Temporary Protection Status in Turkey,</p>

	regardless of the location where they are registered, it provides them a channel to reach primary healthcare.
is inclusive with regard to people with a migrant background.	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?:</p> <p>The primary beneficiaries are rural migrants, including seasonal agricultural migrant workers and their families.</p>
works with a whole of government approach.	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?:</p> <p>The project is implemented and coordinated under the auspices of the Turkish state actors.</p>
improves the well-being of migrants	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ensuring that rural residents and migrants are in a state of complete physical, mental and social well-being; • Increasing their access to basic health and protection services, making these services more accessible to everyone and increasing the demand for these services.
is gender sensitive.	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?:</p> <p>The Project prioritizes vulnerable groups, primarily the women in rural areas. There are specific follow-ups in implementation and information sharing activities for specific women groups, considering for example their age or their situation such as pregnancy.</p>
fosters societal diversity.	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?:</p> <p>The project helps the interaction between migrants and project team members with Turkish citizenship who act as mediators inbetween.</p>
develops possibilities for a safe and orderly regular migration.	<p>Yes <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p>

<p>fosters preparedness and resilience to migration events/crises.</p>	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?:</p> <p>The project helps migrants and refugees resolve their health problems so that they could generate resilience in everyday life.</p>
<p>realizes a participatory and/or multi-level governance approach.</p>	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?:</p> <p>The Project embraces a participatory and multi-level approach through a provincial level coordination. The implementation is realized by the coordination of Provincial Health Directorates, Provincial Public Health Directorates, seasonal agricultural workers coordinators and UNFPA field officers.</p>
<p>promotes effective funding mechanism.</p>	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?:</p> <p>The project benefits from international funding.</p>
<p>fosters effective monitoring and evaluation approaches.</p>	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?:</p> <p>The project team keeps individual data of the recipients according to the individual data privacy regulations.</p>

Authors: Fatma Yılmaz-Elmas and Ayhan Kaya (BILGI)

Improving the Health Status of the Syrian Population under Temporary Protection and Related Services Provided by Turkish Authorities (SIHHAT)	
General information	
Type of good/new practice	Project
Area of action	Health
Adopting body	Governmental adopted by the Ministry of Health (MoH), financed under the EU Facility for Refugees in Turkey (FRIT)
Level of good/new practice	National
Location and geographical coverage	29 provinces in Turkey: Adana, Adiyaman, Ankara, Batman, Burdur, Bursa, Denizli, Diyarbakir, Elazığ, Gaziantep, Hatay, İstanbul , İzmir, K.Maraş, Kayseri, Kilis, Kocaeli, Konya, Malatya, Manisa, Mardin, Mersin, Muğla, Nevşehir, Osmaniye, Sakarya, Samsun, Şanlıurfa, Isparta
Responsibility for good practice	Ministry of Health (MoH)
Duration	SIHHAT I: 49 months (01/12/2016-31/01/2021) SIHHAT-II (the follow-on programme from its predecessor - SIHHAT I): February 2021 - until mid-2025 latest.
Key words	health, Syrians, availability and access, Migrant Health Center (MHC)
Content of the good/new practice	
Objectives of the good/new practice	<p>SIHHAT Project has an overall objective improving the health status of the targeted group, i.e., Syrians under Temporary Protection (SuTP) in Turkey, by supporting and improving primary and secondary healthcare services provided by the MoH.</p> <p>Specific objectives are:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. To ensure availability and accessibility to healthcare services in 29 targeted provinces with the highest proportion of Syrian population. 2. To ensure increase in demand to healthcare services by Syrian population.

Target group(s)	The Syrian population under temporary protection (SuTP) and healthcare staff in direct contact with refugees in Turkey.
Methodology	<p>The tools that has been used to implement the good practice and to reach the goals are: direct financial funding for paying salaries; providing equipment; training and employment; conducting campaigns.</p> <p>The overall objective of improving the health status of the targeted group has been measured by self-reported health status and access status, prevalence/risk of communicable and noncommunicable diseases.</p> <p>The intended outcome of increasing the availability and accessibility of health care services has been measured by, for example population per health care professional; numbers of consultations/treatments delivered; vitamin/mineral deficiency rates; vaccination coverage; geographic coverage of services.</p> <p>The other intended outcome that is to increase demand for health care services has also been measured by, for example, total visits by Syrians to health care facilities and patient satisfaction with services.</p>
Key facts	<p>The SIHHAT project includes a number of components. It provides:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • support to Migrant Health Centers (MHCs), Extended MHCs and Community Mental Health Centers (CMHCs) by paying salaries, providing equipment and meeting running costs, including rent; • mobile primary health care services targeting rural and hard-to-reach Syrians (including agricultural workers) and mobile cancer screening; • training and employment of Bilingual Patient Guides (BPGs) in both primary and secondary facilities; • vaccination and vitamin D/iron supplements for children and women of childbearing age; • reproductive health equipment; • medical equipment for secondary health care facilities in focus provinces; • training of health care staff delivering services to Syrian patients;

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • a visibility campaign, aiming to improve health literacy in the Syrian population; • ambulances for emergency services.
Background information	<p>Following the outbreak of civil war in Syria, a great number of people have been displaced and forced to flee their country. Since then, more than 3.5 million people have sought protection in Turkey, which made Turkey the country hosting the largest number of Syrian refugees. At first stage, since the stay of Syrians was assumed as a temporary situation, the issue was handled in terms of an emergency. The first Syrians that came to Turkey were settled in tent camps. Only those who stayed in the refugee camps benefited from health services between April 2011 and January 2013. In parallel to the intense and rapid growth in numbers, and with the increase of those living outside the camps, the need to make new arrangements arose. Syrians' access to the health services was first expanded to those locating in the eleven provinces bordering Syria, and then in the final stage, broadened to cover all 81 provinces in Turkey. Since then, all Syrians who are registered in Turkey holding a temporary identification number are able to benefit from the same level of emergency, preventive and curative health services as Turkish citizens.</p> <p>Hosting the largest number of Syrians requires huge efforts to provide them with humanitarian aid and development support. In such an awareness, the EU is committed to assisting Turkey in dealing with this challenge. The EU Facility for Refugees in Turkey (FRIT) is the answer to the EU Member States' call for additional funding to support refugees Turkey. EU assistance aims at supporting refugees, in particular those living outside of camps and in vulnerable situations, while supporting also the host communities in providing access to quality education, health, protection and livelihoods, as well as other local services. In this sense, SIHHAT Project was launched within the scope of FRIT's financial aid for humanitarian and development actions.</p>
Achieved results	The achieved results, shortly, are:

The scope of healthcare services was extended in 29 provinces densely populated by the Syrian population, the capacity and quality of service provision were enhanced and access to services was increased. More specifically, 181 Immigrant Health Centers and 10 Community Mental Health Centers were opened in 29 provinces where immigrants live intensively; and nearly 4,000 health workers have been employed in these centers.

The [mid-term evaluation report](#), covering the years of action 2016-2020, stated that the Turkish health system is sufficiently equipped to provide quality health care to refugees and host communities in focus provinces. This entails ensuring **availability** of equipment, availability of health workers with sufficient training, and availability of health facilities and mobile clinics. Refugee health needs are high because they are exacerbated by social determinants such as poverty, high fertility, early marriage and lack of education. Therefore, a **comprehensive approach** to refugee health would consist of both reducing those determinants as well as providing relevant services to meet the needs.

Regarding the overall services in health, the evaluation report also concluded that the health response within the Facility through SIHHAT project was relevant to the target population's identified health needs, as confirmed by refugee satisfaction levels (e.g. with MHCs), although satisfaction levels have decreased between 2018 and 2020.

The SIHHAT project has contributed to an increased **accessibility** of health care services. The funding has helped with increasing accessibility of health care services in terms of providing **physical access, financial affordability** and **culturally acceptable** services.

More importantly, the Project offers **employment opportunities to immigrants**. Within the scope of the Project, MoH have employed Immigrant-originated health personnel and other support staff. As an anecdotal evaluation, a government official noted in [the evaluation report](#), „SIHHAT provided the first strong legal environment for their [Syrian health workers] employment. We know NGOs employed some of them before, when there was a sudden influx of

	<p>refugees in 2012 and 2013. Many NGOs employed staff but because of legislative constraints in Turkey, to best of my knowledge, they could not have brought a doctor as a doctor, but they were allowed to help with medical services. This was a bit understandable under emergency conditions, but some regularisation was needed later and the SIHHAT project provided some very formal, safe, legal basis“</p> <p>Likewise, in our MATILDE field research, a 35-year-old female nurse with Syrian origin expressed her enthusiasm and happiness to be working in the Karacabey MHC: “I was a dialysis nurse in Syria. I graduated from the University in 2009. [Bashar] Asad prevented in those days us from receiving our diplomas as the regime was concerned that we would leave the country and go somewhere else to work. When I came here with my family, I had my graduation document, and I was able to apply for the SIHHAT Project. We were then in Gaziantep. I was chosen to work in the Project. First, we had two months training in Ankara, and then I had my internship in Sakarya [a city near Bursa in the North]. Then I was posted to Bursa, and I am stationed in Karacabey for the last two years (...) Otherwise I don’t know what to do if the Project ends. I guess I will have to work in an underpaid job” (Interview WP5TRB006).</p>
<p>Impacts of the good/new practice</p>	<p>The Project has made a considerable contribution to the overall access to and availability of health care services, through its support in training and provision of health care workers, and health care facilities, particularly in primary health care. Considering the fact that the Syrian refugees have been forced to migrate, and most have suffered extreme trauma and impoverishment due to the civil war, they are extremely vulnerable, and face significant challenges, including the language barrier, as they struggle to rebuild their lives and meet their many needs with minimal resources in a foreign country. In such an environment, refugee health needs are also exacerbated by social determinants such as poverty, high fertility, early marriage and lack of education. Therefore, the SIHHAT field activities, especially in provision of physical access the healthcare services and promotion of health literacy, make great sense for the targeted groups.</p>

	<p>Integration of Syrians is critical for social cohesion and this requires a long-term vision as well as increased capacity for services (including health services). Community and family support are in place, as well as addressing social cohesion. However, there are still there are inevitable social tensions between host and refugee populations. Nevertheless, provision of interpretation services in primary and secondary health care (through the staff consisting of interpreters, psychologists, social workers, outreach workers) are of great importance for the Syrian beneficiaries to be involved in daily life. Our MATILDE field research reveals that immigrants particularly rely on the MHCs and mobile health services to meet their primary healthcare needs. This makes healthcare personnel be a facilitator in confidence building between immigrants residing and working in the district and any other actors willing to reach out them. This is the case especially in rural areas where the locals and seasonal immigrant agricultural workers do not interact so much.</p>
<p>Innovativeness</p>	<p>First, the SIHHAT Project is the most comprehensive and largest collaborative effort under the largest EU-funded health project in Turkey in terms of migrant health provision. Besides, bilingual patient guides (BPG), some of whom have been trained through the World Health Organisation (WHO) action, are employed by SIHHAT. By September 2020, 1,128 BPGs had been hired and were working at both primary and secondary facilities, primarily, but not exclusively, in SIHHAT focus provinces. The evaluation report names this intervention as the most significant attempt at directly improving the acceptability of the Turkish health care system for refugees (primarily Syrians).</p> <p>The importance of accessing health care in one's own language is also evident from the follow-up interviews through which it is indicated that Syrian refugees may be inclined to seek care from an informal Syrian physician rather than through other available services. This makes the services given in the MHCs a great role. Because as long as services are available free, are in close proximity, and are provided in Arabic, this reduces the use of informal Syrian physicians.</p>

	<p>Measures to make health care accessible to hard-to-reach groups are of great contribution for rural migrants in accessing healthcare services. The SIHHAT component covering mobile health services aims to improve the accessibility of health care for rural-based Syrian refugees and harder-to-reach groups.</p>
<p>Constraints</p>	<p>There has been considerable progress in increasing access to healthcare of the targeted groups and in increasing availability of healthcare services, especially considering during the first phase of the Project (SIHHAT I). However, requirement of further efforts are also being emphasized in the evaluation reports. In short, the need signifies the ongoing barriers to access for Syrian refugees generally, including transportation, language and cultural barriers, and awareness of health care services.</p> <p>Limited quantitative disaggregated data is available for non-Syrians or unregistered Syrians.</p> <p>The other significant challenge in terms of access relates to the registration status of Syrians. Syrians who reside outside of their province of registration have limited access to health care services in accordance with Turkish law. There are also challenges that are specific to the non-Syrians or unregistered groups. For example, without a ‘refugee ID’ card, unregistered Syrians have limited access to health care services except emergency services and vaccines. Non-Syrian refugees (those under international protection) face legal barriers, to health care access, based on insurance and subsequent affordability rather than location of residence. These issues, although outside of the direct implementation of the Project, are critical and will need to be addressed to overcome the challenges in front of accessing healthcare.</p> <p>The challenge of social cohesion is important as it relates to health care and refugees. The Project also operates in a context within which there are inevitable social tensions between host and refugee populations. Misinformation on the available services and rights and misinformation on the budget that is spent all increase social tension.</p>

	Language barrier is still a challenge in terms of hiring Syrian health care workers at MHCs to provide services that are culturally and linguistically friendly.
Replicability	
Replication conditions and success factors	This is a very successfully implemented project with a large geographical focus. This requires a very well functioning collaboration between national and international institutions.
Replicability and/or up-scaling	SIHHAT Project is now continuing in its second phase, and the Migrant Health Centres generated within the framework of the project are connected with the national health system.
Selection of good practice	
Reasons for choosing the good/new practice	Turkey is now standing since 2015 in the first places with the highest number of refugees in the world. With a population of around 4 million refugees, health services become essential. Matilde research team has also witnessed the key role of the health personnel in the Migrant Health Centres in connecting the migrants and refugees with the majority society.
Selection of European good/new practices	This project shows how instrumental the international assistance can become to improve the living conditions of migrants and refugees in a country that is too much under pressure because of the high number of refugees.
Personal experiences	The MATILDE research team paid a field visit to Karacabey MHC.
Validation/evaluation external	EU Monitoring reports, external reviews, and evaluation surveys
Validation/evaluation by project team	Local stakeholders
Sources	
Source(s) to the good/new practice	Official website, monitoring reports, evaluation reports and survey reports as well as MATILDE field research outcomes and testimonies from the field visit to Karacabey MHC: The official website, https://eng.sihhatproject.org/ European Commission, <i>The Facility Results Framework Monitoring Report No.8</i> , The Facility for Refugees in Turkey, November 2021. EU Delegation to Turkey:

	<p>https://www.avrupa.info.tr/en/project/improving-health-status-syrian-population-under-temporary-protection-and-related-services</p> <p>European Commission, <i>Strategic Mid-term Evaluation of the Facility for Refugees in Turkey 2016-2019/2020</i>, Final Report</p> <p>Volume II: Sector Report on Health, June 2021.</p> <p>Peker, A. <i>Final Report: Surveys for Health Care Needs Analysis of Syrian Population under Temporary Protection</i>, Ministry of Health Directorate General of Public Health, June 2020.</p>
Date of documentation	16/08/2022

Figure 32 - Improving the Health Status of the Syrian Population under Temporary Protection and Related Services
Provided by Turkish Authorities (SIHHAT) © Anadolu Agency

Checklist for good/new practice selection

The selected good/new practice ...	
is innovative.	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?:</p> <p>The SIHHAT project innovative in a sense that it includes a number of components, including offering employment</p>

	opportunities for migrants and accessing health care in one's own language.
develops creative solutions.	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?:</p> <p>Offering bilingual patient guides (BPG), and measures to make health care accessible to hard-to-reach groups are those among creative solutions to overcome some very important challenges.</p>
succeeds in achieving its objective(s).	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?:</p> <p>There has been considerable progress in increasing access to healthcare of the targeted groups and in increasing availability of healthcare services. Still, requirement of further efforts to overcome the ongoing barriers (e.g. transportation, language and cultural ones) are also being emphasized in the evaluation reports.</p>
is ethical.	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?:</p> <p>EU ethical rules and norms are followed in the project.</p>
is fair.	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?:</p> <p>Regarding the overall services in health, the health response through SIHHAT project was relevant to the identified health needs of the target population, i.e. Syrians. Although there are challenges specific to the non-Syrians or unregistered groups, these issues, are outside of the direct implementation of the Project. Still, they are critical and will need to be addressed to overcome the challenges in front of accessing healthcare for other migrant groups.</p>
Is been proven/evaluated (ideally: has been tested and validated) to work well and produce good results.	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?:</p>

	The Project has been implemented under the monitoring and evaluation of the EU Commission.
is replicable.	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?:</p> <p>The Project has already been its second phase.</p>
improves migrants' rights.	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?:</p> <p>It ensures availability and accessibility to healthcare services.</p>
is inclusive with regard to people with a migrant background.	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?:</p> <p>The Project targets directly ensuring healthcare services for Syrian population under the Temporary Protection Status in Turkey.</p>
works with a whole of government approach.	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?:</p> <p>The project has been implemented in accordance with the legal regulations in cooperation with the Ministry of Health.</p>
improves the well-being of migrants	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?:</p> <p>The Project has been designed to improve the health status of the migrants, mainly Syrians. This very much relates to physical and psychological well-being of refugees and immigrants.</p>
is gender sensitive.	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?:</p> <p>Specific targeting of women, children, and vulnerable groups:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The SIHHAT vitamin supplement, vaccination and reproductive health interventions specifically focused on the needs of children and women of reproductive age.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sexual and reproductive health services: maternal health services; family planning counselling and commodities; counselling on women's health issues; provision of information, education and communication materials, and identifying most vulnerable cases. • psychosocial support, counselling, awareness raising and outreach. <p>According to the SIHHAT post-survey, in 2020, women were more likely to access any health care organisation (81.5%) than men (66.6%)²⁰³ and women also have higher percentages applying to MHCs.</p>
fosters societal diversity.	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?:</p> <p>It provides refugees with health services and the health personnel bridges between refugees and local dwellers.</p>
develops possibilities for a safe and orderly regular migration.	<p>Yes <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p>
fosters preparedness and resilience to migration events/crises.	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?:</p> <p>It provides health services.</p>
realizes a participatory and/or multi-level governance approach.	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?:</p> <p>Migrant Health Centres are helping refugees have access to other services as well since they are the first station for many refugees to have access to everyday life in Turkey.</p>
promotes effective funding mechanism.	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?:</p> <p>A very successful collaboration between the Turkish Ministry of Health and the European Commission.</p>
fosters effective monitoring and evaluation approaches.	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?:</p> <p>Individuals' health data are stored to follow up better.</p>

Authors: Fatma Yilmaz-Elmas and Ayhan Kaya (BILGI)

Bursa Cohabitation Support Program	
General information	
Type of good/new practice	A program for supporting refugees' integration to local economy and supporting cohabitation has been launched by Bursa Metropolitan Municipality within the scope of the project titled Resilience in Local Governance (RESLOG)
Area of action	Social cohesion
Adopting body	Public adopted by Bursa Metropolitan Municipality
Level of good/new practice	Regional (Bursa Metropolitan Region)
Location and geographical coverage	The province of Bursa in Turkey
Responsibility for good practice	Implemented by Bursa Metropolitan Municipality; Launched by Resilience in Local Governance (RESLOG) Project which is carried out by the Swedish Local Authorities and Regions Association (SALAR), through its affiliate SKL- International. Programme partners include the Bursa branch of the Presidency of Migration Management, Bursa directorates of ministries of Education and Health, district municipalities and NGOs.
Duration	January 2021- December 2023
Key words	social cohesion, cohabitation, training, capacity building
Content of the good/new practice	
Objectives of the good/new practice	<p>The program aims;</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - to develop the life skills of the immigrants who come to the city for various reasons, to develop and support their living environment together with the local people; - to develop the professional capacity of municipal employees working with immigrants on migration and immigration issues; - to ensure the sustainability of this cooperation by developing the cooperation of local institutions and non-governmental organizations.
Target group(s)	Refugees, particularly young woman and child Syrians, who are observed to experience integration and adaptation problems more on the basis of gender, and who came with an

	<p>intense and sudden migration, were determined as the priority target group. Indigenous young women and children living in the same region were included in the courses in the target group.</p>
<p>Methodology</p>	<p>The Program aims to strengthen the integration of foreign origin individuals and of those coming from other provinces for various reasons. The Metropolitan Municipality prepared a migration master plan of Bursa together with other stakeholders. A road map was determined with the participation of several institutions and relevant non-governmental organizations. A cooperation protocol about living together in Bursa was prepared for the institutionalization of the process. The protocol welcomes the migrants and refugees and offers venues of social cohesion for both natives and migrant-origin individuals. To that end, various kinds of training modules for capacity building such as computational skills, Turkish language, gastronomy, and others are delivered to all the residents including migrants and refugees in the Vocational Training Course Centre (BUSMEK). In the preparation of the Protocol, our PI, Prof. Dr. Ayhan Kaya, also contributed with his feedback.</p>
<p>Key facts</p>	<p>The Program aims to facilitate the adaptation of immigrants to urban life. It includes language and vocational courses, guidance for social support and employment, and cohabitation activities.</p>
<p>Background information</p>	<p>Bursa is a city renowned as city of sanctuary for many centuries. Currently, Bursa hosts more than 175.000 Syrian refugees along with a large number of economic immigrants from all over the world. Especially with the Syrian influx, the need to coordinate migration management at the local level became urgent. Bursa Metropolitan Municipality took the initiative to harmonize the work of various public and civil society organizations in the field of migration with the “Cohabitation Support Program”.</p>
<p>Achieved results</p>	<p>The following results have been achieved:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - An inter-institutional cooperation protocol was signed for the implementation of Bursa Coexistence Support Program

	<p>- Consisting of 30 modules and training videos, Bursa Coexistence Support Program in-house personnel capacity building training program was realized. (see http://www.reslogproject.org/egitimler)</p> <p>- Three computer classrooms were established (with 36 computers and hardware) under the roof of Vocational Training Course Center (BUSMEK). New generation software support was received.</p>
Impacts of the good/new practice	<p>It has been seen that the project has a positive effect on target groups. It is understood from the number of participation in language and vocational courses, which is higher than expected and continuously increases. It has been observed that project activities support mutual recognition of cultures and creation of opportunities for recognition of Bursa as a common living space. Since this good/new practice is new, its effects on economic development, rural/regional development and regional transformation have not been measured yet.</p>
Innovativeness	<p>The most important innovation brought by the good/new practice to migration and integration issues and regional development is that key public institutions and non-governmental organizations related to migration in the city have come together to form the "Bursa Cohabitation Support Program" and has prepared a joint cooperation protocol in order to implement this program and ensure its sustainability. In addition, it can be seen as an innovation that the migration and immigration training modules created in the institutional capacity building module within the program are disseminated on the online platform.</p>
Constraints	<p>The continuation of the Syrian crisis; the ambiguity of the temporary protection status, which does not allow Syrians to settle permanently in Turkey and the fact that the environment for the safe return of immigrants to Syria has not been fully formed still affects Turkey as well as other countries. This uncertainty affects the implementation of the program as the immigrants do not feel their stay in Turkey secured and local people also perceive immigrants as</p>

	temporary. Besides, bureaucratic processes within the municipality take longer than expected.
Replicability	
Replication conditions and success factors	<p>The Bursa Cohabitation Program is designed for the city of Bursa, considering its local social dynamics and inter-institutional networks. However, the general framework consisting of language and vocational trainings and social events for cohabitation can be adopted with minor changes by other migration receiving cities in Turkey.</p> <p>A careful stakeholder analysis is key in adaptation of this program in other cities.</p> <p>The success of the program also depends on the existence of structures that will monitor and improve the implementation of the program at least one time each period, and by conducting impact analysis.</p>
Replicability and/or up-scaling	<p>Once it is completed it will be setting up the framework of social cohesion that the Metropolitan Municipality will follow. It can also be implemented by other provinces and municipalities, as it is a flexible program that can be developed continuously and can be shaped according to local resources.</p>
Selection of good practice	
Reasons for choosing the good/new practice	This is the first of its kind in the Turkish Municipal Administration system.
Selection of European good/new practices	This is the metropolitan municipality that also includes MATILDE locality, Karacabey.
Personal experiences	The PI, Prof Ayhan Kaya, helped the Municipality in the process of writing the social cohesion protocol.
Validation/evaluation external	The validation is made by the members of the local council that is composed of the members of different political parties in the city.
Validation/evaluation by project team	MATILDE research team has been closely working with the persons in Social Services Directorate of the Bursa Metropolitan Municipality.
Sources	

Source(s) to the good/new practice	Bursa Metropolitan Municipality, Smart Urbanism and Innovation Department, R&D Directorate; documents and information provided by the RESLOG project team; internet sources
Date of documentation	29/08/2022

Figure 33 - Bursa Cohabitation Support Program © Bursa Metropolitan Municipality

Checklist for good/new practice selection

The selected good/new practice ...	
is innovative.	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?:</p> <p>It is the first of its kind in Turkey.</p>
develops creative solutions.	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?:</p> <p>The protocol sets the tone and motives of social cohesion of migrants and local residents.</p>
succeeds in achieving its objective(s).	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?:</p> <p>The program was successful in realizing its objectives, as it was created with participatory methods and planned in a flexible structure.</p>

	It will set a precedence for the other municipalities in Turkey.
is ethical.	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?:</p> <p>It pays attention to ethical concerns. The program and protocol have been prepared and carried out in accordance with universal human rights, gender equality, national and international laws and institutional regulations.</p>
is fair.	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?:</p> <p>It follows the logic of fellow citizenship that is explained in Article 13 of the Municipality Law in Turkey. This principle is based on the idea of providing equal services to every dweller of the city irrespective of citizenship.</p>
Is been proven/evaluated (ideally: has been tested and validated) to work well and produce good results.	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?:</p> <p>The members of the city council as well as the relevant migrant NGOS are taking part in the preparation of the protocol.</p>
is replicable.	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?:</p> <p>Having a framed program and the existence of a cooperation protocol will ensure its reproducibility.</p>
improves migrants' rights.	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?:</p> <p>It enables immigrants to benefit from all the opportunities offered by the city, facilitates access to these opportunities and improves the adaptation capacity of immigrants.</p>
is inclusive with regard to people with a migrant background.	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?:</p> <p>It covers all domestic and foreign immigrants who come to the city and prefer to settle.</p>

<p>works with a whole of government approach.</p>	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?:</p> <p>It is a municipal work that includes all the members of parties represented in the city council. The program and protocol are prepared and implemented with a holistic approach in accordance with the legal regulations in cooperation with key public institutions and non-governmental organizations related to migration.</p>
<p>improves the well-being of migrants</p>	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?:</p> <p>It supports immigrants to develop their social, professional and economic capacities by developing coexistence environments and integrating with local people.</p>
<p>is gender sensitive.</p>	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?:</p> <p>Gender related issues are also addressed in the protocol.</p>
<p>fosters societal diversity.</p>	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?:</p> <p>It is a social cohesion protocol which acknowledged diversity by default.</p>
<p>develops possibilities for a safe and orderly regular migration.</p>	<p>Yes <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p>
<p>fosters preparedness and resilience to migration events/crises.</p>	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?:</p> <p>The program was implemented with the support of the RESLOG project, which aims to increase the resilience of local governments in the face of rapid and intense migration. For this reason, it directly aims to increase the resilience of both the municipality and the other partners of the city against the migration events/crises.</p>

<p>realizes a participatory and/or multi-level governance approach.</p>	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?:</p> <p>The program was created together with the Municipality, RESLOG experts and key stakeholders, taking into account the opinions of immigrants. The protocol created for the execution of the program also includes a participatory and/or multi-level governance approach.</p>
<p>promotes effective funding mechanism.</p>	<p>Yes <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p>
<p>fosters effective monitoring and evaluation approaches.</p>	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?:</p> <p>The protocol involves the members of different political parties represented in the city council in monitoring the social cohesion related acts, policies and practices of the municipality.</p>

United Kingdom, Scotland

Authors: Michele Bianchi and Maria Luisa Caputo (UNIPR)

Rural Visa Pilot	
General information	
Type of good/new practice	Policy Pilot elaborated by the Scottish Expert Advisory Group on Migration and Population
Area of action	Migration; Labour force shortage; Demographic challenges; Regional development;
Adopting body	British Government (Home Office)
Level of good/new practice	Regional: Scotland
Location and geographical coverage	Scottish rural local authorities
Responsibility for good practice	Home Office; Scottish Government; Scottish Local Authorities; Economic actors
Duration	Under elaboration
Key words	Regional Visa; Regional Development; Shortage Occupation List; Demographic challenges
Content of the good/new practice	
Objectives of the good/new practice	<p>This pilot aims to grant regional (Scottish) visas to migrants with the demographic profile and the professional skills that would best contribute to sustaining local communities and the economy in rural Scotland. It proposes different solutions to design a place-based migration policy:</p> <p>(a) Expanding the Shortage Occupation List and considering labour shortages at the local scale. In this sense, a migrant will need to fill a job position that will be in a shortage occupation and a designated area (non-tradable).</p>

	<p>(b) Introducing a Scottish Visa targeted at specific areas. This would require the Scottish Government and local authorities to prioritize the weighting of different features (e.g. age, family/dependents, language skills, and ties to the region, occupation or skills) as part of a points-based system.</p> <p>(c) Remote and rural partnership scheme (modelled on the Canadian Atlantic Pilot scheme). Migrants would need a specific job offer from an employer in a designated area. Local authorities, employers and public services would identify which types of areas and employers would benefit most from the scheme and would be engaged in delivering an integration plan.</p>
Target group(s)	Economic migrants.
Methodology	Expert Advisory Group on Migration and Population designed this pilot analysing existing regional Visa schemes and collaborating with local authorities and the Scottish Government.
Key facts	The pilot is currently kept on hold by the Central Government. A less ambitious pilot aimed at allowing 300 Visa was published at the end of September 2022 by the Scottish Government.
Background information	The depopulation and ageing trends in Scottish rural areas have been witnessed for decades.
Achieved results	The pilot is still a proposal.
Impacts of the good/new practice	Potentially, the pilot will allow migrants to have a facilitated migration path to rural Scotland and for the hosting communities to invert the de-population and ageing process, and address the local labour shortage.
Innovativeness	It would allow changing the migration system from a UK-based to a place-based one, designed to respond to the needs of rural and remote migrant communities. It would allow granting visas and managing migration flows to rural areas specifically.
Constraints	The Scottish Government cannot implement this policy, as Migration is a reserved matter of the Central Government. This represents a major theme of political power devolution.
Replicability	

Replication conditions and success factors	The scheme is based on other similar schemes in Canada and Australia, so it is itself a replication. The principle is fully replicable based on the central government's willingness to allow a regional visa approach.
Replicability and/or up-scaling	The scheme is replicable in countries that face similar challenges: regions with very low population density and whose rural and remote communities face demographic challenges and labour shortages.
Selection of good practice	
Reasons for choosing the good/new practice	The innovation in the policy framework for migration to rural areas.
Selection of European good/new practices	It contributes to the political debate on solutions for rural population challenges and labour shortage.
Personal experiences	We discussed with the experts that proposed the pilot as well as with stakeholders in rural communities facing the challenges of an ageing population and workforce shortage.
Validation/evaluation external	Not Known
Validation/evaluation by project team	Not possible at the moment.
Sources	
Source(s) to the good/new practice	https://www.gov.scot/publications/designing-pilot-remote-rural-migration-scheme-scotland-analysis-policy-options/documents/
Date of documentation	27/09/22

Figure 34 - Rural Visa Pilot © Maria-Luisa Caputo

Checklist for good/new practice selection

The selected good/new practice ...	
is innovative.	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?:</p> <p>This is a new policy approach that can allow Scotland to manage its own way to attract newcomers according to necessities and to direct these flows toward rural areas.</p>
develops creative solutions.	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?:</p> <p>It experiments with the possibility to connect have regional shortage occupations list and related visas to specific places.</p>
succeeds in achieving its objective(s).	<p>Yes <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?:</p> <p>Still under elaboration.</p>
is ethical.	<p>Yes <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?:</p> <p>It does not target any particular ethical topic.</p>
is fair.	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?:</p> <p>It allows better conditions for migration to Scotland.</p>
Is been proven/evaluated (ideally: has been tested and validated) to work well and produce good results.	<p>Yes <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?:</p> <p>Still under elaboration.</p>
is replicable.	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?:</p> <p>The scheme is based on other similar schemes in Canada and Australia, so it is itself a replication. The principle is fully</p>

	replicable based on the central government's willingness to allow a regional visa approach.
improves migrants' rights.	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?:</p> <p>It implements the possibility to migrate to Scotland under fairer conditions compared to the current system.</p>
is inclusive with regard to people with a migrant background.	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?:</p> <p>It is a migration policy.</p>
works with a whole of government approach.	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?:</p> <p>It is a government-based action.</p>
improves the well-being of migrants	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?:</p> <p>Allows them to have recognition of their skills and to match proper job positions.</p>
is gender sensitive.	<p>Yes <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p>
fosters societal diversity.	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?:</p> <p>It aims to have more people in rural areas.</p>
develops possibilities for a safe and orderly regular migration.	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?:</p> <p>Check on working and accommodation conditions for migrants.</p>
fosters preparedness and resilience to migration events/crises.	<p>Yes <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p>
realizes a participatory and/or multi-level governance approach.	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p>

	<p>In what way?:</p> <p>Work in partnership among regional government, local authorities and economic players.</p>
<p>promotes effective funding mechanism.</p>	<p>Yes <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p>
<p>fosters effective monitoring and evaluation approaches.</p>	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?:</p> <p>They might consider this a valuable option.</p>

Authors: Michele Bianchi and Maria Luisa Caputo (UNIPR)

Syrian Vulnerable Persons Resettlement Program	
General information	
Type of good/new practice	Syrian Vulnerable Persons Resettlement Program
Area of action	Human Protection, Rights and Citizenship, Housing, Education, Health
Adopting body	Home Office UK, Scottish Government, COSLA (Coordinator) and all the 32 Scottish Local Authorities
Level of good/new practice	Regional: Scotland
Location and geographical coverage	32 Scottish Local Authorities
Responsibility for good practice	Scottish Government; COSLA (Convention of Scottish Local Authorities); Local Authorities
Duration	2015 - 2020
Key words	Refugees; Resettlement; Integration; Social inclusion; Rural areas
Content of the good/new practice	
Objectives of the good/new practice	This program supported refugees from Syrian since 2015. After the grant of a UK visa, the main goals are the provision of social security, accommodation, education, and health services to help them in their resettlement in Scotland. The outcome is the settlement of this refugee population also in rural areas and the creation of specialized services for refugees and more generally for the migrant population in those areas.
Target group(s)	Syrian Refugees, particularly those people identified as highly vulnerable (e.g. for health conditions)
Methodology	The UK Home Office delegates the responsibility for the program to the Scottish Government, COSLA and the Scottish Local Authorities. The first part of the process is to assess the needs (e.g. health needs) and aspirations of the refugees to relocate them. Secondly, it accompanies refugee families in their settlement (access to social rented houses), and in their access to public funds and services (GP registration, school enrollment, etc.). Thirdly, it supports integration by supporting refugees' language learning (ESOL) and employability.

	Furthermore, this program was framed by the New Scots policy, an integration policy that oriented the actions at the national and local levels.
Key facts	From 2015 to 2020, over 3.000 Syrians arrived and settled in Scotland through this program (20.000 in the UK).
Background information	In front of the tragedy of the war in Syria and the pressing demands to welcome thousands of refugees, the UK and Scottish Governments have elaborated this program to welcome the most vulnerable people. Furthermore, the program allocates resources to regional bodies to coordinate these efforts among central governments, local authorities and civil society.
Achieved results	The program helped over 3000 people to settle in Scotland providing them with houses, services and long-term life perspectives. The success of this program is in the share of families who decided to remain in the rural and remote Scottish local authorities. The limits are in the number of refugees that are still 'depending' on the program for their everyday life and in the low share of economic integration in some areas (this needs to be weighted with the specificity of this population - e.g. important health conditions, trauma, etc.).
Impacts of the good/new practice	Syrian refugees can settle not only in urban areas but successfully also in rural areas with support and assistance
Innovativeness	For the first time forced migrants were resettled to Scottish rural areas; before asylum seekers and refugees were concentrated only in the Central Belt of Scotland
Constraints	The program lasts five years. Therefore, the support for the refugee families ends after this time. As well, the know-how developed by the local authorities and the people employed in the program can be lost.
Replicability	
Replication conditions and success factors	The main framework condition to allow replicability is the political will to carry out a program like this one. It requires consistent investments, initiatives and cooperation by the decision-makers at the national, regional and local scale.

	It also needs a clear integration policy framework (like the New Scots Strategy) to orient the policies and the actions at all levels.
Replicability and/or up-scaling	<p>This program is currently reproduced in the Afghan Locally Employed Staff Relocation Scheme and Afghan Citizens Resettlement Scheme, yet this population is very different from the former (e.g. education, urban/rural, migration path, aspirations) and this highly impacts the replicability of the program.</p> <p>It is possible to consider the replicability of this program in other regions. The necessary step is to involve a regional organization able to coordinate the efforts between the central government and the local authorities. The program requires a high amount of funding.</p>
Selection of good practice	
Reasons for choosing the good/new practice	Tangible good results in refugees' settlement and good indications about the process to coordinate resources and efforts to create local units for this task. Development of know-how and integration strategies in rural and remote local authorities.
Selection of European good/new practices	This can represent a valid example of the intertwining of a program for refugees resettlement and an initiative to re-populate rural areas.
Personal experiences	Yes, COSLA is our local partner for the MATILDE project, the researcher on the field met some organizations involved in the local project and a representative from the Scottish Refugees Council participated in the Case Study Working Group.
Validation/evaluation external	Not known
Validation/evaluation by project team	We interviewed the coordinators of the project, local teams and refugees (WP3; WP5); we participated in a SVPRS team meeting in a local authority.
Sources	
Source(s) to the good/new practice	https://www.migrationscotland.org.uk/our-priorities/current-work/syrian-refugee-resettlement
Date of documentation	27/09/22

Figure 35 - Syrian Vulnerable Persons Resettlement Program © Maria-Luisa Caputo

Checklist for good/new practice selection

The selected good/new practice ...	
is innovative.	Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> In what way?: For the first time forced migrants were resettled to Scottish rural areas - before asylum seekers and refugees were concentrated only in the Central Belt of Scotland.
develops creative solutions.	Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
succeeds in achieving its objective(s).	Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> In what way?: 3000 people passed through the program and many of them settled in Scotland.
is ethical.	Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/>

	<p>In what way?:</p> <p>It provides support to people who run away from war contexts.</p>
is fair.	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?:</p> <p>It allows whoever asks for protection (and receives the status of "refugees") to settle in Scotland.</p>
Is been proven/evaluated (ideally: has been tested and validated) to work well and produce good results.	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?:</p> <p>Feedback from officials on the field.</p>
is replicable.	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?:</p> <p>Indeed, it has been the basis to develop the strategy for the Afghani and Ukrainian refugees strategy.</p>
improves migrants' rights.	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?:</p> <p>It makes more accessible resources and services.</p>
is inclusive with regard to people with a migrant background.	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?:</p> <p>It is a refugee settlement program.</p>
works with a whole of government approach.	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?:</p> <p>Coordination among the diverse levels.</p>
improves the well-being of migrants	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?:</p> <p>It supports them in accessing those basic resources and services that determine social security.</p>
is gender sensitive.	<p>Yes <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p>

<p>fosters societal diversity.</p>	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?: It favours connections between refugees and locals.</p>
<p>develops possibilities for a safe and orderly regular migration.</p>	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?: It enhances the process of settlement and integration.</p>
<p>fosters preparedness and resilience to migration events/crises.</p>	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?: It generates know-how and expertise for officials which have lately been used for the Afghani and Ukrainian refugee crises.</p>
<p>realizes a participatory and/or multi-level governance approach.</p>	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?: Coordination between regional and local levels.</p>
<p>promotes effective funding mechanism.</p>	<p>Yes <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p>
<p>fosters effective monitoring and evaluation approaches.</p>	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?: Field report from officials.</p>

Author: Michele Bianchi (UNIPR)

New Scots strategy	
General information	
Type of good/new practice	Policy
Area of action	Integration, settlement, regional development
Adopting body	Scottish Government
Level of good/new practice	Regional
Location and geographical coverage	Scotland
Responsibility for good practice	Scottish Government, Local Authorities, third sector
Duration	2014/17 - 2018/22
Key words	Integration;
Content of the good/new practice	
Objectives of the good/new practice	This strategy aims to coordinate the efforts of both local authorities and third sector organizations involved in the facilitation of refugees' integration. This strategy main aim is to help people in the areas of employment, education, housing, health, communities and social connections.
Target group(s)	Refugees.
Methodology	It is a holistic approach to addressing those issues that affect the process of settlement and integration. The Scottish Government provides the necessary funds from the equity budget and the local third sector organizations run the activities in collaboration with communities and local authorities. This is a consequence of the 2016 development of power from the Central Government. The 2014 - 2017 plan was useful to create networks between public and third sectors to develop local initiatives. The 2018 - 2022 plan aims to implement these results and continue the work.
Key facts	The intertwining of this strategy with local policies has developed a range of initiatives that reach out to newcomers and with potential occasions to connect with the hosting communities.
Background information	New Scot Strategy helps to address the needs of these vulnerable people and to favour their integration into the Scottish socio-economic context. Therefore, we can consider

	<p>this as a good practice because the government has decided to re-invest in this assessing the outcomes as positive. The strategy invests resources in the creation of networks that connect people's needs with responses in the hosting communities through the organizational flexibility of the third sector.</p>
Achieved results	<p>Better and more holistic approach in support refugees' integration and settlement. New collaborations with the third sector. Change in the public authorities' communication with increased use of migrants' languages</p>
Impacts of the good/new practice	<p>The strategy has facilitated the mutual integration between newcomers and the hosting community "breaking" the monoculture of certain places and putting in contact locals with other cultures. Moreover, the contamination has created a more welcoming environment in which refugees can feel safe and secure.</p>
Innovativeness	<p>Before the 2016 devolution of political power, the Scottish Government could not implement such kind of strategy. This has been an important step toward the development of a Scottish approach to dealing with refugees' settlements. The main innovation has been the addressing of a necessity to generate collaboration between the public and third sector to implement local initiatives.</p>
Constraints	<p>This strategy strictly depends on public funds; therefore, it needs a political choice to be implemented. From the fieldwork, findings do not highlight any particular results in terms of local development.</p>
Replicability	
Replication conditions and success factors	<p>The main framework condition to replicate this strategy is the political will of the government and the availability of resources to invest in this direction.</p>
Replicability and/or up-scaling	<p>There are concrete possibilities to replicate this strategy in other contexts considering the presence of third sector organizations all over Europe and their important role in rural areas.</p>
Selection of good practice	

Reasons for choosing the good/new practice	This strategy plan allows knowing more in deep the plans adopted by the Scottish Government on
Selection of European good/new practices	This is an important strategy from a regional government that has decided to reinvest after the first 4-years plan. Moreover, this strategy innovates the process of refugees' integration.
Personal experiences	We involved experts on this topic to know better about the strategy.
Validation/evaluation external	The Scottish Government led an evaluation after the 2014 - 2017 plan.
Validation/evaluation by project team	Experts' opinions by interview
Sources	
Source(s) to the good/new practice	Interviews
Date of documentation	28/09/22

Figure 36 - New Scots strategy © Maria-Luisa Caputo

Checklist for good/new practice selection

The selected good/new practice ...	
is innovative.	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?:</p> <p>It creates collaborations between public and third sectors organization to develop local solutions for refugees' integration.</p>
develops creative solutions.	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?:</p> <p>It creates a system of coordination and for this initiatives and dedicated resources for them.</p>
succeeds in achieving its objective(s).	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?:</p> <p>Good feedbacks from the initiatives and satisfaction of the government that has confirmed the strategy.</p>
is ethical.	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?:</p> <p>It aims to create a more welcoming society for refugees.</p>
is fair.	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?:</p> <p>It aims to develop equal opportunities to access services and resources for refugees.</p>
Is been proven/evaluated (ideally: has been tested and validated) to work well and produce good results.	<p>Yes <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p>
is replicable.	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?:</p>

	The main framework condition to replicate this strategy is the political will of the government and the availability of resources to invest in this direction.
improves migrants' rights.	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?: Actually, it improves the possibility to obtain what they can rightfully ask for.</p>
is inclusive with regard to people with a migrant background.	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?: It is a dedicated strategy for refugees' integration.</p>
works with a whole of government approach.	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?: The government designs the strategy and invests the resources while the local authorities are called to collaborate with the third sector.</p>
improves the well-being of migrants	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?: This strategy main aim is to help people in the areas of employment, education, housing, health, communities and social connections.</p>
is gender sensitive.	<p>Yes <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p>
fosters societal diversity.	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?: The strategy has facilitated the mutual integration between newcomers and the hosting community "breaking" the monoculture of certain places and putting in contact locals with other cultures.</p>
develops possibilities for a safe and orderly regular migration.	<p>Yes <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p>

	<p>In what way?:</p> <p>It works more on the further steps of the migrations process.</p>
<p>fosters preparedness and resilience to migration events/crises.</p>	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?:</p> <p>Indeed, since the creation of this strategy this has been going through the Syrian, Afghani and Ukrainian refugees crisis.</p>
<p>realizes a participatory and/or multi-level governance approach.</p>	<p>Yes <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?:</p> <p>It mostly works at local level.</p>
<p>promotes effective funding mechanism.</p>	<p>Yes <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?:</p> <p>It is a full public funded strategy.</p>
<p>fosters effective monitoring and evaluation approaches.</p>	<p>Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>In what way?:</p> <p>Feedback from the initiatives.</p>